

**MODELING THE TRANSMISSION DYNAMICS OF
TWO STRAINS COVID-19 WITH OPTIMAL
CONTROL STRATEGIES FOR ITS SPREAD**

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**DEPARTMENT OF MATHEMATICAL SCIENCES
SCHOOL OF PHYSICAL SCIENCES
FEDERAL UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY AKURE
NIGERIA**

SEPTEMBER, 2025

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A THESIS IN THE DEPARTMENT OF MATHEMATICAL
SCIENCES, SCHOOL OF PHYSICAL SCIENCES,
SUBMITTED TO THE SCHOOL OF POSTGRADUATE
STUDIES, FEDERAL UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY,
AKURE, NIGERIA

IN PARTIAL FULFILMENT OF THE REQUIREMENTS
FOR THE AWARD OF DOCTOR OF PHILOSOPHY
(Ph.D) DEGREE IN MATHEMATICS OF THE FEDERAL
UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY, AKURE, NIGERIA

SEPTEMBER, 2025

DECLARATION

I solemnly declare that this thesis is the result of my independent research efforts and accurately reflects the work I have undertaken. It has not been submitted, in whole or in part, for the award of any degree or diploma at any other institution. All sources of information and references used have been duly acknowledged.

Candidate's Name: IDISI, OKE ISAIAH

Signature.....

Date.....

30-09-2025

CERTIFICATION

We hereby certify that this thesis entitled "Modeling The Transmission Dynamics of Two Strains COVID-19 with Optimal Control Strategies for its Spread" is the outcome of the research carried out by Idisi, Oke Isaiah, matriculation number MTS/19/3937 in the Department of Mathematical Sciences, The Federal University of Technology, Akure.

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Co-Supervisor's Name: Dr. K. M. OWOLABI

Signature.....

Date.....30-09-2025

DEDICATION

I dedicate this research work to Almighty God for His goodness, favor, provisions, compassion and mercies in my life and to my entire family members.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

”For He breaks down gates of bronze and cuts through bars of iron” (Psalm 107:16).

”He raises the poor from the dust and lifts the needy from the ash heap; He seats them with princes and bestows on them a throne of honor. For the foundations of the earth are the Lord’s; on them He has set the world” (1 Samuel 2:8). These words of Scripture profoundly capture my journey. It has been by the unfailing hand of the Almighty God that I have been sustained, strengthened, and brought to the successful completion of my PhD. Through every challenge and triumph, His grace has carried me. I am truly and deeply grateful to God.

I wish to express my profound gratitude to my supervisor, Professor T. T. Yusuf, for his exceptional guidance, unwavering support, and insightful contributions throughout the course of this program. His thoroughness, kindness, and meticulous approach to research have been truly inspiring and instrumental to my academic journey.

My heartfelt appreciation also goes to my co-supervisor, Dr. K. M. Owolabi, whose invaluable support and guidance have significantly enriched the quality of this research work.

I am deeply grateful to Euro-Mega Atlantic Nigeria for the opportunities and leverage provided during this program. I also sincerely appreciate my wonderful colleagues and mentors: Mr. Kingsley Onuah, Mr. Akeem Oyalowo, Mr. Sibashi Barnejiree, Mr. Samuel Akinrimisi, Mr. AJibade Joshua, Mr. Ekujumi Samson, Mr. Oliver Okon, and Mr. Igbasan Funmilayo for their support and encouragement. Special thanks to the Black in Mathematics Association (BMA) for their continuous inspiration and academic engagement. I particularly acknowledge Dr. Kayode Oshinubi, Dr. Adejimi

Adeniji, Dr. Samuel Akinyemi, Dr. Kazeem Akande, and Mr. Olaniyi Ebenezer and Dr. Oyebo Yakub for their support and mentorship. I also extend my gratitude to my dear coursemate, Dr. Evan Omorogie, for his camaraderie and encouragement.

I am sincerely appreciative of all the members of staff in the department for their support and contributions throughout the program. Furthermore, I am deeply thankful to my mother Mrs. Idisi Victoria, my beloved wife, Mrs. Idisi Favour, and our wonderful children, Oke Victory, Oke Deborah, and Oduhu Ereremena, for their love, patience, and steadfast support. My heartfelt thanks also go to my Lagos Mummy, Mrs. Elum Deborah, my elder brother Mr. Idisi Cyril and his lovely wife Mrs Idisi Edith for their constant care, encouragement, and prayers.

To all who have contributed to the success of this journey in one way or another, I remain ever grateful.

ABSTRACT

This thesis presents a comprehensive mathematical modeling framework to assess and optimize control strategies for the transmission dynamics of two co-circulating strains SARS-CoV-2 in Nigeria, with a specific focus on the original and Delta variants. Leveraging compartmental modeling and optimal control theory, the study formulates a deterministic model comprising susceptible, exposed, infected, hospitalized, recovered, and vaccinated compartments, further disaggregated by strain type. The model incorporates time-dependent control measures, namely preventive efforts, vaccination, and treatment interventions, aimed at mitigating infection spread and associated costs. The model analysis begins with theoretical validation, including positivity and boundedness of the model solution, derivation of disease-free and endemic equilibria. Basic reproduction numbers for each strain of the infection are computed using the next-generation matrix approach, serving as thresholds for disease persistence or elimination. Stability analyses are conducted to characterize the conditions under which the virus can be eradicated. The model exhibits backward bifurcation under certain parameter, emphasizing the necessity for rigorous control efforts even when reproduction numbers are below unity. Optimal control strategies are derived using Pontryagin's Maximum Principle, leading to a system of coupled differential equations comprising the state and adjoint variables. The forward-backward sweep method is implemented in MATLAB to numerically simulate the optimal trajectories under various scenarios. Sensitivity analyses is conducted to identify the most influential parameters, guiding policy decisions. Numerical results reveal that a combined strategy incorporating prevention, vaccination, and treatment is most effective in reducing infection prevalence and the overall cost of intervention.

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background on Epidemic

The idea that unseen entities could be responsible for causing illness has roots in ancient thought, with early speculation from philosophers like Aristotle (384–322 BC), who proposed the existence of imperceptible agents behind disease. This rudimentary notion gradually matured into a more structured theory during the 16th century, signaling a pivotal transformation in how diseases were understood and studied. The development of the microscope by Antonie van Leeuwenhoek (1632–1723) enabled scientists to observe microorganisms for the first time, offering concrete evidence for what would later be formalized as the germ theory of disease. Jacob Henle (1809–1885) laid the groundwork for this theory in 1840, which was subsequently expanded by key figures including Robert Koch (1843–1910), Joseph Lister (1827–1912), and Louis Pasteur (1822–1895) during the latter part of the 19th and early 20th centuries.

Today, our understanding of how diseases spread and how the immune system functions has grown substantially. For example, infections caused by viruses such as measles, influenza, rubella, and chickenpox typically result in long-lasting immunity against subsequent infections. In contrast, bacterial diseases like tuberculosis, gonorrhea, and meningitis often fail to induce lasting immunity, making repeated infections more likely (NCBI, 2023a).

1.1.1 Epidemic vs. Endemic

Diseases can be categorized based on their prevalence within specific populations as either epidemic or endemic. An epidemic is characterized by a sudden increase in disease incidence that affects a significant portion of the population over a short duration, often resulting in high mortality rates before subsiding. In contrast, endemic diseases persist within a population over extended periods, typically infecting a smaller fraction of individuals consistently (NCBI, 2023b). When an epidemic crosses international borders and impacts large populations globally, it is classified as a pandemic.

Pandemics have been a recurrent phenomenon throughout human history, shaping civilizations and often altering the course of societal development. One of the most infamous pandemics was the Black Death (bubonic plague), which began in 1346 and ravaged Europe, killing an estimated one-third of the continent's population. The plague, believed to have originated in Asia, spread rapidly across Europe and became endemic, with recurring outbreaks over a span of 300 years. A notable resurgence occurred during the Great Plague of London between 1656 and 1666, after which the disease gradually faded from the continent (WIKI, 2024).

Smallpox, another devastating pandemic, was responsible for over 300 million deaths in the 19th century alone. Another major health crisis occurred in 1918 with the emergence of the Spanish Flu (H1N1 influenza), which affected nearly one third of the global population. The pandemic resulted in an estimated 20 to 100 million deaths, making it one of the most devastating outbreaks in human history (WIKI, 2024).

Infectious diseases have continued to emerge and re-emerge in modern times. The identification of the human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) in the early 1980s marked the beginning of the global HIV/AIDS epidemic. Since then, the disease has led to the

deaths of approximately 25 million people, with about 33 million individuals currently living with HIV. Malaria also remains a persistent global health issue, infecting hundreds of millions annually and causing nearly two million deaths each year.

In addition to these, other infectious diseases such as cholera, hemorrhagic fevers, and plague continue to appear sporadically in certain regions. Meanwhile, illnesses like malaria, tuberculosis, HIV/AIDS, typhoid, cholera, and schistosomiasis have become endemic in many low- and middle-income countries. Their recurrence underscores the enduring threat posed by infectious diseases despite significant advancements in diagnostics, treatment, and prevention.

Despite remarkable progress in medical science over the past century, infectious diseases continue to account for a large share of global morbidity and mortality, particularly in resource-limited settings. Data from sub-Saharan Africa, for instance, indicate that more than 50% of all deaths are attributable to infectious causes (Moyo *et al.*, 2023). This high disease burden places considerable pressure on healthcare infrastructure and undermines economic development. Furthermore, infectious diseases not only affect human populations but also disrupt animal health and agricultural productivity, complicating efforts to manage outbreaks comprehensively.

The persistence of infectious diseases is driven by multiple interconnected factors, including ecological complexity, rapid genetic adaptation of pathogens, and the continuous emergence of novel infectious agents. These challenges suggest that infectious diseases will remain a significant global health concern in the years ahead.

In response to disease outbreaks, public health officials are often confronted with key questions such as:

- i. How many individuals will be infected?

- ii. How many will require treatment?
- iii. For how long will the epidemic persist in the community?
- iv. Does infection confer immunity against subsequent episodes?
- v. What intervention strategies (e.g., treatment, vaccination, quarantine) should be implemented to mitigate the epidemic's impact?

These questions highlight the complexity of managing infectious disease outbreaks and the importance of preparedness and response strategies. Despite ongoing advancements in medical and public health interventions, the dynamic nature of infectious diseases continues to pose significant challenges worldwide.

Mathematical modeling serves as an indispensable tool in understanding infectious diseases. Through these models, researchers can estimate critical epidemic thresholds, including the basic reproduction number and measures of disease burden such as morbidity, mortality, and attack rates. They also enable the analysis of the efficacy of various preventive and therapeutic interventions. Furthermore, modeling aids in developing and testing theories by examining how sensitive model outcomes are to parameter changes. Such models provide deeper insights into the spread of infections in real-world contexts, accounting for the complexities of disease transmission. Lastly, they contribute to identifying trends and making predictions about epidemic behavior, which is crucial for effective public health planning and response. Through these methodologies, public health officials can develop informed strategies to combat infectious diseases effectively (WIKI, 2023; Kumar, 2023).

1.1.2 The Foundation of Mathematical Epidemiology

The application of mathematical modeling in tracking the transmission dynamics of infectious diseases has a rich history dating back to the eighteenth century. A notable early example is Daniel Bernoulli's pioneering work on smallpox in 1760. Bernoulli developed a mathematical model to evaluate the effectiveness of variolation, a precursor to vaccination, which ultimately demonstrated that this intervention could enhance individual life expectancy. His innovative approach included the concept of differential mortality, allowing him to estimate death rates attributable to smallpox and other diseases. This methodology has since been utilized to approximate mortality rates in historical epidemics, such as the influenza pandemic of 1918 (CDC, 1990; Plana-Ripoll *et al.*, 2020). The late nineteenth and early twentieth centuries marked significant advancements in mathematical epidemiology, driven by both public health physicians and biologists. Key figures in this evolution included En'ko , Hammer, Brownlee, Rose, McKendrick, and Kermack (En'Ko, 1889; Hammer, 1906; Brownlee, 1907; Ross, 1911; Kermack & McKendrick, 1972). Following Bernoulli's foundational model, various mathematical frameworks emerged to better understand disease dynamics.

In 1906, Ronald Ross made a groundbreaking discovery regarding malaria transmission; he identified mosquitoes as the vectors responsible for spreading the disease between humans. Ross subsequently developed a mathematical model that illustrated how reducing mosquito populations could effectively control malaria outbreaks. His work introduced the epidemic threshold concept, which posits that an epidemic can only occur if the density of susceptible individuals surpasses a critical threshold (Plana-Ripoll *et al.*, 2020; Martin & Preston, 1994). This principle has become a cornerstone of modern epidemiological theory.

Two decades later, Kermack and McKendrick expanded upon Ross's theories, demonstrating that if the population of susceptible individuals remains below this critical threshold, an epidemic cannot be initiated. Their contributions laid the groundwork for contemporary mathematical biology and have influenced numerous studies on infectious disease dynamics ever since (Kermack & McKendrick, 1972).

The early model developed by Kermack and McKendrick to describe the transmission dynamics of bubonic plague is presented as (Kermack & McKendrick, 1972)

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{dS}{dt} &= -\frac{\beta SI}{N}, \\ \frac{dI}{dt} &= \frac{\beta SI}{N} - \alpha I, \\ \frac{dR}{dt} &= \alpha I.\end{aligned}\tag{1.1}$$

The mathematical model under consideration categorizes the total population $N(t)$ into three epidemiological compartments: susceptible individuals $S(t)$, infected individuals $I(t)$, and those who have either recovered or been removed from the infectious pool $R(t)$. This yields the population identity $N(t) = S(t) + I(t) + R(t)$. The parameter β defines the rate of effective contact leading to transmission, while α characterizes the per capita rate at which infected individuals recover or are otherwise removed from the population. Disease transmission occurs when a susceptible individual interacts with an infectious one, and recovery or removal happens at rate α . The system's evolution is determined solely by its initial values and fixed rules, classifying it as a deterministic model.

While this basic SIR framework provides foundational insights into infectious disease dynamics, it has been generalized to reflect more realistic epidemiological scenarios. These adaptations may include factors such as waning immunity or a latent phase,

where individuals have been infected but are not yet capable of spreading the disease. Such modifications lead to alternative compartmental structures like SIS, SIRS, SEIR, SEIRS, SEIRE, and SEIRI models. In these extensions, the E compartment denotes exposed individuals who are infected but not yet infectious or symptomatic (Isaac, 2017). These enhanced models build upon the classical formulation introduced by (Kermack & McKendrick, 1972) to better capture the complexity of real-world disease transmission.

1.2 Reproduction Number and Equilibrium Analysis

To fully grasp why a disease can persist within a population and become endemic, a deeper examination of the governing system of equations is essential. This requires an in-depth analysis to investigate how perturbations in the system influence the dynamics, leading to potential instability and shifts in disease behavior. Such an approach allows for a clearer understanding of the fundamental reproduction threshold, which determines the conditions for disease persistence or eradication. Additionally, it sheds light on the bifurcation structure of the system, revealing critical transition points where small changes in parameters can result in significant alterations in disease outcomes. Through this analytical framework, we can gain insights into the mechanisms that drive endemicity and the factors that contribute to sustained transmission within a population.

1.2.1 Basic Reproduction Number

The basic reproduction number, denoted as R_0 , is a central concept in the study of infectious disease dynamics. It quantifies the expected number of new infections caused by a single infectious individual in a population where all individuals are susceptible (Song & Lou, 2013; Diekmann *et al.*, 2010). While the origins of R_0 can be traced back to demographic modeling, it later found important applications in fields such as ecology and

epidemiology (Isaac, 2017). However, its critical role in shaping the theoretical foundation of modern epidemiology became more apparent and widely appreciated starting in the 1980s.

1.2.2 Forward Bifurcation

The basic reproduction number, R_0 , plays a crucial role in determining the potential for an infectious disease to invade and persist within a population. When $R_0 > 1$, an infected individual is expected to transmit the disease to more than one susceptible person on average, which can lead to sustained transmission and possible outbreaks. On the other hand, if $R_0 < 1$, the infection is unlikely to spread widely and will eventually disappear from the population (Anderson & May, 1991).

In the context of mathematical models of disease transmission, two primary equilibrium states are typically observed: the disease-free equilibrium (DFE) and the endemic equilibrium point (EEP). The DFE describes a situation where the disease is entirely absent from the population, whereas the EEP characterizes a long-term state in which the infection remains present at a constant level.

The shift between these equilibria is governed by a transcritical bifurcation that occurs at the critical threshold $R_0 = 1$. This threshold acts as a key marker in epidemiological modeling: when $R_0 < 1$, the DFE is stable, indicating that the disease cannot persist and will fade out over time. However, once R_0 exceeds 1, the DFE loses its stability, and the system transitions toward a stable endemic equilibrium, reflecting ongoing transmission within the population (Van Den Driessche & Watmough, 2002).

Figure 1.1: Forward Bifurcation

This shift in stability, depicted in Figure 1.1, illustrates a typical forward bifurcation, where the force of infection at equilibrium represented on the y axis of Figure 1.1 changes as a function of R_0 . The diagram demonstrates that when $R_0 < 1$ the force of infection is zero, reinforcing a stable disease-free state. However, once the threshold is crossed ($R_0 > 1$) a stable endemic equilibrium emerges, leading to sustained disease transmission (Brauer, 2017).

1.2.3 Backward Bifurcation

For many years, the condition ($R_0 < 1$) has been widely regarded as a fundamental requirement for disease eradication (Diekmann *et al.*, 2010). However, recent theoretical studies have questioned this assumption, suggesting that this criterion alone may not always be sufficient (Dushoff *et al.*, 1998; Roberts & Heesterbeek, 2023). Instead, the concept of backward bifurcation provides an alternative perspective. This phenomenon demonstrates that even when ($R_0 < 1$) and the disease-free equilibrium (DFE) is stable, a stable endemic equilibrium may still exist simultaneously (Dushoff *et al.*, 1998). Consequently, a population could remain in an endemic state where the disease persists

indefinitely, despite R_0 being less than one. When multiple stable equilibria coexist, the eventual state a population reaches depends on the initial distribution of individuals across its sub-populations (Kribs-Zaleta, 1990). A typical bifurcation diagram illustrates the key characteristics of backward bifurcation. Notably, when R_0 falls within the range $(0 < R_c < R_0 < 1)$, where R_c as represented in Figure (1.2) represents a critical threshold e.g., ($R_c = 0.4$), three equilibria emerge. Among these, the middle equilibrium remains unstable, while the other two DFE and endemic equilibrium are both stable (Song & Lou, 2013). If R_0 is below R_c , only the DFE exists and remains stable.

The presence of multiple equilibria can lead to interesting dynamical behaviors, particularly when R_0 changes gradually. For instance, if the number of infected individuals is close to extinction ($I^* = 0$), and R_0 slowly increases beyond the threshold of $R_0 = 1$, the infection level may suddenly jump to a stable endemic equilibrium ($I^* > 0$) (Kribs-Zaleta, 1990). However, if a population is near the endemic equilibrium and R_0 slowly decreases below one, rather than shifting to the DFE, the infected population may stabilize at the endemic equilibrium. Thus, when R_0 drops below R_c , the infected population collapses to zero as the endemic equilibrium disappears. Such abrupt transitions are characteristic of nonlinear dynamical systems and are associated with hysteresis, where multiple endemic equilibria coexist when $R_0 > 1$ [see Figure 1.2]

Figure 1.2: Backward Bifurcation

1.3 COVID-19

The COVID-19 pandemic, caused by the novel coronavirus SARS-CoV-2, has profoundly impacted global health, economies, and societies, since its emergence in late 2019. This unprecedented crisis has affected 215 countries/territories, leading to a devastating global pandemic, within the first two years of the COVID-19 pandemic, more than 450 million cases were reported worldwide, more than 100 million in the EU/EEA and 30 million in African alone (ECDPC, 2023). SARS-CoV-2 infectious disease is characterized by a wide spectrum of symptoms ranging from mild respiratory illness to severe pneumonia and multi-organ failure, leading to widespread morbidity and mortality across Europe, North America, Asia, South America, Africa, and Oceania continent [see Figure 1.3]. Presently, the pandemic continues to pose significant challenges to public health systems worldwide.

Figure 1.3: John Hopkins COVID-19 Dash Board

1.3.1 Origin and Spread of COVID-19

The emergence of COVID-19 was initially documented in December 2019 in Wuhan, located in the Hubei Province of China. The first reports involved a series of pneumonia cases with an unknown cause. Investigations suggested a zoonotic origin, with bats considered a likely reservoir host, and pangolins posited as a potential intermediary in the transmission to humans (Lu *et al.*, 2020). Due to its high transmissibility, the virus later identified as SARS-CoV-2 spread rapidly across regions and countries, with international mobility significantly accelerating its global reach. In acknowledgment of the public health risks posed by the virus, the World Health Organization (WHO) classified COVID-19 as a Public Health Emergency of International Concern on February 11, 2020.

1.3.2 Viral Structure of SARS-CoV-2

SARS-CoV-2 virions are generally spherical, with diameters ranging between 60 and 140 nanometers (approximately 2.4×10^{-6} to 5.5×10^{-6} inches), which is typical for viruses within the Coronaviridae family. The relatively small size of the virion facilitates its ability to remain suspended in the air and be transmitted via respiratory droplets. This dimension is particularly relevant for understanding its transmission characteristics and

the design of mitigation strategies.

Global Viral Mass Estimates

It has been estimated that the cumulative mass of all SARS-CoV-2 virions present within the global human population ranges from 0.1 to 10 kilograms. This approximation underscores the extensive replication capacity of the virus and serves to emphasize the scale of the pandemic in epidemiological and biomedical terms.

1.3.3 Structural Proteins of SARS-CoV-2

SARS-CoV-2, like other coronaviruses, encodes four major structural proteins that are essential for its assembly, infectivity, and pathogenicity: the Spike (S), Envelope (E), Membrane (M), and Nucleocapsid (N) proteins.

1. **Spike (S) Protein:** This surface glycoprotein plays a central role in host cell entry. It is made up of two functional subunits: S1, which harbors the receptor-binding domain (RBD), and S2, which mediates membrane fusion. The S1 subunit binds to the host cell receptor angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 (ACE2), initiating viral attachment (Huang *et al.*, 2020). The spike protein undergoes cleavage by host proteases into S1 and S2 during viral assembly, a process that enhances viral infectivity (Satarker & Nampoothiri, 2020).
2. **Envelope (E) Protein:** The E protein contributes to virion assembly and budding. It forms ion channels (viroporins) that aid in altering the host cell environment, thereby facilitating efficient virus release and contributing to pathogenic effects (Kakavandi *et al.*, 2023).
3. **Membrane (M) Protein:** This is the most abundant structural protein and is vital

in determining the virion's shape. It interacts with other structural components to orchestrate virus assembly within the host cell (Kakavandi *et al.*, 2023).

4. **Nucleocapsid (N) Protein:** The N protein binds tightly to the viral RNA genome, forming a ribonucleoprotein complex that stabilizes and protects the genome. It is essential for the regulation of viral RNA synthesis and plays roles in host immune response modulation (Kakavandi *et al.*, 2023).

The concerted functions of these structural proteins not only define the viral architecture but also impact its ability to spread and evade immune responses. In particular, the S protein is a primary target for neutralizing antibodies and vaccine design. Insight into these molecular components has been instrumental in developing antiviral therapeutics and prophylactic interventions.

Figure 1.4: SARS-CoV-2 Structural Proteins

1.3.4 Symptomatology of COVID-19

COVID-19 manifests across a wide clinical spectrum. Common symptoms include fever, dry cough, fatigue, muscle or joint pain, shortness of breath, and anosmia (loss of smell) or ageusia (loss of taste). While many individuals exhibit only mild to moderate symptoms, others may experience severe complications. Epidemiological studies suggest that approximately 25% to 33% of infections are asymptomatic, particularly among younger age groups such as children and adolescents (Li *et al.*, 2022; Zheng, 2020).

1.3.4.1 Progression to Severe Illness

In susceptible individuals, especially the elderly and those with underlying health conditions such as cardiovascular disorders, diabetes, or obesity, the infection may escalate to more critical stages. These include acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS), septic shock, and multi-organ failure (Laue *et al.*, 2021). Mortality rates are notably higher among older adults, a trend observed across multiple national and international studies.

1.3.4.2 Clinical Severity Classification

COVID-19 presentations are generally classified into mild, moderate, and severe categories:

- **Mild cases:** These involve general symptoms like fever, sore throat, and cough, without signs of pneumonia.
- **Moderate cases:** Patients may develop clinical pneumonia but typically do not require supplemental oxygen.
- **Severe cases:** Marked by respiratory distress (e.g., respiratory rate exceeding 30 breaths per minute) or oxygen saturation falling below 93%, these cases often

necessitate hospitalization and advanced medical care (Li *et al.*, 2022).

1.3.4.3 Multi-Organ Involvement

Though COVID-19 is primarily a respiratory illness, it can affect multiple systems in the body. Documented complications include cardiovascular dysfunction, acute kidney injury, gastrointestinal symptoms, and various neurological manifestations. These extrapulmonary effects illustrate the systemic nature of SARS-CoV-2 and underscore the importance of multidisciplinary management approaches (Huang *et al.*, 2020).

1.3.5 Epidemiology and Transmission of COVID-19

COVID-19 exhibits human-to-human transmission primarily through respiratory droplets and aerosols expelled during coughing, sneezing, or talking (WHO, 2019)

Figure 1.5: SARS-Cov-2 Transmission Dynamics:
Source: <https://www.mdpi.com/1660-4601/18/2/395/#>

However findings has reveal that asymptomatic and pre-symptomatic individuals can also transmit the virus, contributing to its stealthy spread within communities. The

virus's incubation period ranges from two to fourteen days, during which infected individuals can unknowingly transmit the virus, complicating containment efforts (WHO, 2020).

1.3.6 Variants of SARs-Cov-2

Viruses commonly undergo changes and evolve as they spread among people over time. When these alterations reach a notable level compared to a previously identified virus, these new virus types are termed "variants." To detect variants, scientists analyze the genetic material of viruses through sequencing and then compare them to identify differences indicating changes . Since 2020, SARS-CoV-2, the virus responsible for COVID-19, has been spreading and evolving globally (CDC, 2023). These changes have led to the identification of variants in numerous countries worldwide. The most significant of these variants are categorized into three groups: variants under monitoring (VUM), variants of interest (VOI), and variants of concern (VOC).

- i A Variant Under Monitoring (VUM) is a term used to signal to public health authorities that a SARS-CoV-2 variant may require prioritized attention and monitoring. The main objective of this category is to investigate if this variant (and others closely related to it) may pose an additional threat to global public health as compared to other circulating variants.
- ii A Variant of Interest (VOI) is a term used to describe a SARS-CoV-2 variant with changes that are known to affect how the virus behaves or its potential impact on human health. This can include, for example, its ability to spread, its ability to cause serious disease, or how easily it may be detected or treated. A VOI may also be identified because it has an increased ability to spread when compared with

other circulating variants, suggesting a potential emerging risk to global public health.

- iii A Variant of Concern (VOC) is a term that describes a SARS-CoV-2 variant that meets the definition of a (VOI), but also meets at least one of the following criteria when compared with other variants: (a):it can cause a detrimental change in disease severity; (b) there is a significant decrease in the effectiveness of available vaccines in protecting against severe disease. these variants includes Epsilon, Zeta, Eta, Theta, Iota, Kappa, and Lambda (Integrity, 2024).

1.3.7 COVID-19 Vaccine

The COVID-19 vaccine is designed to protect people from the coronavirus infection known as COVID-19. It works by priming the immune system to identify and combat the SARS-CoV-2 virus, which causes the disease. Typically, the vaccine contains either a small, harmless component of the virus—such as a fragment of its spike protein—or genetic instructions that prompt cells to produce a protein that stimulates an immune response. When someone receives the vaccine, their body’s immune system produces antibodies and activates other defense mechanisms that can recognize and remember the virus. This immune memory helps protect the vaccinated individual from becoming seriously ill if they encounter the virus later on.

There are several types of COVID-19 vaccines, each developed using different scientific approaches. These include mRNA vaccines (like Pfizer-BioNTech and Moderna), viral vector vaccines (such as Oxford-AstraZeneca and Johnson & Johnson), protein subunit vaccines, and inactivated or live-attenuated vaccines [refer to Figure 1.6]. All of these vaccines have undergone extensive clinical testing to confirm their safety and effectiveness before receiving approval from regulatory bodies such as the U.S. Food and Drug

Administration (FDA) or the European Medicines Agency (EMA). As shown in Figure 1.8, there is a noticeable disparity in vaccine distribution among countries worldwide.

Figure 1.6: SARs-Cov-2 Vaccine development History

COVID-19 vaccine doses administered by manufacturer, European Union

All doses, including boosters, are counted individually.

Data source: Official data collated by Our World in Data

OurWorldInData.org/covid-vaccinations | CC BY

Figure 1.7: SARs-C0v-2 vaccine administration

The widespread administration of COVID-19 vaccines has been a key tool in controlling the pandemic by reducing the severity of illness, hospitalizations, and deaths associated with COVID-19, as well as decreasing transmission of the virus within communities (ECDPC, 2023). There was an argent need to develop and introduce a vaccines against COVID-19 in a shorter period of time to cushion the spread of the disease compared to the traditional vaccine development whose timeline are generally measured in years or decades before mass administration as depicted in Figure 1.7. An example is the Ebola vaccine that took approximately 27 years to develop. However, more than 5.55 million (70.6%) people worldwide have received a dose of a COVID-19 vaccine, and 5,894 are now administered each day while about 32.7% of people in low-income countries have received at least one dose as depicted in Figure 1.8

Figure 1.8: Global COVID-19 Vaccine Coverage

Previous analysis has shown that to minimise mortality and severity and transmission of SARs-Cov-2 disease, it has been recommended to prioritise vaccination for those members of the community who are most likely to become seriously ill and regions with high endemicity. (ECDPC-2, 2023)

1.3.8 Public Health Response

Governments and public health organizations have implemented a range of measures to control the spread of COVID-19. These include widespread testing, contact tracing, quarantine and isolation protocols, social distancing measures, mask mandates, and travel restrictions. The development and deployment of vaccines have been instrumental in mitigating the impact of the pandemic, although challenges persist in achieving equitable global vaccine distribution.

1.3.8.1 Impact on Health Systems and Society

The COVID-19 pandemic has strained healthcare systems worldwide, leading to shortages of medical supplies, hospital beds, and healthcare personnel. The psychological and social impact of the pandemic, including increased rates of anxiety, depression, and social isolation, has been profound. Disruptions to education, employment, and everyday life have further underscored the far-reaching consequences of the pandemic beyond its immediate health effects.

1.3.9 Challenges and Future Outlook

Although significant progress has been made in the areas of vaccine development and clinical management, the COVID-19 pandemic still presents numerous unresolved challenges. The continuous emergence of new variants, coupled with vaccine skepticism and disparities in healthcare access, hampers global containment efforts. Addressing these challenges demands persistent international collaboration, strategic investments in health systems, and sustained scientific inquiry aimed at deepening our understanding of viral evolution and improving intervention effectiveness. Future success in controlling the pandemic will rely heavily on adaptive response strategies informed by both data

and evolving public health priorities.

In summary, this introduction provides a comprehensive overview of the COVID-19 pandemic, encompassing its origins, epidemiology, clinical manifestations, structure of the virus, different variants of SARS-Cov-2, public health response, societal impact, and future outlook.

1.4 Justification

Although a wide range of mathematical models have been proposed to investigate the transmission dynamics of the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic, relatively few research have focused on the coexistence and interaction of multiple strains of COVID-19. Notable studies in this area include (Ngonghala *et al.*, 2023; Tchoumi *et al.*, 2022; Avila-Ponce *et al.*, 2022; Gonzalez-Parra *et al.*, 2021; Arruda *et al.*, 2021), which underscore the complexity of modeling dual-strain epidemics. However, the ongoing emergence of novel SARS-CoV-2 variants and the persistence of recurrent waves continue to present serious global health challenges, often leading to increased morbidity and mortality.

This study is motivated by the pressing need to enhance our understanding of how multiple strains of SARS-CoV-2 interact within populations, and to develop targeted intervention strategies that can minimize their spread. In particular, we aim to explore and recommend strategies that are not only epidemiologically effective but also economically viable. To achieve this, the analysis employs both the Efficiency Index (EI) and the Incremental Cost-Effectiveness Ratio (ICER) to identify optimal combinations of control interventions capable of containing dual-strain outbreaks.

1.5 Research Questions

This research investigates the dynamics of two co-circulating strains of COVID-19 in the Nigeria population and formulates optimal control problem (OPC) aimed at reducing infection rates. Drawing insights from previous studies on diseases such as tuberculosis, influenza, chickenpox, and some sexually transmitted diseases. This research emphasizes the importance of timely public health interventions and vaccine strategies in controlling multi-strains epidemics.

Accordingly, the study seeks to answer the following research questions:

- i What are the key factors responsible for the continuous spread of different strains of SARS-CoV-2 disease ?
- ii How does the emergence of the new delta strain of COVID-19 affect the effective control for the spread of COVID-19 ?
- iii What combinations of control measures can be deployed to effectively suppress the simultaneous spread of dual strains of SARS-CoV-2 disease ?

1.6 Aim and Objectives

The aim is to model the emergence of two co-circulating strain of COVID-19 epidemics as an optimal control problem with a view to unveiling the most effective strategies that can remarkably reduce new cases of the dual strain of SARS-CoV-2 disease.

The objectives of this research are to:

- i Develop a comprehensive mathematical model that accurately captures the real-life dynamics of two co-circulating strains of COVID-19;

- ii Quantitatively analyze the model to show that it is mathematically and epidemiologically well-posed;
- iii Determine model equilibrium solutions with criteria for their respective stability established, derive model basic reproduction number, and carry out relevant sensitivity analysis;
- iv Formulate the prevailing two co-circulating strains COVID-19 epidemic as an optimal control problem and solve it appropriately to optimize impact of the disease management cum control strategies; and
- v Simulate numerical results to determine the optimal control strategy that would effectively address COVID-19 dual strains epidemics in the most cost-effective manner.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

COVID-19, caused by the SARS-CoV-2 virus, was first identified on December 31, 2019, and quickly evolved into a global crisis impacting regions across Europe, North America, Asia, South America, Africa, and Oceania. The pandemic's reach was extensive, affecting 215 countries and territories and leaving a profound mark on public health worldwide. Recognizing the gravity of the outbreak, the World Health Organization (WHO) classified COVID-19 as a Public Health Emergency of International Concern on February 11, 2020 (WHO, 2019). This study seeks to examine the emergence and spread of COVID-19 through three distinct transition phases observed globally.

- a) The first phase focuses on the emergence of the disease, its rapid spread, and the initial response to contain it.
- b) The second phase covers the era of vaccination efforts to combat the disease.
- c) The third phase addresses the emergence of multiple strains of the virus and the challenges posed by its Variants of Concern (VoC).

These transitions provide essential insights into the evolution and impact of COVID-19 on a global scale.

2.1.1 The Emergence of SARS-CoV-2 Virus

The emergence of severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) gave rise to a global pandemic characterized by significant concern due to its symptoms and

high mortality rate, particularly in the absence of effective vaccines or treatments. The unprecedented scale of the outbreak led to the urgent need for preventive and therapeutic strategies against COVID-19, highlighting the importance of understanding the virus's transmission dynamics within human populations. However, during this early phase, significant efforts were dedicated to developing mathematical models capable of predicting the spread of COVID-19.

During this period, the primary means of reducing COVID-19 transmission worldwide involved non-pharmaceutical interventions (NPIs), including measures such as physical distancing, mask-wearing, quarantines, school and business closures, and travel restrictions. Given this context, numerous mathematical modeling approaches were employed to analyze the disease's transmission patterns and to evaluate the potential effectiveness of various control and mitigation strategies in populations globally.

For instance, Iboi *et al.* (2020) develop a mathematical model to study the transmission dynamics and control of COVID-19 in Nigeria. Using data published by the Nigerian Center for Disease Control (NCDC), the study assesses the community-wide impact of various control and mitigation strategies in specific locations, particularly Kano, Lagos, and the Federal Capital Territory (FCT-Abuja). Below is the symmetric diagram, model equations, and parameter descriptions for the proposed model. Their model extends the classical SIR model (Kermack & McKendrick, 1972) by dividing the population into mutually exclusive compartments: susceptible $S(t)$, exposed $E(t)$, symptomatically infectious $I_s(t)$, asymptotically infectious $I_a(t)$, hospitalized $I_h(t)$, and recovered $R(t)$. The total population is defined as:

$$N(t) = S(t) + E(t) + I_s(t) + I_a(t) + I_h(t) + R(t)$$

below is the Symmetric diagram describing the flow in each compartment while the governing system of equations is presented in equation 2.1

$$\begin{aligned}
\dot{S} &= -\beta_s(1 - \epsilon_m c_m) \frac{I_s}{N} S - \beta_a(1 - \epsilon_m c_m) \frac{I_a}{N} S, \\
\dot{E} &= -\beta_s(1 - \epsilon_m c_m) \frac{I_s}{N} S - \beta_a(1 - \epsilon_m c_m) \frac{I_a}{N} S - \sigma E, \\
\dot{I}_s &= (1 - r) \sigma E - (\phi_s + \gamma_s + \delta_s) I_s, \\
\dot{I}_a &= r \sigma E - \gamma_a I_a, \\
\dot{I}_h &= \phi_s I_s - (\gamma_h + \delta_h) I_h, \\
\dot{R} &= \gamma_s I_s + \gamma_a I_a + \gamma_h I_h
\end{aligned} \tag{2.1}$$

In model 2.1, the parameters β_s and β_a correspond to the effective transmission rates for individuals who are symptomatically infectious (I_s) and asymptotically infectious (I_a), respectively. These parameters capture the frequency of interactions that can result in new infections. The variable c_M , where $0 < c_M < 1$, denotes the fraction of the population that adheres to proper and consistent use of face masks in public settings. Similarly, ϵ_M , with $0 < \epsilon_M < 1$, indicates the protective efficiency of the masks. The assumption $\beta_s \neq \beta_a$ allows the model to distinguish between the transmission dynamics of symptomatic versus asymptomatic individuals, acknowledging that clinical symptoms may influence behavioral and contact patterns.

Figure 2.1: Schematic Diagram (Enahoro *et al.*, 2020)

The parameter σ signifies the rate at which individuals in the exposed class progress to an infectious state, with $1/\sigma$ representing the average duration of the incubation period of COVID-19. A fraction r , where $0 < r \leq 1$, of those exposed do not develop symptoms and are instead classified as asymptotically infectious (I_a) following the incubation phase. The remaining portion, given by $1 - r$, become symptomatically infectious (I_s). Recovery from infection is governed by the parameters γ_s , γ_a , and γ_h , which denote the recovery rates for symptomatic (I_s), asymptomatic (I_a), and hospitalized (I_h) individuals, respectively. The transition rate from symptomatic infection to hospitalization or isolation is captured by ϕ_s . Furthermore, COVID-19-related fatality rates for the symptomatic and hospitalized compartments are modeled by δ_s and δ_h , respectively.

In 2020, given the absence of a safe and effective vaccine or antivirals for COVID-19, Ngonghala *et al.* (2020) developed a mathematical model to assess the impact of non-pharmaceutical interventions for controlling COVID-19.

Figure 2.2: Schematic Diagram for (Ngonghala *et al.*, 2020) model

The model described in equation (2.2) follows the foundational structure of the classical Kermack McKendrick framework Kermack & McKendrick (1972), extended to incorporate various non-pharmaceutical interventions (NPIs) aimed at reducing the spread of COVID-19 within a population. These interventions include public health measures such as social distancing, quarantine of individuals suspected of infection, isolation of confirmed cases, contact tracing, widespread testing, and the use of face masks.

In constructing the model (2.2), the total population at any given time t , denoted by $N(t)$, is divided into a set of epidemiologically distinct compartments. These include: non-quarantined susceptible individuals $S_u(t)$, quarantined susceptible individuals $S_q(t)$, non-quarantined exposed individuals $E_u(t)$, quarantined exposed individuals $E_q(t)$, symptomatically infectious individuals $I_u(t)$, asymptotically infectious individuals $I_a(t)$, hospitalized or isolated individuals $I_h(t)$, patients receiving intensive care $I_{icu}(t)$, and those who have recovered $R(t)$. Hence, the total population is given by:

$$N(t) = S_u(t) + S_q(t) + E_u(t) + E_q(t) + I_u(t) + I_a(t) + I_h(t) + I_{icu}(t) + R(t)$$

Based on this structure, the model equations are developed to capture the transitions between compartments under the influence of intervention strategies and natural disease

progression.

$$\begin{aligned}
\dot{S}_u &= -[(1-p) + (1-q)p + qp]\lambda S_u + \psi_q S_q, \\
\dot{S}_q &= (1-p)\lambda S_u - (\theta_j \lambda + \phi_q) S_q, \\
\dot{E}_u &= (1-q)p\lambda S_u - (\sigma_u + \alpha_u) E_u, \\
\dot{E}_q &= qp\lambda S_u + \alpha_u E_u + \theta_j \lambda S_q - \sigma_q E_q, \\
\dot{I}_u &= f_1 \sigma_u E_u - (\gamma_u + \phi_u + \delta_u) I_u, \\
\dot{I}_a &= (1-f_1-f_2)\sigma_u E_u + (1-r)\sigma_q E_q - (\gamma_a + \sigma_a + \delta_a) I_a, \\
\dot{I}_h &= f_2 \sigma_u E_u + \rho \sigma_q E_q + \phi_u I_u + \sigma_a I_a - (\gamma_h + \nu_h + \delta_h) I_h, \\
\dot{I}_{icu} &= \nu_h - (\gamma_{icu} + \delta_{icu}) I_{icu}, \\
\dot{R} &= \gamma_u I_u + \gamma_h I_h + \gamma_a I_a + \gamma_{icu} I_{icu}.
\end{aligned} \tag{2.2}$$

From the model analysis they concluded that strict social distancing measures were effective in reducing the pandemic burden, and early termination could lead to a devastating second wave in New York and the United state. They recommended from their findings that the use of effective face masks in public, combined with social distancing, could help eliminate COVID-19, and that adherence to these measures is crucial in minimizing the disease's spread.

In the early phase of the COVID-19 outbreak, Okuonghae & Omame (2020) developed a mathematical model to assess the effectiveness of various control strategies aimed at mitigating the transmission of the virus, with particular attention to the population dynamics in Lagos, Nigeria. The model categorizes the total human population at any time t , denoted by $N_h(t)$, into six distinct and non-overlapping compartments: susceptible individuals $S(t)$, exposed individuals $E(t)$, asymptomatic infectious individuals $A(t)$, symptomatic infectious individuals $I(t)$, infectious individuals who have been identified

through testing and subsequently isolated or hospitalized $I_D(t)$, and recovered individuals $R(t)$.

A key assumption in the model is that those within the $I_D(t)$ compartment are effectively isolated from the general population, thereby playing no role in further transmission of the disease. This structural assumption allows for the analysis of isolation effectiveness and its influence on epidemic outcomes.

Thus,

$$N_h(t) = S(t) + E(t) + A(t) + I(t) + I_D(t) + R(t)$$

Figure 2.3: Schematic Diagram from (Okuonghae & Omame, 2020)

Moreover, the model parameter are described in Table 2.3 and the governing model system of deterministic non-linear differential equations is represented in the system of

equations (2.3) below:

$$\begin{aligned}
\dot{S} &= -\frac{\beta_c(\alpha A + I)}{N_h - I_D}S, \\
\dot{E} &= \frac{\beta_c(\alpha A + I)}{N_h - I_D}S - \sigma E, \\
\dot{A} &= v\sigma E - (\theta + \gamma_a)A, \\
\dot{I} &= (1 - v)\sigma E - (\psi + \gamma_0 + \delta_0)I, \\
\dot{I}_D &= \theta A + \psi I - (\gamma_i + \delta_D)I_D, \\
\dot{R} &= \gamma_i I_D + \gamma_a A + \gamma_0 I.
\end{aligned} \tag{2.3}$$

v

Table 2.1: **Descriptions of Parameters in the COVID-19 Model (2.3)**

Parameter	Interpretation
β_c	Transmission rate per contact between susceptible and infectious individuals
σ	Rate at which exposed individuals become infectious
v	Proportion of newly infectious individuals who remain asymptomatic
α	Factor accounting for the reduced transmissibility of asymptomatic individuals (A class) compared to symptomatic individuals (I class)
$\gamma_a, \gamma_0, \gamma_i$	Recovery rates for individuals in the A , I , and I_D compartments, respectively
ψ	Rate at which symptomatic individuals are identified via contact tracing or testing
θ	Detection rate for asymptomatic individuals through testing or tracing
δ_0, δ_D	Disease-induced mortality rates for individuals in the I and I_D compartments, respectively

Through numerical simulation techniques, the authors examined how various public health strategies such as social distancing, face mask usage, and enhanced case identification via testing and contact tracing affect the transmission dynamics of COVID-19. Their findings include projections for cumulative reported cases and active infections under different levels of intervention uptake. The study revealed that if at least 55% of the population adopts consistent social distancing practices and proper face mask use in public spaces, the spread of the virus could be effectively brought under control, leading to eventual elimination.

A number of mathematical models were developed in the early stages of the pandemic to evaluate control measures and predict outbreak trajectories. These include works by Harapan *et al.* (2020); Bugalia *et al.* (2020); Mushayabasa *et al.* (2020); Mathew & Bruce (2020); Ivorra *et al.* (2019); Oke *et al.* (2021); Enahoro *et al.* (2020); Lin *et al.* (2020); Tang *et al.* (2020); Giordano *et al.* (2020). Among them, the comprehensive review conducted by Harapan *et al.* (2020) presented a detailed report on the clinical manifestations and laboratory findings associated with COVID-19, highlighting common abnormalities among patients. The review concluded that COVID-19 is a significant global health problem, emphasizing the need for improved disease surveillance systems and enhanced national laboratory capacity to effectively address the pandemic. In a related study, Bugalia *et al.* (2020) developed a compartmental model for COVID-19 transmission that incorporates public health interventions such as lockdowns, hospitalization, and quarantine strategies. The model's reproduction number and the conditions for both disease-free and endemic equilibria were derived and analyzed. The authors validated the model using epidemiological data from India, estimated key parameters, and projected future scenarios. Sensitivity analysis was conducted to identify influential parameters. Their findings stress the critical role of lockdown measures, suggesting that without stringent restrictions, the country could witness over six million infections. The study concludes that implementing strong public health measures is essential to control the epidemic's spread.

In the context of South Africa, Mushayabasa *et al.* (2020) constructed a mathematical model to evaluate how both government-imposed policies and individual behavioral responses influence COVID-19 transmission. Their model accounted for non-pharmaceutical interventions such as quarantine and lockdown. Using official data from

March to early May 2020, the authors demonstrated that a daily detection rate of at least 0.5 could significantly lower infection numbers. Moreover, in the absence of interventions, the epidemic peak would occur earlier. The study recommends proactive measures to delay the peak and reduce transmission, especially in high-risk communities.

Similarly, Mathew & Bruce (2020) introduced a behavioral SEIR model that accounts for public fear of infection and fatigue toward social distancing measures. Their framework revealed three possible epidemic outcomes: no outbreak, a contained outbreak, and an uncontrolled outbreak. Applying the model to global COVID-19 data, they showed that communities that strongly suppressed the first wave were better prepared for subsequent waves, whereas those with moderate control faced more severe resurgences. The study underscores the need for effective and sustained public health policies to manage future waves of infection.

Also in Nigeria, Ivorra *et al.* (2019) developed a community-based COVID-19 transmission model that incorporates social distancing, mask usage, and mass testing. The model recommends a minimum testing rate of 0.3 per day to effectively manage the outbreak. Their results advocate for rigorous adherence to face mask protocols and physical distancing to reduce transmission, especially considering the country's economic constraints. The recommended interventions align with global best practices and offer feasible solutions for national pandemic response.

Addressing the Nigerian epidemic, Oke *et al.* (2021) formulated an SEIHRD model that captures both undetected and detected infectious individuals, including hospitalized patients. The model was calibrated using data from January 28 to December 5, 2020. Key findings revealed the occurrence of backward bifurcation, indicating that reducing the transmission rate alone is insufficient for disease eradication. The authors emphasize

that strict compliance with COVID-19 guidelines is vital to mitigating transmission and mortality of the disease.

Enahoro *et al.* (2020) developed a mathematical model to assess the trajectory of the COVID-19 pandemic in Nigeria. The study highlights the importance of increasing diagnostic testing and robust contact tracing systems. It also stresses the critical role of personal hygiene practices, such as regular hand washing, physical distancing, and face mask usage. Furthermore, the study calls for adequate provision of protective equipment for healthcare workers to safeguard frontline responders and enhance pandemic control efforts.

Lin *et al.* (2020) developed a conceptual model tailored to the COVID-19 situation in Wuhan, China, incorporating both public behavior and government interventions, including travel restrictions, extended holidays, hospitalization, and quarantine. Drawing parallels with the 1918 influenza pandemic in London, their model estimated a case-fatality rate comparable to early COVID-19 levels in Wuhan. The framework successfully reproduced the epidemic curve and provided insights into future outbreak dynamics and underreporting rates.

Tang *et al.* (2020) developed a deterministic model that evaluates the impact of hospitalization and quarantine on COVID-19 transmission dynamics. This model was extended by Ngonghala *et al.* (2020) to include a more detailed breakdown of the infectious class distinguishing between isolated cases and those in intensive care. The refined model enabled assessment of various non-pharmaceutical interventions (NPIs) and their potential to suppress outbreak spread.

In another contribution, Giordano *et al.* (2020) presented a model to explore how different levels of quarantine influence COVID-19 transmission. Their study identifies the

contact rate and recovery rate of asymptomatic individuals as critical parameters for controlling outbreaks. The results emphasize the necessity of timely isolation and hospitalization in reducing transmission and managing healthcare system burdens.

Yusuf *et al.* (2022) proposed an optimal control model designed to identify the most effective combinations of interventions for minimizing the burden of COVID-19. The model includes four time dependent control measures: personal protection, testing and contact tracing for asymptomatic individuals, detection of symptomatic cases, and hospital treatment. By applying Pontryagin's Maximum Principle and solving the resulting system numerically via the forward-backward sweep method, the study concludes that a minimum of three control strategies especially when including personal protection can significantly reduce transmission. However, implementing all four controls yields the most cost effective and epidemiologically impactful outcome.

2.1.2 Vaccination Era

COVID-19, the disease resulting from SARS-CoV-2, first appeared in late 2019 and rapidly escalated into a global health crisis. Within just two years, it had affected over 450 million individuals globally, including more than 100 million cases in the EU/EEA and 30 million cases across Africa (ECDPC, 2023). Initially, mitigation strategies focused on limiting transmission by reducing interactions between infected and susceptible individuals. These measures included stay-at-home advisories, mask mandates, and social distancing. However, by the end of 2020, efforts shifted toward minimizing susceptibility by introducing vaccines.

Since Edward Jenner's groundbreaking work in 1796 on smallpox, vaccination has been a central tool in combating infectious diseases (Smith & McFadden, 2022). In the case of COVID-19, the global urgency necessitated an accelerated vaccine development

process, unlike traditional vaccine timelines which often span years or even decades. The scale and speed of the COVID-19 vaccine rollout were unprecedented, especially considering the virus's high transmissibility and associated mortality. For context, the Ebola vaccine required nearly 27 years from its development to widespread use.

To minimize severe disease outcomes and fatalities, early vaccination programs prioritized individuals most at risk of serious illness. Consequently, mass vaccination campaigns were swiftly deployed throughout the EU/EEA in an effort to reduce the spread and impact of COVID-19 (ECDPC-2, 2023).

In line with the previous statement, Bhattar *et al.* (2023) proposed a novel mathematical model that evaluates the role of vaccination in controlling COVID-19 outbreaks. The model divides the population into unvaccinated, first-dose vaccinated, and fully vaccinated individuals to capture distinct transmission dynamics. It was initially formulated using integer-order derivatives, then extended via Caputo fractional derivatives to incorporate memory effects. Model stability was assessed, and the reproduction number was derived. Using a numerical approach, the fractional-order system was simulated and validated against real data from India covering August 1, 2021, to July 21, 2022. The sensitivity analysis highlighted that the transmission and recovery rates among unvaccinated individuals significantly affect disease progression. Simulation results reinforced the need for stringent preventive practices and timely treatment, especially among the unvaccinated. Furthermore, the study emphasized that widespread vaccination is essential for curbing transmission in settings with ongoing community spread, such as India, and provided recommendations for guiding public health responses.

2.1.3 Multi-Strain Transmission and Vaccination Dynamics

Ngonghala *et al.* (2023) explored the effects of emerging variants, particularly Delta

and Omicron, on COVID-19 transmission in the United States. Their study incorporated vaccination, treatment, and mask usage into a mathematical model, which was calibrated with real case data from November 2021 to March 2022. They showed that when the control reproduction number \mathcal{R}_c is below one, the disease-free equilibrium is locally stable. Under conditions where disease-induced death is negligible and vaccine or natural immunity is retained, global stability of the model is achieved when $\mathcal{R}_c < 1$. Their results suggest that a combination of vaccination and booster doses could lead to the elimination of the disease, provided \mathcal{R}_c remains below unity. They also computed the threshold for vaccine-induced herd immunity, estimating that at least 68% of the population must be fully vaccinated (e.g., with Pfizer or Moderna) to suppress disease spread in the U.S. Notably, the study found that the Omicron variant had a reproduction number approximately 3.5 times that of Delta, implying a significant shift in dominance.

Building on this, Avila-Ponce *et al.* (2022) formulated a mathematical model integrating two competing virus strains alongside a vaccination intervention. The model estimated transmission, death, and recovery rates for each strain and was used to forecast the emergence of the Alpha variant and the potential impact of the Delta variant in 2021. Their analysis also identified the minimum vaccination coverage required to suppress each variant. However, they noted some limitations: the model did not consider seasonal effects or immune response variation due to single vs. double doses. Additionally, their model focused on only two variants, despite the presence of numerous SARS-CoV-2 strains globally, each with unique characteristics.

Similarly, Arruda *et al.* (2021) constructed a model that accounts for multiple strains and reinfections due to waning immunity. They incorporated an optimal control framework to balance disease mitigation efforts with economic costs. Their simulations, ap-

plied to the UK context, suggested that premature easing of interventions could trigger new waves of infections, necessitating stricter measures later. While both Arruda *et al.* (2021) and Gonzalez-Parra *et al.* (2021) considered variant dynamics, their models did not explicitly assess the role of vaccination in suppressing multi-strain outbreaks.

In summary, existing models offer important insights into the complex interplay of COVID-19 variants, transmission, and interventions. However, there remains a significant gap in evaluating how vaccination can influence the control of pandemics involving multiple co-circulating strains. To address this, we incorporate vaccination into our proposed mathematical model as a central control measure alongside cost effectiveness analysis. Our goal is to assess how a combination of strategies can effectively mitigate multi-strain COVID-19 spread.

Specifically, we develop a deterministic compartmental model tailored to the Nigerian population, accounting for the circulation of two major SARS-CoV-2 variants: Eta (B.1.525) and Delta (B.1.617.2). By including these strain-specific dynamics and associated interventions, our model seeks to understand the factors that contribute to endemicity in Nigeria and identify the most effective paths toward containment and eventual eradication.

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY

3.1 Model Formulation for Single Strain COVID-19 Transmission Dynamics

This section presents a compartmental model that captures the transmission dynamics of COVID-19, grounded in current epidemiological understanding and existing literature (Lynne, 2021; WHO, 2020). Due to the novel nature of the virus, especially during its early emergence, there were significant knowledge gaps in its spread and behavior, motivating the development of models that reflect real world transmission patterns.

The total population at any time t , denoted by $N(t)$, is partitioned into seven epidemiological classes: Susceptible $S(t)$, Vaccinated $V(t)$, Exposed $E(t)$, Asymptomatic Infectious $I_a(t)$, Symptomatic Infectious $I_s(t)$, Hospitalized (or Self-Isolated) $H(t)$, and Recovered $R(t)$. Mathematically, this is represented as:

$$N(t) = S(t) + V(t) + E(t) + I_a(t) + I_s(t) + H(t) + R(t).$$

The model structure is adapted from frameworks reported by (WHO, 2005; NCDC, 2020), which highlight that COVID-19 transmission primarily occurs through close contact with infectious individuals—whether asymptomatic, symptomatic, or hospitalized especially when preventive measures such as mask wearing and physical distancing are not followed. The model further assumes that vaccinated individuals may still acquire infection if they are exposed to infectious persons during unprotected interactions.

In this framework, individuals in the susceptible class (S) are infected at an effective contact rate β_1 . Parameters w and s , where $0 < (w, s) < 1$, account for partial protec-

tion due to adherence to non-pharmaceutical interventions (NPIs) like mask usage and physical distancing. The modification factors η and ε (with $0 < (\eta, \varepsilon) < 1$) reduce the effective transmission from infectious individuals due to varying levels of infectiousness or compliance with NPIs.

Vaccination is introduced at a constant rate ρ , increasing the vaccinated compartment V . However, vaccinated individuals are still susceptible to infection through a modified transmission rate σ . Newly infected individuals enter the exposed compartment E , from which a proportion $\theta\gamma$ progresses to the asymptomatic infectious class I_a , while the remaining $(1 - \theta)\gamma$ develops symptomatic infection (I_s). Additionally, some individuals in I_a may later develop symptoms at rate ϕ , thereby transitioning to the symptomatic class.

A proportion τ of symptomatic individuals, identified through contact tracing or voluntary testing, transitions into the hospitalized/self-isolation compartment H . Recovery occurs at rates ψ_1 , ψ_2 , and ψ_3 for the respective infectious compartments, moving individuals to the recovered class R . Temporary immunity is assumed to wane at rate m , returning individuals to the susceptible class. Disease-induced death rates for the symptomatic and hospitalized classes are given by δ_1 and δ_2 , respectively. Additionally, all compartments are subject to a natural mortality rate μ .

The model is governed by the following system of nonlinear ordinary differential equations:

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{dS}{dt} &= \Lambda + mR + \alpha V - \beta_1(1-w-s)\frac{(I_a + \eta I_s + \varepsilon H)S}{N} - (\mu + \rho)S, \\
\frac{dV}{dt} &= \rho S - \sigma(1-w-s)\frac{(I_a + \eta I_s + \varepsilon H)V}{N} - (\mu + \alpha)V, \\
\frac{dE}{dt} &= \beta_1(1-w-s)\frac{(I_a + \eta I_s + \varepsilon H)S}{N} + \sigma(1-w-s)\frac{(I_a + \eta I_s + \varepsilon H)V}{N} - (\gamma + \mu)E, \\
\frac{dI_a}{dt} &= (1-\theta)\gamma E - (\psi_1 + \phi + \mu)I_a, \\
\frac{dI_s}{dt} &= \theta\gamma E + \phi I_a - (\psi_2 + \tau + \delta_1 + \mu)I_s, \\
\frac{dH}{dt} &= \tau I_s - (\psi_3 + \delta_2 + \mu)H, \\
\frac{dR}{dt} &= \psi_1 I_a + \psi_2 I_s + \psi_3 H - (\mu + m)R.
\end{aligned}
\tag{3.1}$$

The proposed model dynamics is depicted by the flow diagram in Figure (3.1):

Figure 3.1: Schematic Diagram for the proposed Model (Single Strain Model)

while the state variables and the model parameters are described in Table (3.1).

Table 3.1: Summary of Variables and Parameters use in the Model (3.1)

Symbol	Description
S	population of individuals susceptible to infection
V	population of vaccinated individuals
E	population of individuals exposed to the virus
I_a	population of asymptomatic infectious individuals
I_s	population of symptomatic infectious individuals
H	population of hospitalized or self-isolating individuals
R	population of individuals who have recovered
Parameter	Description
Λ	Rate of new individuals entering the population
m, α	Rates of waning immunity in $V(t)$ and $R(t)$ classes, respectively
γ	Rate at which exposed individuals become infectious
ρ	Vaccination rate
θ	Proportion of exposed individuals developing symptoms
δ_1, δ_2	COVID-19-induced mortality rates in I_s and H classes
Ψ_1, Ψ_2, Ψ_3	Recovery rates from $I_a, I_s,$ and H compartments, respectively
ϕ	Rate of progression from presymptomatic to symptomatic infection
τ	Rate at which symptomatic individuals move to the H compartment
σ	Effective transmission rate to vaccinated individuals
β_1	Effective transmission rate to susceptible individuals
w	Proportion of the population using face masks
s	Proportion practicing physical distancing
η, ϵ	Reduction factors for infectiousness in I_s and H classes
$1/\mu$	Average life expectancy

It is important to note that system (3.1) is expressed in a compact form to support the analytical study of the model. Accordingly, the simplified formulation of the model equations, which will form the basis for the subsequent qualitative analysis, is provided below:

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{dS}{dt} &= \Lambda + mR + \alpha V - \beta XS - (\mu + \rho)S, \\
\frac{dV}{dt} &= \rho S - \sigma XV - (\mu + \alpha)V, \\
\frac{dE}{dt} &= \beta XS + \bar{\sigma} XV - k_1 E, \\
\frac{dI_a}{dt} &= (1 - \theta)\gamma E - (k_2 + \phi)I_a, \\
\frac{dI_s}{dt} &= \theta\gamma E + \phi I_a - k_3 I_s, \\
\frac{dH}{dt} &= \tau I_s - k_4 H, \\
\frac{dR}{dt} &= \psi_1 I_a + \psi_2 I_s + \psi_3 I_H - (\mu + m)R,
\end{aligned} \tag{3.2}$$

where $\beta = \beta_1(1 - w - s)$, $\sigma = \sigma_1(1 - w - s)$, $X = \frac{(I_a + \eta I_s + \varepsilon H)}{N}$, $k_1 = (\gamma + \mu)$, $k_2 = (\psi_1 + \mu)$, $k_3 = (\psi_2 + \delta_1 + \tau + \mu)$, $k_4 = (\psi_3 + \delta_2 + \mu)$.

with Initial conditions:

$$S(0) > 0, V(0) \geq 0, E(0) \geq 0, I_a(0) \geq 0, I_s(0) \geq 0, H(0) \geq 0, R(0) \geq 0. \tag{3.3}$$

However, to extend the analysis, equation (3.2) was further refined to formulate the co-circulating dual-strains model presented in equation (3.6).

3.2 Formulation of Mathematical Model for Dual Strain COVID-19 Transmission Dynamics

The proposed mathematical model is developed as a system of ordinary differential equations aimed at analyzing the transmission dynamics of two co-existing SARS-CoV-2 variants: the original (Eta) strain and the emerging (Delta) strain. These variants are reflective of the predominant strains currently observed in Nigeria. The extended SVEIHR model builds upon the single-strain framework introduced in Chapter Three (refer to equation 3.1), with modifications made to more accurately represent the disease dynamics.

3.2.1 Formulation of the Mathematical Model

The dual-strain SARS-CoV-2 model presented here incorporates key features of variant-based transmission, with the goal of capturing both the spread and control measures in Nigeria population. The total human population, denoted by $N(t)$, is divided into the following epidemiological compartments: susceptible individuals $S(t)$ (those at risk of infection), vaccinated individuals $V(t)$ (those who have completed a full vaccination regimen), hospitalized individuals $H(t)$ (active clinical cases under medical care), and recovered individuals $R(t)$. In addition, due to the circulation of multiple strains, the model distinguishes between exposed and infectious individuals for each variant: $E_1(t)$ and $I_1(t)$ for the original strain, and $E_2(t)$ and $I_2(t)$ for the new strain. Therefore, the total population at time t is expressed as:

$$N(t) = S(t) + V(t) + E_1(t) + I_1(t) + E_2(t) + I_2(t) + H(t) + R(t), \quad (3.4)$$

for $t \in [0, t]$, $t > 0$.

The model is constructed under the following realistic assumptions, consistent with available epidemiological evidence (CDC, 2023; Tillett *et al.*, 2021):

- i Every individual in the population has an equal probability of contracting either variant of SARS-CoV-2.
- ii The model does not account for simultaneous (co-)infection with both strains; however, it can be extended to similar dual-strain diseases.
- iii Approved vaccines provide protection against both strains, although with varying efficacy.
- iv All new entrants into the population (through birth or immigration) are susceptible.
- v The natural death rate μ applies uniformly to all compartments.
- vi Disease-induced mortality only occurs in the infectious (I_1, I_2) and hospitalized (H) compartments.
- vii Vaccinated, hospitalized, and recovered individuals are not strain-specific, but their progression rates differ by variant.
- viii The vaccination rate ρ satisfies $0 < \rho \leq 1$, reflecting efficacy bounds.
- ix Individuals in the hospitalized class either recover or die, implying no treatment failure pathway is considered.

Let Π represent the recruitment rate into the susceptible population. Natural death occurs at rate μ across all compartments. Infection spreads through effective contacts with infectious individuals, characterized by the forces of infection:

$$\lambda_1 = \frac{\beta_1(I_1 + \varepsilon_1 H)}{N}, \quad \lambda_2 = \frac{\beta_2(I_2 + \varepsilon_2 H)}{N}, \quad (3.5)$$

Equation 3.5 represents the distinct forces of infection for the two co-circulating COVID-19 strains, where λ_1 corresponds to the force of infection for the Eta strain, and λ_2 represents the force of infection for the Delta strain, which is characterized by a higher transmission rate.

where β_1 and β_2 are the transmission rates for strains 1 and 2 respectively, and $\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2$ represent modification factors capturing the reduced transmission potential from hospitalized individuals compared to those who are symptomatically infectious.

Individuals in the susceptible class receive vaccinations at rate ρ and move into the vaccinated compartment. However, due to imperfect vaccine efficacy, vaccinated individuals may still contract the virus (either strain) at a reduced rate $\sigma(\lambda_1 + \lambda_2)$, where $0 < \sigma < 1$ is the vaccine efficacy against infection. Loss of vaccine-induced immunity occurs at rate α , returning individuals to the susceptible class.

The exposed classes (E_1, E_2) represent individuals who have acquired the infection but are not yet infectious. These individuals progress to the infectious compartments at rates γ_1 and γ_2 for strains 1 and 2, respectively. Infectious individuals recover at rates ψ_1 and ψ_2 , and experience disease-induced mortality at rates δ_1 and δ_2 . Progression from the infectious to the hospitalized class occurs at rates τ_1 and τ_2 for each strain. Within the hospitalized compartment, additional mortality occurs at rates δ_{12} and δ_{21} , respectively. Moreover, some infectious individuals recover without hospitalization at rates ϕ_1 and ϕ_2 for the respective strains, transitioning directly into the recovered class. Immunity following recovery is temporary, and recovered individuals return to the susceptible class at a rate m . Incorporating these assumptions and transitions, the full dual strain SARS-CoV-2 model is formulated as a system of nonlinear ordinary differential equations, where each derivative represents the rate of change with respect to time.

$$\begin{aligned}
\dot{S}(t) &= \Pi + mR - (\lambda_1 + \lambda_2)S + \alpha V - (\rho + \mu)S \\
\dot{V}(t) &= \rho S - \sigma(\lambda_1 + \lambda_2)V - (\alpha + \mu)V \\
\dot{E}_1(t) &= (S + \sigma V)\lambda_1 - (\gamma_1 + \mu)E_1 \\
\dot{I}_1(t) &= \gamma_1 E_1 - (\tau_1 + \delta_1 + \psi_1 + \mu)I_1 \\
\dot{E}_2(t) &= (S + \sigma V)\lambda_2 - (\gamma_2 + \mu)E_2 \\
\dot{I}_2(t) &= \gamma_2 E_2 - (\tau_2 + \delta_2 + \psi_2 + \mu)I_2 \\
\dot{H}(t) &= \tau_1 I_1 + \tau_2 I_2 - (\psi_3 + \mu + \delta_{12} + \delta_{21})H \\
\dot{R}(t) &= \psi_1 I_1 + \psi_2 I_2 + \psi_3 H - (m + \mu)R
\end{aligned} \tag{3.6}$$

$$S(0) > 0, V(0) \geq 0, E_1(0) \geq 0, I_1(0) \geq 0, E_2(0) \geq 0, I_2(0) \geq 0, H(0) \geq 0, R(0) \geq 0, \tag{3.7}$$

Figure 3.2 illustrate the model formulation for dual strains SARs Cov-2 dynamics incorporating model assumptions, coupled with the Model parameters description as presented in Table (3.2).

Figure 3.2: Flow diagram of the dual strain model 3.6 where λ_1 and λ_2 are defined in equations (3.7), respectively. The state variables and parameters of the model are described in Tables 3.2, respectively.

Table 3.2: **Description of Model Variables and Parameters for the Dual-Strain Framework (3.6)**

Variable	Meaning
S	Population of individuals susceptible to infection
V	Population of fully vaccinated individuals
E_1	Individuals exposed to SARS-CoV-2 strain 1
E_2	Individuals exposed to SARS-CoV-2 strain 2
I_1	Infectious individuals carrying strain 1
I_2	Infectious individuals carrying strain 2
H	Individuals receiving treatment in hospitals
R	Recovered individuals with temporary immunity
Parameter	Meaning
Λ	Recruitment rate of individuals into the population
m, α	Rates of immunity loss in $V(t)$ and $R(t)$ compartments, respectively
$\gamma_{(1,2)}$	Progression rates from exposed to infectious classes for both strains
ρ	Vaccination rate per unit time
$\delta_{(1,2)}$	Death rates from infection in I_1 and I_2 classes
$\delta_{(12)}$	Mortality rate for hospitalized cases originally infected with strain 1
$\delta_{(21)}$	Mortality rate for hospitalized cases originally infected with strain 2
$\Psi_{(1,2,3)}$	Recovery rates from I_1 , I_2 , and H compartments respectively
$\tau_{(1,2)}$	Hospitalization rates from infectious classes I_1 and I_2
σ	Reduced infection rate among vaccinated individuals
$\beta_{(1,2)}$	Effective contact rates for susceptible individuals exposed to each strain
$\epsilon_{(1,2)}$	Infectivity adjustment for hospitalized individuals with strain 1 and strain 2
μ	Natural death rate across all compartments

3.3 Formulation of Optimal Control Strategies for Dual-Strain SARS-Cov-2 Dynamics

To address the spread of COVID-19 involving two co-circulating variants, the extended Optimal Control Model (OCM) defined in equation (3.8) introduces three primary intervention strategies into the dual-strain framework outlined in (3.6): vaccination, non-pharmaceutical interventions (NPIs), and clinical treatment. This expanded model evaluates the role and effectiveness of these public health measures in curbing disease transmission and managing case severity, while also considering implementation feasibility and economic cost. By incorporating these control mechanisms, the model offers a unified perspective on how coordinated interventions can reduce the overall impact of the

pandemic, particularly in the Nigerian context.

The first intervention, vaccination, is introduced as a time-dependent control variable $u_1(t)$, targeting the susceptible population. This control aims to increase the rate of immunization, thus decreasing the number of individuals at risk of infection. The model examines how expanding vaccine coverage can reduce the effective reproduction number and slow the spread of both viral strains.

The second control, denoted by $u_2(t)$, represents the application of NPIs such as wearing face masks, maintaining physical distance, and enforcing lockdowns. This strategy modifies the force of infection in the model, with the goal of reducing the rate at which susceptible individuals become infected. NPIs are particularly valuable during periods of limited vaccine availability or when novel variants reduce vaccine effectiveness. Through this control, the model assesses how behavioral and policy-driven interventions can suppress transmission dynamics.

The third control, $u_3(t)$, captures the impact of timely and effective medical treatment for infected individuals, specifically those who require hospitalization. By enhancing the recovery rate and reducing disease-induced mortality, this intervention reflects improvements in clinical care, including the use of antiviral medications, better hospital infrastructure, and early detection. The control modifies the hospitalized compartment and helps determine how treatment efforts contribute to overall disease burden reduction.

Altogether, the inclusion of these three time-dependent controls allows the OCM to simulate realistic public health scenarios, providing a strategic tool for understanding and optimizing response efforts against a dual-strain outbreak. The resulting system of differential equations governs the dynamics of the disease under these interventions and

is presented below.

$$\begin{aligned}
\dot{S}(t) &= \Pi + \varepsilon R - \left(\frac{\beta_1(I_1 + H\varepsilon_1)}{N} + \frac{\beta_2(I_2 + H\varepsilon_2)}{N} \right) S(1 - u_2) + \alpha V - (u_1 + \mu)S \\
\dot{V}(t) &= u_1 S - \sigma \left(\frac{\beta_1(I_1 + H\varepsilon_1)}{N} + \frac{\beta_2(I_2 + H\varepsilon_2)}{N} \right) (1 - u_2)V - (\alpha + \mu)V \\
\dot{E}_1(t) &= (S + \sigma V)(1 - u_2) \left(\frac{\beta_1(I_1 + H\varepsilon_1)}{N} \right) - (\gamma_1 + \mu)E_1 \\
\dot{I}_1(t) &= \gamma_1 E_1 - (\tau_1 + \delta_1 + \psi_1 + \mu)I_1 \\
\dot{E}_2(t) &= (S + \sigma V) \left(\frac{\beta_2(I_2 + H\varepsilon_2)}{N} \right) (1 - u_2) - (\gamma_2 + \mu)E_2 \\
\dot{I}_2(t) &= \gamma_2 E_2 - (\tau_2 + \delta_2 + \psi_2 + \mu)I_2 \\
\dot{H}(t) &= \tau_1 I_1 + \tau_2 I_2 - (u_3 + \mu + \delta_{12} + \delta_{21})H \\
\dot{R}(t) &= \psi_1 I_1 + \psi_2 I_2 + u_3 H - (\varepsilon + \mu)R
\end{aligned} \tag{3.8}$$

The initial conditions given for the corresponding state variable at time $t = 0$ are $S(0) > 0$, $V(0) \geq 0$, $E_1(0) \geq 0$, $I_1(0) \geq 0$, $E_2(0) \geq 0$, $I_2(0) \geq 0$, $H(0) \geq 0$, and $R(0) \geq 0$, while the model parameters are defined in Table 3.3.

However, In the formulation of equation (3.8), the time-dependent control (u_1, u_3) are applied across the population, with the vaccinated rate (ρ) incorporated into (u_1) and recovery rates (ψ) incorporated into (u_3) respectively.

Table 3.3: **Description of Variables and Parameters used for the optimal control model (3.8)**

Parameter	Description
Π	Recruitment rates into the population
m, α	Immunity waning rate for individuals in $V(t)$ or $R(t)$ class respectively
$\gamma_{(1,2)}$	Transmission rate of individuals from exposed compartment to infectious compartment for strain 1 and strain 2
ρ	Vaccination rate of individuals
$\delta_{(1,2)}$	Disease mortality rate in infectious population strain 1 and strain 2
$\delta_{(12)}$	Disease mortality rate in hospitalized class for strain 1
$\delta_{(21)}$	Disease mortality rate in hospitalized class for strain 2
$\Psi_{(1,2,3)}$	Rate of recovery from (I_1, I_2 & H) class
$\tau_{(1,2)}$	Rate of transmission from infectious compartment to Hospitalized class
σ	Effective infection rate for vaccinated individuals
$\beta_{(1,2)}$	Effective infection rate for susceptible individuals for strain 1 and strain 2
$\varepsilon_{(1,2)}$	modification paramater for effective contact rate for Hospitalized individuals for strain 1 and strain 2
μ	Natural mortality rate
Control Variable	Description
u_1	Vaccination effort that minimizes the susceptible
u_2	Control variable that accounts for COVID-19 preventive protocols that minimizes the new cases of infection for both strain
u_3	Control variable that accounts for effective treatment that minimizes individuals in hospitalize compartment

3.3.1 Optimal Control Problem Formulation

Here, the objective functional is formulated with control terms expressed in a quadratic form, aligning with conventional approaches commonly adopted in existing research (Lenhart & Workman, 2007; Katia *et al.*, 2022; Yusuf *et al.*, 2022). Thus, the model's objective functional is defined as follows:

$$J(u_1, u_2, u_3) = \int_0^t \left(w_1 S + w_2 I_1 + w_3 I_2 + w_4 H + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^3 \kappa_i u_i^2 \right) .dt, \quad (3.9)$$

and

$$J(u_1^*, u_2^*, u_3^*) = \min J(u_1, u_2, u_3) : u_1, u_2, u_3 \in \mathbb{U}, \quad (3.10)$$

such that

$$\mathbb{U} = (u_1(t), u_2(t), u_3(t)) \in \mathcal{R}^3$$

$u_1(t)$, $u_2(t)$, and $u_3(t)$ are Lebesgue measurable functions; and $0 \leq u_1(t), u_2(t), u_3(t) \leq 1$ for $0 \leq t$ is the control set. Defining t as the final time, w_1, w_2, w_3 , and w_4 are the weight constants of susceptible individuals, individuals infected with strain I, individuals infected with strain II, and hospitalized individuals respectively. The weights indicate the relative importance of reducing specific population classes to effectively control the spread of COVID-19 within Nigeria, while w_i , ($i = 1, \dots, 4$) are the weights designed to reflect the relative costs or efforts associated with implementing each time-dependent control strategy.

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Qualitative Analysis of Single Strain COVID-19 Model

This section provides a comprehensive analysis of the model defined in equation (3.1) to better understand its dynamic behavior. Key mathematical characteristics of the system are examined, including the existence and uniqueness of solutions, positivity and boundedness of trajectories, computation of the basic reproduction number, identification of the disease-free equilibrium, and an investigation into its local stability. Additionally, the possibility of backward bifurcation is explored, followed by numerical simulations to further illustrate the model's behavior.

4.1.1 Fundamental Properties of the Model

The model described in equation (3.1) is shown to possess well-defined, unique solutions that remain within a biologically feasible (positive and bounded) region for all time $t > 0$. This ensures that the system is mathematically well-posed and consistent with the principles of epidemiological modeling.

Theorem 4.1.1. *Let Γ denote a rectangular region, the model (3.2) with initial values $S(0) > 0, V(0) \geq 0, E(0) \geq 0, I_a(0) \geq 0, I_s(0) \geq 0, H(0) \geq 0, R(0) \geq 0$ exist, bounded, positively invariant and attracting for all $t > 0$*

4.1.1.1 Existence and Uniqueness

Proof.

We show that $\frac{\partial F_i}{\partial x_i}, i, j = 1 \dots 6$ are continuous and bounded in \mathcal{D} .

Let $F_1 = \Lambda + mR + \alpha V - \bar{\beta}XS - (\mu + \rho)S$ from the first system of equation (3.2), differentiating with respect to the state variable, we have:

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial F_1}{\partial S} &= -\frac{\bar{\beta}X}{N} + \frac{\bar{\beta}XS}{N^2} - \mu - \rho, & \left| \frac{\partial F_1}{\partial S} \right| &= \left| -\frac{\bar{\beta}X}{N} \right| + \left| \frac{\bar{\beta}XS}{N^2} - \mu - \rho \right| < \infty \\
\frac{\partial F_1}{\partial V} &= \alpha + \frac{\bar{\beta}XS}{N^2}, & \left| \frac{\partial F_1}{\partial V} \right| &= \left| \alpha + \frac{\bar{\beta}XS}{N^2} \right| < \infty \\
\frac{\partial F_1}{\partial E} &= \frac{\bar{\beta}XS}{N^2}, & \left| \frac{\partial F_1}{\partial E} \right| &= \left| \frac{\bar{\beta}XS}{N^2} \right| < \infty \\
\frac{\partial F_1}{\partial I_s} &= -\frac{\bar{\beta}\eta S}{N} + \frac{\bar{\beta}XS}{N^2}, & \left| \frac{\partial F_1}{\partial I_s} \right| &= \left| -\frac{\bar{\beta}\eta S}{N} \right| + \left| \frac{\bar{\beta}XS}{N^2} \right| < \infty \\
\frac{\partial F_1}{\partial I_a} &= -\frac{\bar{\beta}S}{N} + \frac{\bar{\beta}XS}{N^2}, & \left| \frac{\partial F_1}{\partial I_a} \right| &= \left| -\frac{\bar{\beta}S}{N} \right| + \left| \frac{\bar{\beta}XS}{N^2} \right| < \infty \\
\frac{\partial F_1}{\partial H} &= -\frac{\bar{\beta}\epsilon S}{N} + \frac{\bar{\beta}XS}{N^2}, & \left| \frac{\partial F_1}{\partial H} \right| &= \left| -\frac{\bar{\beta}\epsilon S}{N} \right| + \left| \frac{\bar{\beta}XS}{N^2} \right| < \infty \\
\frac{\partial F_1}{\partial R} &= m + \frac{\bar{\beta}XS}{N^2}, & \left| \frac{\partial F_1}{\partial R} \right| &= \left| m + \frac{\bar{\beta}XS}{N^2} \right| < \infty
\end{aligned} \tag{4.1}$$

which is obvious that the partial derivatives of the whole system of equations exists, finite and bounded.

4.1.1.2 Positivity and Boundedness

For the model (3.2) to be epidemiologically meaningful, all its state variables are non-negative for all time (t).

Theorem 4.1.2. *Given $S(0) > 0, V(0) \geq 0, E(0) \geq 0, I_a(0) \geq 0, I_s(0) \geq 0, H(0) \geq 0, R(0) \geq 0$. Then the solution $(S(t), V(t), E(t), I_a(t), I_s(t), H(t), R(t))$ of model (3.2) are positive at all $t > 0$.*

Proof.

Let $t_1 = \sup\{t > 0 \mid S > 0, V \geq 0, E \geq 0, I_a \geq 0, I_s \geq 0, H \geq 0, R \geq 0\}$. From the first equation of (??) we have

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{dS}{dt} &= \Lambda + mR(t) + \alpha V(t) - \bar{\beta}X(t)S(t) - (\mu + \rho)S(t) \\ \frac{dS}{dt} &\geq \Lambda - (\bar{\beta}X(t) + \mu + \rho)S(t)\end{aligned}\tag{4.2}$$

The integrating factor is given as: $\exp\left(\int_0^t \bar{\beta}X(s)ds + (\mu + \rho)t\right)$ Multiplying the inequality (4.2) by the integrating factor, we obtain

$$\frac{d\left[S(t) \exp\left\{\int_0^t \bar{\beta}X(s)ds + (\mu + \rho)t\right\}\right]}{dt} \geq \Lambda \exp\left(\int_0^t (\bar{\beta}X(s)ds + \mu + \rho)t\right)\tag{4.3}$$

Solving inequality (4.3) we obtain

$$S(t) \exp\left\{\int_0^t \bar{\beta}X(s)ds + (\mu + \rho)t\right\} - S(0) \geq \int_0^t \Lambda \exp\left\{\int_0^v (\bar{\beta}X(q)dq + (\mu + \rho)v\right\} dv\tag{4.4}$$

$$\begin{aligned}S(t) &\geq S(0) \exp\left\{-\int_0^t \bar{\beta}X(q)dq + (\mu + \rho)t\right\} + \exp\left\{-\int_0^t \bar{\beta}X(q)dq + (\mu + \rho)t\right\} \\ &\quad \times \int_0^t \Lambda \exp\left\{\int_0^v (\bar{\beta}X(q)dq + (\mu + \rho)v\right\} dv > 0\end{aligned}\tag{4.5}$$

In a similar pattern, it can be shown that:

$V > 0, E > 0, I_a > 0, I_s > 0, H > 0, R > 0$ in model (??);

which implies that $S(t), V(t), E(t)I_s(t), I_a(t), H(t)$ and $R(t)$ are all non-negative for non-negative initial conditions.

4.1.1.3 Boundedness of the solution

Theorem 4.1.3. *All solutions $S(t), V(t), E(t)I_s(t), I_a(t), H(t),$ and $R(t)$ of model (3.2) are bounded.*

Proof.

Adding all the equations of model system (3.2) gives:

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{dN}{dt} &= \Lambda - \mu N - \delta_1 I_s + \delta_2 H \\ \frac{dN}{dt} &\leq \Lambda - \mu N\end{aligned}\tag{4.6}$$

Solving equation (4.6) using standard comparison theorem; we illustrate the following steps:

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{dN(t)}{dt} &\leq \Lambda - \mu N \\ \frac{dN}{dt} + \mu N &\leq \Lambda\end{aligned}\tag{4.7}$$

The integrating factor is given as: $\exp^{\int \mu t}$; thus multiplying the inequality (4.7) by the integrating factor, we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned}\int d e^{\mu t} N(t) &\leq \int \Lambda e^{\mu t} .dt \\ e^{\mu t} N(t) &\leq \frac{\Lambda}{\mu} e^{\mu t} + C \\ N(t) &\leq e^{-\mu t} \left(\frac{\Lambda}{\mu} e^{\mu t} + C \right)\end{aligned}\tag{4.8}$$

Using initial condition (*i.e.* $N(t) = N(0)$ at $t = 0$), it implies that

$$\begin{aligned}N(t) &\leq e^{-\mu t} \left[\frac{\Lambda}{\mu} e^{\mu t} + \left(N(0) - \frac{\Lambda}{\mu} \right) \right] \\ N(t) &\leq N(0) e^{-\mu t} + \frac{\Lambda}{\mu} (1 - e^{-\mu t}) \\ \Rightarrow \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} N(t) &\leq \frac{\Lambda}{\mu}\end{aligned}\tag{4.9}$$

Hence, $\frac{\Lambda}{\mu}$ is the upper bound of $N(t)$, applying the comparison theorem as in Vangipuram *et al.* (1989), we have that $N(t) \leq \frac{\Lambda}{\mu}$, if $N(0) \leq \frac{\Lambda}{\mu}$. Thus, $\frac{\Lambda}{\mu}$ is the upper bound for the region Γ and is positively invariant (Idisi & Yusuf, 2021). Further, if $N(t) > \frac{\Lambda}{\mu}$ then either the solution enters Γ in finite time, or $N(t)$ approaches $\frac{\Lambda}{\mu}$. Then $N(t) = S + E + I_a + I_s + H + R$ is bounded by $\frac{\Lambda}{\mu}$. Hence $S(t), E(t), \dots, R(t)$ are all bounded since they are subject of $N(t)$

4.1.2 Disease Free Equilibrium (DFE)

To determine the equilibrium states of the model, we set the left-hand side of the differential equations in system(3.1) to zero and solve the resulting algebraic system. This approach yields both the Disease-Free Equilibrium (DFE) and the endemic equilibrium points of the model. The expression for the Disease-Free Equilibrium is presented as:

$$\mathcal{E}_0 = \{S^*, V^*, E^*, I_a^*, I_s^*, H^*, R^*\} = \left(\frac{(\mu + \alpha)\Lambda}{\mu(\rho + \alpha + \mu)}, \frac{\rho\Lambda}{\mu(\rho + \alpha + \mu)}, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0 \right) \quad (4.10)$$

4.1.2.1 Reproduction Number

The control reproduction number, denoted as R_{0V} , represents the expected number of secondary COVID-19 cases produced by a single infectious individual in a population where a proportion of individuals are protected through interventions such as vaccination and non-pharmaceutical measures. In contrast, the basic reproduction number, \mathcal{R}_0 , reflects the transmission potential in a completely susceptible population with no control strategies in place.

To compute \mathcal{R}_0 , we apply the next-generation matrix method as outlined in Van Den Driessche & Watmough (2002), using the model system (3.2) evaluated at the disease-free equilibrium (DFE) defined in equation(4.10). The derivation involves constructing two matrices: F , which captures the rate of new infections, and V , which includes all other transitions among the infected compartments. These matrices are used to evaluate the spectral radius of FV^{-1} , which yields both the basic and control repro-

duction numbers, depending on the presence or absence of intervention terms.

$$FV^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \frac{(\mu+\alpha)\beta+\rho\sigma}{\mu+\alpha+\rho} & \frac{[(\mu+\alpha)\beta+\rho\sigma]\eta}{\mu+\alpha+\rho} & \frac{[(\mu+\alpha)\beta+\rho\sigma]\varepsilon}{\mu+\alpha+\rho} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{k_1} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{(1-\theta)\gamma}{k_1(k_2+\phi)} & \frac{1}{k_2+\phi} & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{\gamma(k_2+\phi)}{k_1(k_2+\phi)k_3} & \frac{\phi}{(k_2+\phi)k_3} & \frac{1}{k_3} & 0 \\ \frac{\tau\gamma(k_2+\phi)}{k_1(k_2+\phi)k_3k_4} & \frac{\tau\phi}{(k_2+\phi)k_3k_4} & \frac{\tau}{k_3k_4} & \frac{1}{k_4} \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.11)$$

Now, we define the quantity \mathcal{R}_{0V} as the spectral radius of the next generation matrix (FV^{-1}) which is obtained as stated below :

$$\mathcal{R}_{0V} = \rho(FV^{-1}) = \frac{\gamma[\beta(\mu+\alpha) + \rho\sigma] [k_3k_4(1-\theta) + k_4\eta(k_2\theta + \phi) + \tau\varepsilon(k_2\theta + \phi)]}{k_1k_3k_4(\mu+\alpha+\rho)(k_2+\phi)} \quad (4.12)$$

where

$$\mathcal{R}_a = \frac{\gamma(1-\theta)A_1}{(\mu+\alpha+\rho)k_1(k_2+\phi)}, \quad \mathcal{R}_s = \frac{\gamma\eta(k_2\theta + \phi)A_1}{(\mu+\alpha+\rho)(k_2+\phi)k_1k_3}, \quad \mathcal{R}_h = \frac{\varepsilon\tau\gamma(k_2\theta + \phi)A_1}{(\mu+\alpha+\rho)k_1(k_2+\phi)k_3k_4} \quad (4.13)$$

with $A_1 = (\mu+\alpha)\beta + \sigma\rho$

The term \mathcal{R}_{0V} denotes the control reproduction number associated with model (3.1). It reflects the average number of secondary COVID-19 infections caused by a single infectious individual in a population where a certain portion is either vaccinated or complies with non-pharmaceutical interventions (NPIs), such as mask usage or social distancing. This metric captures the impact of public health measures on disease transmission. Specifically, \mathcal{R}_{0V} is composed of contributions from different infectious classes, namely asymptomatic individuals (\mathcal{R}_a), symptomatic individuals (\mathcal{R}_s), and those receiving hospital care (\mathcal{R}_h), with each component reflecting the transmission potential within its

respective group.

4.1.2.2 Threshold Analysis and Vaccine Impact

In this subsection, the potential impact of a single dose and a fractional dosing of the vaccine is analyzed. Based on the facts that it is often impracticable to vaccinate all susceptible individuals due to many reasons (e.g financial constraints, age of the recipient, belief, etc).

Let us recall that the control reproduction number in term of S and V is

$$\mathcal{R}_{0V} = \frac{(S^*\beta + V^*\sigma)\gamma[k_3k_4(1 - \theta) + k_4\eta(k_2\theta + \phi) + \tau\varepsilon(k_2\theta + \phi)]}{(S^* + V^*)(k_2 + \phi)k_1k_3k_4}. \quad (4.14)$$

Considering the worse case scenario, where there is no public health control or mitigation measures implemented and the disease spreads in the population, then $V^* = 0$ and $S^* = N^*$. Therefore, the control reproduction number reduces to

$$\mathcal{R}_0 = \mathcal{R}_{0V}|_{V^*=0} = \frac{\gamma\beta[k_3k_4(1 - \theta) + k_4\eta(k_2\theta + \phi) + \tau\varepsilon(k_2\theta + \phi)]}{k_1(k_2 + \phi)k_3k_4}. \quad (4.15)$$

So, $\mathcal{R}_{0V} \leq \mathcal{R}_0$, since $\frac{\beta(\alpha+\mu)+\rho\sigma}{\mu+\alpha+\rho} > 0$. Thus, vaccination of individuals will have positive impact in the community by reducing the value of the associated reproduction number \mathcal{R}_0 . Furthermore, using a similar approach as employed in (Danbaba & Garba, 2020), the impact of vaccination can be analysed qualitatively by differentiating \mathcal{R}_{0V} with respect to the fraction of vaccinated individuals (V). It can be shown that

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{R}_{0V}}{\partial V} = \frac{-S^*\gamma(\beta - \sigma)[k_3k_4(1 - \theta) + k_4\eta(k_2\theta + \phi) + \tau\varepsilon(k_2\theta + \phi)]}{(S^* + V^*)^2(k_2 + \phi)k_1k_3k_4} < 0, \quad \text{since } \beta > \sigma. \quad (4.16)$$

Therefore, \mathcal{R}_{0V} is a decreasing function of V . The implication of the foregoing result is that vaccination will have a positive impact in COVID-19 disease control, since \mathcal{R}_0 is

a measure of the marginal incidence of the disease which cumulatively constitutes the disease burden in the society.

4.1.3 Equilibrium Analysis at the Disease-Free State (\mathcal{E}_0)

To achieve the eradication of COVID-19, it is essential to verify that the disease-free equilibrium (DFE) is both locally and globally asymptotically stable. Local stability is assessed by analyzing the eigenvalues of the Jacobian matrix evaluated at the DFE. For global stability, we apply the Metzler matrix technique, following the frameworks established in Danbaba & Garba (2020) and Kamgang & Sallet (2005) to determine the conditions under which the DFE remains stable throughout the entire biologically feasible domain.

4.1.3.1 Local Stability

Theorem 4.1.4. *The disease free equilibrium point is locally asymptotically stable if the constituent $\{R_a, R_s\} < 1$ and unstable for $\{R_a, R_s\} > 1$.*

Proof.: The Jacobian of the system 3.2 at the DFE point in (4.10) is given as:

$$J(E_0) = \begin{bmatrix} -(\mu+\rho) & \alpha & 0 & \frac{\beta(\mu+\alpha)}{\mu+\alpha+\rho} & \frac{\eta\beta(\mu+\alpha)}{\mu+\alpha+\rho} & \frac{\varepsilon\beta(\mu+\alpha)}{\mu+\alpha+\rho} & m \\ \rho & -(\alpha+\mu) & 0 & -\frac{\sigma\rho}{\mu+\alpha+\rho} & \frac{-\eta\sigma\rho}{\mu+\alpha+\rho} & -\frac{\varepsilon\sigma\rho}{\mu+\alpha+\rho} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \kappa_1 & \frac{\beta(\mu+\alpha)+\sigma_1\rho}{\mu+\alpha+\rho} & \frac{\eta[\beta(\mu+\alpha)+\sigma_1\rho]}{\mu+\alpha+\rho} & \frac{\varepsilon[\beta(\mu+\alpha)+\sigma_1\rho]}{\mu+\alpha+\rho} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & (1-\theta)\gamma & -\kappa_2 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \theta\gamma & \phi & -\kappa_3 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \tau & -\kappa_4 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \psi_1 & \psi_2 & \psi_3 & -(\mu+m) \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.17)$$

Obviously it is clear, that the first two eigenvalues of the matrix in equation (4.17) are

negative ($-\kappa_4$ and $-(\mu + m)$). However, we solve for the characteristic Polynomial as

$$P(\xi) = (\xi + \mu)(\xi + \mu + \alpha + \rho) [\xi^3 + a_x \xi^2 + a_y \xi + a_z]$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} a_x &= \kappa_1 + \kappa_2 + \kappa_3 + \phi \\ a_y &= (\mu + \alpha + \rho)(1 - R_a) + \kappa_3(\kappa_1 + \kappa_2 + \phi) - \gamma\eta\theta A \\ a_z &= (\kappa_2 + \phi)(1 - R_s) + \kappa_3(\kappa_2 + \phi)(1 - R_a) \end{aligned} \quad (4.18)$$

The third-order polynomial $P(\xi) = \xi^3 + a_x \xi^2 + a_y \xi + a_z$ has all roots in the open left half-plane if and only if a_x , a_y , and a_z are positive. Moreover, in order to ensure that the quantity $a_x a_y - a_z$ is positive; it suffices that $\{R_a, R_s\} < 1$, which fulfils the condition of Routh-Hurwitz criteria. Thus, the Disease-free equilibrium is locally asymptotically stable (LAS).

4.1.3.2 Global Stability

To show the global asymptotical stability, of the disease free equilibria of the system represent by equation (3.2), we adopt the Metzler technique. The subsequent theorem yield to the desired result.

Theorem 4.1.5. *Considering the model system (??), let $\Gamma \subset \mathbb{R}_+^{n_1+n_2}$ be a positively invariant set. If*

1. *The system (3.2) is defined on the positively invariant set $\Gamma \subset \mathbb{R}_+^{n_1+n_2}$;*
2. *The sub-system $\dot{x}_1 = A_1(x_1, 0) \cdot (x_1 - x_1^*)$ is globally asymptotically stable at the equilibrium x_1^* ;*
3. *For any $x \in \Gamma$, the matrix $A_{22}(x)$ is Metzler irreducible;*

4. There exist an upper bound matrix \bar{A}_{22} for the set $\mathcal{M} = \{A_{22}(x)|x \in \Gamma\}$ with the property that either $A_{22}(x) \notin \mathcal{M}$ or if $A_{22}(x) \in \mathcal{M}$ (i.e., $\bar{A}_{22} = \max_{\Gamma} \mathcal{M}$), then for $x^* \in \Gamma$ such that , $\bar{A}_{22} = A_{22}(x^*)$, then $x^* \in \mathcal{M}^7 \times \{0\}$ (the DFE sub-manifold contains the points where the maximum is attained);
5. The stability modulus of \bar{A}_{22} satisfies $\alpha(\bar{A}_{22}) \leq 0$;

Then, the associated disease free equilibrium is globally asymptotically stable in Γ .

Proof:

Given model (3.2) rewritten in pseudo-triangular form with the use of property of DFE,

we have

$$\begin{cases} \dot{x}_1 &= A_{11}(x).(x_1 - x_1^*) + A_{12}(x)x_2 \\ \dot{x}_2 &= A_{22}(x)x_2 \end{cases} \quad (4.19)$$

where $x_1 = (S, V, R)^T$ represents the non transmitting compartment of model (??), $x_2 = (E, I_a, I_s, H)^T$ represents the infectious compartment of the model, $x_1^* = (S^*, V^*, R^*)^T$ is the DFE while

$$A_{11}(x) = \begin{pmatrix} -(\mu + \rho) & \alpha & m \\ \rho & -(\mu + \alpha) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -(\mu + m), \end{pmatrix}$$

$$A_{12}(x) = \begin{pmatrix} -\frac{\beta_1 S}{S+V} & -\frac{\beta_1 \eta S}{S+V} & -\frac{\beta_1 \epsilon S}{S+V} \\ -\frac{\sigma_1 V}{S+V} & -\frac{\sigma_1 \eta V}{S+V} & -\frac{\sigma_1 \epsilon V}{S+V}, \\ \Psi_1 & \Psi_2 & \Psi_3, \end{pmatrix} \quad (4.20)$$

$$A_{22}(x) = \begin{pmatrix} -\kappa_1 & \frac{\beta_1 S + \sigma_1 V}{S+V} & \frac{\eta [(S\beta_1 + \sigma_1 V)]}{S+V} & \frac{\epsilon [S\beta_1 + \sigma_1 V]}{S+V} \\ (1 - \theta)\gamma & -(\kappa_2 + \phi) & 0 & 0 \\ \theta\gamma & \phi & -\kappa_3 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \tau & -\kappa_4. \end{pmatrix}$$

Recall that the model (3.2) is defined on a positive invariant domain given by Γ in Theorem (4.1.1). Also, by direct computation, the eigenvalues of $A_{11}(x)$ are $\{-(\mu + \rho), -(\mu + \alpha), -(\mu + m)\}$ which are real and negative. Therefore, conditions 1 and 2 of (4.2.5) are satisfied. For condition 3 of (4.2.5), we show that a square matrix $A_{22}(x_2)$ is irreducible if and only if its diagraph is strongly connected

Figure 4.1: Connected di-graph associated with the matrix $A_{22}(x)$

Figure 4.1 is obtained by substituting the parameter baseline values as presented in Table 4.1 into equation (4.67) to obtain its adjacency matrix and using online platform https://graphonline.ru/en/create_graph_by_matrix to plot the associated di-graph of the matrix $A_{22}(x)$ which is further verified at <https://www.geeksforgeeks.org/check-if-a-directed-graph-is-connected-or-not/> using online version of C++ programme whose output indicate that the digraph is strongly connected. Thus condition (3) is satisfied.

Furthermore, since $S = \frac{\Lambda(\mu + \alpha)}{\mu(\mu + \alpha + \rho)}$ and $V = \frac{\Lambda\rho}{\mu(\mu + \alpha + \rho)}$, then the matrix *

$$\bar{A}_{22}(x) = \begin{pmatrix} -\kappa_1 & \frac{\beta_1(\mu + \alpha) + \sigma_1\rho}{\mu + \alpha + \rho} & \frac{\eta[\beta_1(\mu + \alpha) + \sigma_1\rho]}{\mu + \alpha + \rho} & \frac{\varepsilon[\beta_1(\mu + \alpha) + \sigma_1\rho]}{\mu + \alpha + \rho} \\ (1 - \theta)\gamma & -\kappa_2 & 0 & 0 \\ \theta\gamma & \phi & -\kappa_3 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \tau & -\kappa_4 \end{pmatrix} \quad (4.21)$$

is an upper bound of $A_{22}(x)$. For condition 5 of Theorem (4.55), we present the condition for a Metzler matrix M to satisfy $\alpha(M) < 0$ using Lemma (4.1.1)

Lemma 4.1.1. *Let $M(x)$ be a Metzler matrix which is block decomposed as :*

$$M = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbb{A} & \mathbb{B} \\ \mathbb{C} & \mathbb{D} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (4.22)$$

where \mathbb{A} and \mathbb{D} are square matrices. Then, M is Metzler stable if and only if \mathbb{A} and $\mathbb{D} - \mathbb{C}^{-1}\mathbb{B}$ are Metzler stable.

In this case, $\bar{A}_{22}(x)$ is decompose as:

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} -\kappa_1 & \frac{A_1}{\mu + \alpha + \rho} \\ (1 - \theta)\gamma & -\kappa_2 - \phi \end{pmatrix}, \quad C = \begin{pmatrix} \theta\gamma & \phi \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (4.23)$$

$$B = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{A_1\eta}{\mu + \alpha + \rho} & \frac{A_1\varepsilon}{\mu + \alpha + \rho} \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad D = \begin{pmatrix} -\kappa_3 & 0 \\ \tau & -\kappa_4 \end{pmatrix}$$

and

$$\mathbb{D} - \mathbb{C}^{-1}\mathbb{B} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{-k_1 k_3 (k_2 + \phi)(\mu + \alpha + \rho) + A_1 \gamma [(k_3(1 - \theta) + \eta(k_2 \theta + \phi))]}{k_1 k_2 (\mu + \alpha + \rho) - A_1 \gamma (1 - \theta)} & \frac{A_1 \gamma \epsilon [(\phi(1 - \theta) + k_2 \theta)] - k_1 (k_2 + \phi) k_3 (\mu + \alpha + \rho)}{k_1 (k_2 + \phi)(\mu + \alpha + \rho) - A_1 \gamma (1 - \theta)} \\ \tau & -\kappa_4 \end{bmatrix}$$

Therefore $\mathbb{D} - \mathbb{C}^{-1}\mathbb{B}$ is a Metzler matrix if $(\mathcal{R}_a, \mathcal{R}_s) < 1$ in (4.72)

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{-k_1 k_3 (k_2 + \phi)(\mu + \alpha + \rho) + A_1 \gamma [(k_3(1 - \theta) + \eta(k_2 \theta + \phi))]}{k_1 k_2 (\mu + \alpha + \rho) - A_1 \gamma (1 - \theta)} \\ &= \frac{-k_1 k_3 (k_2 + \phi)(\mu + \alpha + \rho) [(1 - (\mathcal{R}_a) + (1 - \mathcal{R}_s))]}{k_1 (k_2 + \phi)(\mu + \alpha + \rho)(1 - \mathcal{R}_a)} < 1, \end{aligned} \quad (4.24)$$

and it is stable if

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{k_1 k_3 k_4 (k_2 + \phi)(\mu + \alpha + \rho) - A_1 \gamma [k_3 k_4 (1 - \theta) + k_4 \eta (k_2 \theta + \phi) + \tau \epsilon (k_2 \theta + \phi)]}{\kappa_1 \kappa_2 (\mu + \alpha + \rho) - A_1 \gamma (1 - \theta)} \\ &= \frac{k_1 k_3 k_4 (k_2 + \phi)(\mu + \alpha + \rho)(1 - \mathcal{R}_{0V})}{k_1 k_3 k_4 (k_2 + \phi)(\mu + \alpha + \rho)(1 - \mathcal{R}_a)} = \frac{k_3 \kappa_4 (1 - \mathcal{R}_{0V})}{(1 - \mathcal{R}_a)} > 0 \end{aligned} \quad (4.25)$$

It should be noted that, condition (4.74) is a generalization of condition (4.72).

$$\text{Hence, } \mathcal{R}_{0V} < \frac{\gamma \beta [k_3 k_4 (1 - \theta) + k_4 \eta (k_2 \theta + \phi) + \tau \epsilon (k_2 \theta + \phi)]}{k_1 k_3 k_4 (k_2 + \phi)} < 1 \quad (4.26)$$

Thus, satisfying condition (4.74) is sufficient for the GAS of the DFE. \square

4.1.3.3 Endemic Equilibrium (\mathcal{E}_1)

In order to establish the existence of endemic equilibria of model (3.2) (i.e, a scenario where at least one of the infected state variable of the model is non-zero), the model system (3.2) is solved in term of force of infection expressed as:

$$X^{**} = \frac{(I_a^{**} + \eta I_s^{**} + \epsilon H^{**})}{N^{**}} \quad (4.27)$$

We solve the equations of the model (??) at state variable in term of X^{**} and we

obtain:

$$S^{**} = \frac{k_1(k_2 + \phi)(X^{**}\sigma + \alpha + \mu)I_a^{**}}{(1 - \theta)\gamma X^{**} [(X^{**}\sigma + \alpha + \mu)\beta + \rho\sigma]}, \quad H^{**} = \frac{\tau(k_2\theta + \phi)I_a^{**}}{k_3(1 - \theta)K_4},$$

$$V^{**} = \frac{k_1\rho(k_2 + \phi)I_a^{**}}{(1 - \theta)\gamma X^{**} [(X^{**}\sigma + \alpha + \mu)\beta + \rho\sigma]}, \quad I_s^{**} = \frac{(k_2\theta + \phi)I_a^{**}}{k_3(1 - \theta)}, \quad E^{**} = \frac{I_a^{**}(k_2 + \phi)}{(1 - \theta)\gamma},$$

$$R^{**} = \frac{\left\{ \beta\sigma [(k_2 + \phi)k_1I_a^{**} - \gamma\Lambda(1 - \theta)] X^{**2} + (k_2 + \phi) [\beta(\mu + \alpha) + \sigma(\mu + \rho)] k_1I_a^{**} X^{**} \right. \\ \left. + \Lambda\gamma(1 - \theta) [\beta(\mu + \alpha) + \rho\sigma] X^{**} + k_1(k_2 + \phi)(\alpha + \mu + \rho)\mu I_a^{**} \right\}}{\gamma m(1 - \theta) [X^{**}\beta\sigma + (\mu + \alpha)\beta + \rho\sigma] X^{**}}$$

$$I_s^{**} = \frac{\gamma(\mu + m)k_3(1 - \theta)\Lambda k_4 [(X^{**}\sigma + \alpha + \mu)\beta + \rho\sigma] X^{**}}{[k_1k_3k_4\beta\sigma [(k_2 + \phi)(m + \mu) - \gamma(1 - \theta)m] - \gamma m\beta\sigma [k_3\tau + k_2k_4] (k_2\theta + \phi)] X^{**2}}, \\ + \{ [(k_2 + \phi)(\beta + \sigma) - \gamma\beta(1 - \theta)]\mu + [(k_2 + \phi - \gamma(1 - \theta))(\alpha\beta + \rho\sigma)] mk_1k_3k_4 + \\ \mu(k_2 + \phi) [\mu(\sigma + \beta) + \alpha\beta + \sigma\rho] - \gamma m(k_2\theta + \phi) [\alpha\beta + \beta\mu + \rho\sigma] (k_3\tau + k_2k_4) \} X^{**} \\ + \mu k_1k_3k_4(\mu + m) [\alpha + \mu + \rho] (k_2 + \phi).$$

Substituting $(S^{**}, V^{**}, E^{**}, I_a^{**}, I_s^{**}, H^{**}, R^{**})$ into (4.27) which gives

$$X^{**} = \frac{(\mu + m)\gamma\beta\sigma T_1 X^{**2} + (\mu + m)\gamma A_1 T_1 X^{**}}{\sigma\beta X^{**2} [T_2 k_3 \gamma + T_3 \gamma + T_4 k_3 + \gamma\tau T_5] + k_3 T_4 k_1 (\mu + \alpha + \rho)} \quad (4.28) \\ + [T_2 k_3 + T_3 \gamma A_1 + T_4 k_3 A_1 + \sigma T_4 k_1 k_3 + \tau\gamma T_5 A_1] X^{**},$$

where

$$T_1 = [k_3 k_4 (1 - \theta) + \eta k_4 (k_2\theta + \phi) + \tau\epsilon (k_2\theta + \phi)], \quad T_2 = (k_1 + m + \mu)(1 - \theta)k_4,$$

$$T_3 = (k_2 + m + \mu)(k_2\theta + \phi)k_4, \quad T_4 = (m + \mu)(k_2\theta + \phi)k_4, \quad T_5 = (k_3 + m + \mu)(k_2\theta + \phi).$$

Equation (4.28) can be express as

$$X^{**} \left\{ \sigma\beta X^{**2} [T_2k_3\gamma + T_3\gamma + T_4k_3 + \gamma\tau T_5] + [T_2k_3 + T_3\gamma A_1 + T_4k_3 A_1 + \sigma T_4k_1k_3 + \tau\gamma T_5 A_1 - (\mu + m)\beta\gamma\sigma T_1] X^{**} + k_3k_1T_4(\mu + \alpha + \rho) - (\mu + m)\gamma A_1 T_1 \right\} = 0. \quad (4.29)$$

Moreover, equation from (4.29) $X^{**} = 0$ or

$$\sigma\beta [T_2k_3\gamma + T_3\gamma + T_4k_3 + \gamma\tau T_5] X^{**2} + [T_2k_3 + T_3\gamma A_1 + T_4k_3 A_1 + \sigma T_4k_1k_3 + \tau\gamma T_5 A_1 - (\mu + m)\beta\gamma\sigma T_1] X^{**} + k_3k_1T_4(\mu + \alpha + \rho) - (\mu + m)\gamma A_1 T_1 = 0. \quad (4.30)$$

Thus, from equation (4.30), we obtain the quadratic equation below:

$$a_2 X^{**2} + a_1 X^{**} + a_0 = 0, \quad (4.31)$$

with the coefficient of X^{**} given as:

$$\begin{aligned} a_2 &= \sigma\beta [T_2k_3\gamma + T_3\gamma + T_4k_3 + \gamma\tau T_5], \\ a_1 &= T_2k_3 + T_3\gamma A_1 + T_4k_3 A_1 + \sigma T_4k_1k_3 + \tau\gamma T_5 A_1 - (\mu + m)\beta\gamma\sigma T_1, \\ a_0 &= k_3k_4k_1(\mu + m)(k_2\theta + \phi)(\mu + \alpha + \rho) [1 - \mathcal{R}_{0V}]. \end{aligned} \quad (4.32)$$

However, it is clear from equation (4.32) that a_2 is always positive and a_0 is negative whenever $\mathcal{R}_{0V} > 1$. Hence, Theorem (4.2.7) summarizes the condition for existence of endemic equilibrium for the COVID-19 model (3.2).

Theorem 4.1.6. *The COVID-19 model (3.2) has:*

1. *no endemic equilibrium otherwise, if all the coefficient $\{a_2, a_1, a_0\}$ of equation (4.31) are all positive*
2. *a unique endemic equilibrium exists if $a_1 < 0$, and $a_0 = 0$ or $a_1^2 - 4a_0a_2 = 0$*
3. *two endemic equilibria if $a_0 > 0$, $a_1 < 0$ and $a_1^2 - 4a_0a_2 > 0$*

4. a unique endemic equilibrium if $a_0 < 0 \Leftrightarrow \mathcal{R}_{0V} > 1$

Thus, it is clear from Theorem 4.2.7 case (2) that the model system (??) has a unique endemic equilibrium whenever $\mathcal{R}_{0V} > 1$. Furthermore, case (3) of Theorem 4.2.7 establishes the existence of multiple endemic equilibrium points which indicates the possibility of backward bifurcation (where the locally-asymptotically stable DFE co-exists with a locally-asymptotically stable endemic equilibrium in the model(3.2) whenever $\mathcal{R}_{0V} < 1$ (Oke *et al.*, 2021). Hence, to compute the bifurcation, the discriminant of (4.31) is equated to zero. Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta &= a_1^2 - 4a_2k_3k_4k_1(\mu + m)(k_2 + \phi)(\mu + \alpha + \rho)[1 - \mathcal{R}_{0V}] = 0 \\ \mathcal{R}_{0V}^* &= 1 - \frac{a_1^2}{4a_2k_3k_4k_1(\mu + m)(k_2 + \phi)(\mu + \alpha + \rho)} \end{aligned} \quad (4.33)$$

Therefore, equation (4.33) gives the analytical expression of a threshold value for the control reproduction number, and backward bifurcation would occur for values of $\mathcal{R}_{0V}^* < \mathcal{R}_{0V} < 1$.

4.1.3.4 Backward Bifurcation Analysis of the Single Strain Model

Traditionally, the condition $\mathcal{R}_0 < 1$ has been considered sufficient to guarantee disease eradication. However, recent theoretical investigations have revealed that this assumption does not always hold true. The concept of backward bifurcation challenges this notion by illustrating that, under certain conditions, a stable endemic equilibrium may coexist with a stable disease-free equilibrium even when $\mathcal{R}_0 < 1$. This implies that the disease could persist in the population despite the basic reproduction number being below the threshold value of unity. The existence of multiple stable equilibria suggests that the long-term outcome of disease dynamics is highly sensitive to the initial distribution of individuals across compartments.

Given this, it is essential to explore the nature of bifurcation exhibited by the model, particularly under the presence of intervention strategies. In light of this, we proceed to establish the following result.

Theorem 4.1.7.

$$\text{Let } \rho^* = \frac{(\beta^* - \sigma)w_2 + \beta^*(\alpha + \mu)(w_1 + w_4 + w_5 + w_6 + w_7)}{(\beta^* - \sigma)w_1 - \sigma(w_1 + w_4 + w_5 + w_6 + w_7)} \quad (4.34)$$

Then, at $\mathcal{R}_{0V} = 1$, model system (3.2) exhibits transcritical bifurcation and its direction is backward (or forward) iff $\rho^* < \rho$ (or $> \rho$).

Proof. Suppose

$$\mathcal{E}_1 = (S^{**}, V^{**}, E^{**}, I_a^{**}, I_s^{**}, H^{**}, R^{**}) \quad (4.35)$$

represents any arbitrary endemic equilibrium of the model (3.2) (that is, an equilibrium in which at least one of the infected components is non-zero). Applying the Center Manifold theory (Castillo-Chavez & Song, 2004), the existence of backward bifurcation will be studied.. By simplification and change of variables of model (3.2). Let $S = x_1, V = x_2, E = x_3, I_a = x_4, I_s = x_5, H = x_6$, and $R = x_7$ so that $N = x_1 + x_2 + x_3 + x_4 + x_5 + x_6 + x_7$. Further, by using the vector notation $X = (x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, x_5, x_6, x_7)^T$, the model (3.2) can be written in the form $\frac{dX}{dt} = F(X)$, with $(f_1, f_2, f_3, f_4, f_5, f_6, f_7)^T$,

as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{dx_1}{dt} &\equiv f_1 = \Lambda + mx_7 + \alpha x_3 - \beta \kappa x_1 - (\mu + \rho)x_1 \\
\frac{dx_2}{dt} &\equiv f_2 = \rho x_1 - \sigma \kappa x_2 - (\mu + \alpha)x_2 \\
\frac{dx_3}{dt} &\equiv f_3 = \beta \kappa x_1 + \sigma \kappa x_2 - (\gamma + \mu)x_3 \\
\frac{dx_4}{dt} &\equiv f_4 = (1 - \theta)\gamma x_3 - (\psi_1 + \phi + \mu)x_4 \\
\frac{dx_5}{dt} &\equiv f_5 = \theta\gamma x_3 + \phi x_4 - (\psi_2 + \tau + \delta_1 + \mu)x_5 \\
\frac{dx_6}{dt} &\equiv f_6 = \tau x_5 - (\psi_3 + \delta_2 + \mu)x_6 \\
\frac{dx_7}{dt} &\equiv f_7 = \psi_1 x_4 + \psi_2 x_5 + \psi_3 x_6 - (\mu + m)x_7
\end{aligned} \tag{4.36}$$

The force of infection is given as

$$\kappa = \frac{(x_4 + \eta x_5 + \varepsilon x_6)}{x_1 + x_2 + x_3 + x_4 + x_5 + x_6 + x_7}, \quad \beta = \beta_1(1 - w - s) \text{ and } \sigma = \sigma_1(1 - w - s)$$

Considering the case when $\mathcal{R}_{0V} = 1$ and that $\beta = \beta^*$ is chosen as a bifurcation parameter.

Solving for $\beta = \beta^*$ in (4.12) gives

$$1 = \frac{\gamma[\beta(\mu + \alpha) + \rho\sigma][k_3 k_4(1 - \theta) + k_4 \eta(k_2 \theta + \phi) + \tau \varepsilon(k_2 \theta + \phi)]}{k_1 k_3 k_4(\mu + \alpha + \rho)(k_2 \theta + \phi)} \tag{4.37}$$

$$\beta^* = \frac{(\mu + \alpha + \rho)(k_2 + \phi)k_1 k_3 k_4 - \rho\sigma\gamma T_1}{\gamma(\mu + \alpha)T_1} \tag{4.38}$$

The Jacobian for the transformed model (3.2) at the DFE (\mathcal{E}_0) with $\beta = \beta^*$ is given as:

$$J^*(E_0) = \begin{bmatrix} -(\mu+\rho) & \alpha & 0 & -\frac{\beta^*(\mu+\alpha)}{\mu+\alpha+\rho} & -\frac{\eta\beta^*(\mu+\alpha)}{\mu+\alpha+\rho} & -\frac{\varepsilon\beta^*(\mu+\alpha)}{\mu+\alpha+\rho} & m \\ \rho & -(\alpha+\mu) & 0 & -\frac{\sigma\rho}{\mu+\alpha+\rho} & -\frac{\eta\sigma\rho}{\mu+\alpha+\rho} & -\frac{\varepsilon\sigma\rho}{\mu+\alpha+\rho} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \kappa_1 & \frac{\beta^*(\mu+\alpha)+\sigma_1\rho}{\mu+\alpha+\rho} & \frac{\eta[\beta^*(\mu+\alpha)+\sigma_1\rho]}{\mu+\alpha+\rho} & \frac{\varepsilon[\beta^*(\mu+\alpha)+\sigma_1\rho]}{\mu+\alpha+\rho} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & (1-\theta)\gamma & -\kappa_2 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \theta\gamma & \phi & -\kappa_3 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \tau & -\kappa_4 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \psi_1 & \psi_2 & \psi_3 & -(\mu+m) \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.39)$$

The Jacobian matrix $J^*(E_0)$ corresponding to the linearized system of model (4.36) possesses a simple eigenvalue at zero, while all other eigenvalues have negative real parts. As a result, the Center Manifold Theorem, as discussed in (Song & Lou, 2013), is employed to examine the local dynamics near the disease-free equilibrium. To achieve this analysis, both the right and left eigenvectors, denoted by w and v respectively, are determined from the Jacobian matrix.

$$\begin{aligned}
w_1 &= \frac{\gamma\{[(\mu + \alpha)(\mu + \alpha)[(\mu + m)\beta^*T_1 - Qm] + (\alpha\mu + m)\sigma\rho T_1 - Qm\rho(1 + \mu)]\}}{\mu(\mu + \alpha + \rho)^2(k_2 + \phi)k_3k_4} \\
w_2 &= \frac{\gamma\rho\{\mu(\mu + m)(\beta^* + \sigma)T_1 - m(\mu + \alpha + \rho)Q\}}{\mu(\mu + \alpha + \rho)^2(k_2 + \phi)k_3k_4}, \quad w_3 = 1, \quad w_4 = \frac{\gamma(1 - \theta)}{k_2 + \phi}, \\
w_5 &= \frac{\gamma(k_2\theta + \phi)}{k_3(k_2 + \phi)}, \quad w_6 = \frac{\gamma\tau(k_2\theta + \phi)}{k_3k_4(k_2 + \phi)}, \quad w_7 = \frac{\gamma Q}{k_3k_4(k_2 + \phi)(\mu + m)}
\end{aligned} \tag{4.40}$$

With Q define as $(k_2\theta + \phi)[k_4\psi_2 + \tau\psi_3] + k_3\psi_1(1 - \theta)$ and we compute a

left eigenvector satisfying $v \cdot w = 1$ given by

$$\begin{aligned}
v_1 &= 0, \quad v_2 = 0, \quad v_3 = 1, \quad v_4 = \frac{k_1k_2k_3(\mu + \alpha + \rho) - A_1\gamma\theta(\eta k_4 - \varepsilon\tau)}{k_3k_4(\mu + \alpha + \rho)(1 - \theta)\gamma}, \\
v_5 &= \frac{A_1(\varepsilon\tau + \eta k_4)}{k_3k_4(\mu + \alpha + \rho)}, \quad v_6 = \frac{A_1\varepsilon}{k_4(\mu + \alpha + \rho)}, \quad v_7 = 0
\end{aligned}$$

Furthermore, the associated non zero second partial derivatives of model (4.36) evaluated at (E_0, β^*) is obtained as:

$$\frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_1 \partial x_4} = \frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_4 \partial x_1} = \frac{\mu \rho (\beta - \sigma)}{\Lambda(\mu + \alpha + \rho)}, \quad \frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_1 \partial x_5} = \frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_5 \partial x_1} = \frac{\mu \rho (\beta - \sigma) \eta}{\Lambda(\mu + \alpha + \rho)},$$

$$\frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_1 \partial x_6} = \frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_6 \partial x_1} = \frac{\mu \rho (\beta - \sigma) \varepsilon}{\Lambda(\mu + \alpha + \rho)}, \quad \frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_2 \partial x_4} = \frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_4 \partial x_2} = \frac{-\mu \rho (\beta - \sigma) (\mu + \alpha)}{\Lambda(\mu + \alpha + \rho)}$$

$$\frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_2 \partial x_5} = \frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_5 \partial x_2} = \frac{-\mu \rho (\beta - \sigma) (\mu + \alpha) \eta}{\Lambda(\mu + \alpha + \rho)}, \quad \frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_2 \partial x_6} = \frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_6 \partial x_2} = \frac{-\mu \rho (\beta - \sigma) (\mu + \alpha) \varepsilon}{\Lambda(\mu + \alpha + \rho)}$$

$$\frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_3 \partial x_4} = \frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_4 \partial x_3} = \frac{-\mu [\beta(\mu + \alpha) + \sigma \rho]}{\Lambda(\mu + \alpha + \rho)}, \quad \frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_3 \partial x_5} = \frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_5 \partial x_3} = \frac{-\mu [\beta(\mu + \alpha) + \sigma \rho] \eta}{\Lambda(\mu + \alpha + \rho)}$$

$$\frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_3 \partial x_6} = \frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_6 \partial x_3} = \frac{-\mu [\beta(\mu + \alpha) + \sigma \rho] \varepsilon}{\Lambda(\mu + \alpha + \rho)}, \quad \frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_4 \partial x_4} = -2 \frac{\mu [\beta(\mu + \alpha) + \sigma \rho]}{\Lambda(\mu + \alpha + \rho)}$$

$$\frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_4 \partial x_5} = \frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_5 \partial x_4} = \frac{-\mu (\eta + 1) [\beta(\mu + \alpha) + \sigma \rho]}{\Lambda(\mu + \alpha + \rho)}, \quad \frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_4 \partial x_6} = \frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_6 \partial x_4} = \frac{-\mu (\varepsilon + 1) [\beta(\mu + \alpha) + \sigma \rho]}{\Lambda(\mu + \alpha + \rho)}$$

$$\frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_4 \partial x_7} = \frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_7 \partial x_4} = \frac{-\mu [\beta(\mu + \alpha) + \sigma \rho] \varepsilon}{\Lambda(\mu + \alpha + \rho)}, \quad \frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_5 \partial x_5} = -2 \frac{\mu [\beta(\mu + \alpha) + \sigma \rho] \eta}{\Lambda(\mu + \alpha + \rho)}$$

$$\frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_5 \partial x_6} = \frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_6 \partial x_5} = \frac{-\mu (\eta + \varepsilon) [\beta(\mu + \alpha) + \sigma \rho]}{\Lambda(\mu + \alpha + \rho)}, \quad \frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_5 \partial x_7} = \frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_7 \partial x_5} = \frac{-\mu [\beta(\mu + \alpha) + \sigma \rho] \eta}{\Lambda(\mu + \alpha + \rho)}$$

$$\frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_6 \partial x_6} = \frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_6 \partial x_6} = \frac{2\mu [\beta(\mu + \alpha) + \sigma \rho] \eta}{\Lambda(\mu + \alpha + \rho)}$$

Now, the coefficient of \bar{a} and \bar{b} defined by Theorem 4.5 in (Song & Lou, 2013) is calculated as follows:

$$= \gamma(\mu + \alpha)[k_3k_4(1 - \theta) + (k_4\eta + \varepsilon\tau)(k_2\theta + \phi)] \frac{\gamma(\mu + \alpha)T_1}{(k_2 + \phi)(\mu + \alpha + \rho)k_3k_4} > 0 \quad (4.41)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{a} &= \sum_{k,i,j=1}^7 v_k w_i w_j \frac{\partial^2 f_k}{\partial x_i \partial x_j}(E_0, \beta^*) \\ &= v_3 w_1 \left[w_4 \frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_1 \partial x_4} + w_5 \frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_1 \partial x_5} + w_6 \frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_1 \partial x_6} \right] + v_3 w_2 \left[w_4 \frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_2 \partial x_4} + w_5 \frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_2 \partial x_5} + w_6 \frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_2 \partial x_6} \right] \\ &\quad + v_3 w_4 \left[w_1 \frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_4 \partial x_1} + w_2 \frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_4 \partial x_2} + w_3 \frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_4 \partial x_3} + w_4 \frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_4 \partial x_4} + w_5 \frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_4 \partial x_5} + w_6 \frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_4 \partial x_6} + w_7 \frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_4 \partial x_7} \right] \\ &\quad + v_3 w_5 \left[w_1 \frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_5 \partial x_1} + w_2 \frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_5 \partial x_2} + w_3 \frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_5 \partial x_3} + w_4 \frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_5 \partial x_4} + w_5 \frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_5 \partial x_5} + w_6 \frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_5 \partial x_6} + w_7 \frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_5 \partial x_7} \right] \\ &\quad + v_3 w_6 \left[w_1 \frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_6 \partial x_1} + w_2 \frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_6 \partial x_2} + w_3 \frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_6 \partial x_3} + w_4 \frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_6 \partial x_4} + w_5 \frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_6 \partial x_5} + w_6 \frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_6 \partial x_6} + w_7 \frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_6 \partial x_7} \right] \\ &\quad + v_3 w_3 \left[w_4 \frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_3 \partial x_4} + w_5 \frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_3 \partial x_5} + w_6 \frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_3 \partial x_6} \right] + v_3 w_7 \left[w_4 \frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_7 \partial x_4} + w_5 \frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_7 \partial x_5} + w_6 \frac{\partial f_3}{\partial x_7 \partial x_6} \right] \end{aligned}$$

$$\bar{a} = \frac{2\mu(\beta^* - \sigma)\gamma T_1 [w_1 \rho - w_2] - 2\mu[\beta^*(\mu + \alpha) + \sigma\rho]\gamma T_1 [w_1 + w_4 + w_5 + w_6 + w_7]}{\Lambda(\mu + \alpha + \rho)k_3k_4(k_2 + \phi)} \quad (4.42)$$

Then, solving for ρ :

$$\rho^* = \frac{(\beta^* - \sigma)w_2 + \beta^*(\alpha + \mu)(w_1 + w_4 + w_5 + w_6 + w_7)}{(\beta^* - \sigma)w_1 - \sigma(w_1 + w_4 + w_5 + w_6 + w_7)} \quad (4.43)$$

From the calculated values of the bifurcation coefficients \bar{a} and \bar{b} , it can be observed that \bar{b} , as defined in equation (4.1.3.4), remains strictly positive. Consequently, the model described by system (4.36) exhibits a backward bifurcation at the threshold $\mathcal{R}_{0V} = 1$ whenever $\bar{a} > 0$. This condition corresponds to the case where $\rho < \rho^*$, as stated in equation (4.43). On the other hand, the model undergoes a forward bifurcation at $\mathcal{R}_{0V} = 1$ if $\bar{a} < 0$, which occurs when $\rho > \rho^*$. These findings formally establish the result presented in Theorem 4.1.7.

In essence, the analysis reveals that the occurrence of backward bifurcation in model (4.36)

is primarily driven by insufficient vaccination coverage that is, when the vaccination rate ρ is too low, resulting in a proportion of vaccinated individuals at the disease-free equilibrium that falls short of the critical threshold ρ^* .

Figure 4.2: Backward bifurcation for Single Strain Model in the plane (R_0, I^*) , Parameter value use are $\gamma = 10, \delta_1 = 2.99e - 1, \rho = 4$

The condition of backward bifurcation clearly shows the importance of vaccination. For higher value of $\rho (> \rho^*)$, the condition $\mathcal{R}_{0V} < 1$ is insufficient for eliminating COVID-19 epidemic and a slight change in vaccination rate on population can alter the success of vaccination program. However, the presence of backward bifurcation in the transmission dynamics of COVID-19 disease make elimination of the disease difficult, since \mathcal{R}_{0V} has to be significantly less than 3.8.

Figure 4.3: Forward bifurcation in the plane (R_0, I^*) , Parameter values used are $\gamma = 7.15e - 02$, $\delta_1 = 1.50e - 2$, $\rho = 1.0795$ other parameters are presented in Table 4.1

Figure 4.3 describes a scenario where the disease-free state loses stability and a stable endemic state appears once the reproduction number exceeds one. This indicates a gradual shift from no infection to sustained COVID-19 presence as transmission intensifies.

4.1.3.5 Parameter Estimation and Sensitivity Analysis

To effectively simulate the COVID-19 epidemic in Nigeria using the proposed epidemiological model, and to assess the potential impact of vaccination alongside other intervention strategies, it is essential to validate the model by aligning it with real-world data. This validation process involves fitting the model to observed data obtained from the Nigeria Centre for Disease Control (NCDC) and the Our World in Data repository (NCDC, 2020; Worldometer, 2024). By minimizing the sum of squared differences between observed and predicted values, a nonlinear least-squares fitting technique is employed to estimate unknown model parameters. Among the 20 parameters in-

volved in the model, some (such as $\psi_1, \psi_2, \psi_3, \Lambda$, and γ) are sourced from published literature. The remaining parameters ($\alpha, m, \delta_1, \delta_2, \rho, \phi, \varepsilon, \eta, \beta_1, \sigma_1, s, w, \tau, \mu$) are inferred through data fitting techniques and summarized in Table 4.1.

4.1.3.6 Baseline Parameter Values for the Model

The model defined in equation (3.2) explores the spread of a dominant strain of COVID-19 in Nigeria while accounting for the effects of vaccination. Parameter calibration was carried out using publicly available daily COVID-19 case data from NCDC and Our World in Data (NCDC, 2020; Worldometer, 2024). These datasets were used to define initial conditions and determine parameters with known values, facilitating the estimation of unknown quantities through model fitting. The simulations cover the period from March 9, 2020, to August 9, 2020—beginning six days after Nigeria’s index case was officially confirmed. This period also corresponds with the implementation of public health measures such as partial lockdowns, physical distancing, and mask mandates.

According to the findings in Enahoro *et al.* (2020), the average incubation period for COVID-19 is approximately 5.1 days (with a range of 3 to 14 days), resulting in a transition rate of $\gamma = 1/5.1$. Following the assumptions in (Enahoro *et al.*, 2020; Okuonghae & Omame, 2020), the infectiousness of asymptomatic individuals is assumed to be half that of symptomatic individuals, yielding $\theta = 1/2$. Due to uncertainties in the precise proportion of asymptomatic cases, recovery rates were selected based on a 7 to 15-day recovery window. Specifically, $\psi_1 = \psi_2 = 1/7$ for asymptomatic and symptomatic individuals, while the recovery rate for hospitalized or self-isolating individuals is taken as $\psi_3 = 1/15$. The recruitment rate Λ into the susceptible class is estimated at 13,942 individuals per day, using Nigeria’s estimated population of 211.4 million (WHO, 2021).

Initial values for the state variables were set using available case reports and logical

assumptions about pre-existing exposures prior to detection. These were defined as: $S(0) = 211,400,691$, $V(0) = 0$, $E(0) = 11$, $I_A(0) = 0$, $I_S(0) = 2$, $H(0) = 0$, and $R(0) = 0$. Thus, the fitted parameters are summarized in Table 4.1, and the corresponding model fit is illustrated in Figure 4.4.

Figure 4.4: The daily COVID-19 cumulative cases in Nigeria from March 09 to August 09, 2020 with the best fitted curve from simulations of the single strain model

As displayed above, the real COVID-19 Nigerian cases and the fitted curve have been shown in Figure 4.4 wherein it is observed that the model fits NCDC data well enough.

Figure 4.5: Residuals for the best fitted curve

Furthermore, Figure 4.5 show a justified trend of the obtained residuals as they are scattered evenly below and above the horizontal line. By implication, residuals are useful for detecting outlying y-values and checking the linear regression assumptions with respect to the error term in the regression model. Although, high-leverage observations have smaller residuals because they often shift the regression line or surface closer to them (i.e The numbers for residues show the vertical distance between reported data and fitted curve). Thus, when such residues are observed to be scattered randomly above and below the horizontal line, then the model (3.1) is said to fit the data relatively well.

Table 4.1: **Baseline values of the paramaters used in Model (3.2)**

Parameters	Values (Range)	unit	Reference (Source)
Λ	13942	day^{-1}	(WHO, 2019)
γ	$7.15e - 02$	day^{-1}	(Iboi <i>et al.</i> , 2020)
ψ_1	$1.429e - 01$	day^{-1}	(Iboi <i>et al.</i> , 2020)
ψ_2	$1.429e - 01$	day^{-1}	(Iboi <i>et al.</i> , 2020)
ψ_3	$7.14e - 02$	day^{-1}	(Enahoro <i>et al.</i> , 2020)
θ	$5.000e - 01$	day^{-1}	(Enahoro <i>et al.</i> , 2020)
Fitted Parameter			
m	$1.002e - 01$ (2.000 – 0.100)	day^{-1}	Fitted
α	2.1868 (3.000 – 0.0043)	day^{-1}	Fitted
ρ	1.0795 (2.000 – 0.600)	day^{-1}	Fitted
δ_1	$1.50e - 02$ (5 – 0.0009)	day^{-1}	Fitted
δ_2	$2.50e - 02$ (5 – 0.0001)	day^{-1}	Fitted
ϕ	1.0000 (1 – 0.0345)	day^{-1}	Fitted
τ	$3.43e - 02$ (3 – 0.0343)	day^{-1}	Fitted
σ_1	2.5625 (5 – 0.0529)	day^{-1}	Fitted
β_1	2.5265 (5 – 0.00529)	day^{-1}	Fitted
w	$1.60e - 03$ (0.9 – 0.0013)	day^{-1}	Fitted
s	$5.200e - 01$ (1 – 0.0040)	day^{-1}	Fitted
η	$5.377e - 01$ (1 – 0.0034)	day^{-1}	Fitted
ε	$1.13e - 01$ (0.9 – 0.0056)	day^{-1}	Fitted
μ	$6.99e - 01$ (0.7 – 0.0014)	day^{-1}	Fitted

4.1.3.7 Sensitivity Analysis for the Single Strain Model

This section investigates how variations in key parameters affect the control reproduction number, thereby identifying the parameters that play the most significant roles in the transmission of COVID-19. Sensitivity analysis also helps reveal how uncertainty in parameter estimates may influence the model’s predictive accuracy. To perform this analysis, we adopt the Latin Hypercube Sampling coupled with Partial Rank Correlation Coefficients (LHS/PRCC), which is well suited for evaluating parameter importance in complex models with high-dimensional parameter spaces.

Using this approach, we analyze the responsiveness of the model’s output—specifically the control reproduction number, \mathcal{R}_{0V} —to changes in each input parameter. LHS enables the efficient generation of diverse parameter combinations across defined ranges

(as specified in Table 4.1), assuming a uniform distribution for each parameter. For each sampled set, the model is simulated to calculate \mathcal{R}_{0V} , and PRCC values are subsequently computed to quantify the strength and direction of correlation between each parameter and the output.

This methodology provides a more comprehensive understanding of the model's behavior with fewer simulations compared to conventional techniques (Danbaba & Garba, 2020; Marino *et al.*, 2008). The resulting PRCC values highlight the relative significance of each parameter in influencing COVID-19 transmission dynamics. The outcomes of the sensitivity analysis are visually presented in the PRCC bar chart shown in Figure 4.6.

Figure 4.6: Sensitivity plot of the reproduction number for single strain model

Figure 4.6 illustrates the sensitivity of the control reproduction number, \mathcal{R}_{0V} , to varia-

tions in each model parameter. The results identify several parameters that significantly influence the transmission dynamics of COVID-19. Among those with the most positive correlation to \mathcal{R}_{0V} are the effective transmission rate among susceptible individuals (β), the rate at which exposed individuals progress to the infectious stage (γ), the waning rate of vaccine-induced immunity (α), and the rate at which vaccinated individuals contract the infection (σ). In contrast, the natural mortality rate (μ) shows the strongest negative correlation, indicating that natural death can suppress disease spread by reducing the pool of susceptible or infectious individuals. Additionally, other negatively correlated parameters include the recovery rate (ψ), the relative infectiousness of asymptomatic individuals (θ), and the vaccination rate (ρ).

These relationships carry meaningful public health implications. For instance, the strong positive influence of β suggests that interventions aimed at reducing human-to-human contact—such as mask usage, social distancing, and lockdowns—are vital for limiting disease transmission. Similarly, the positive correlation of γ implies that slowing the progression from exposure to active infection, possibly through improved immunity or early intervention, can mitigate the outbreak's intensity.

The effect of α further emphasizes the importance of vaccine durability: extending the duration of immunity conferred by vaccination would likely reduce infection rates. On the other hand, the negative associations of ϕ and θ suggest that improved immune function whether from previous vaccination, mild infections, or enhanced nutrition can slow progression to symptomatic disease and improve recovery outcomes.

Overall, the PRCC results provide valuable insights into how various biological and behavioral factors impact disease spread. This knowledge can inform targeted strategies to strengthen public health responses and optimize resource allocation during COVID-

19 outbreaks.

4.1.4 Numerical Simulation and Discussions for Single Strain COVID-19 Model

This section presents the numerical analysis of the proposed model system (3.2) under two primary conditions: the pre-vaccination phase and the period during which vaccination is actively implemented. The objective is to assess the influence of vaccination on the spread and control of the dominant strain of COVID-19. Furthermore, the study investigates how variations in highly sensitive parameters affect the model's dynamics and validates the theoretical results established earlier. All parameter values utilized in the simulations, as provided in Table 4.1, are biologically reasonable. Numerical integration of the system was performed using the classical fourth-order Runge-Kutta method, employing initial conditions and parameter estimates also summarized in Table 4.1.

Scenario 1: Simulation of the epidemic trajectory before the availability of vaccines. In this case, the model assumes no vaccination by setting both the vaccinated compartment ($V = 0$) and the vaccination rate ($\rho = 0$) to zero, thereby aligning with the initial phase of the pandemic as documented by the Nigeria Centre for Disease Control (NCDC). During this period, non-pharmaceutical interventions (NPIs)—such as wearing face masks, maintaining personal hygiene, and practicing social distancing—were the primary strategies employed to contain the virus.

Figures 4.7 and 4.8 illustrate the temporal dynamics of different sub-populations in the absence of vaccination. These figures also contrast scenarios where the basic reproduction number \mathcal{R}_0 is less than one and greater than one, providing insights into the threshold behavior and potential for disease persistence or elimination under varying transmission conditions.

Figure 4.7: Evolution of sub population when $\mathcal{R}_0 < 1$

Figure 4.7 shows a consistent decline in the numbers of exposed, asymptomatic, and symptomatic individuals when the transmission rate (β) is decreased to 0.2124, resulting in a basic reproduction number of 0.8403. This reduction is attributed to the implementation of preventive measures, including social distancing (s) and face-mask usage (w) in public areas. Additionally, the numbers of recovered and hospitalized individuals initially rise, peak, and then gradually decrease over a three-month period. These simulation results indicate that early adoption of such non-pharmaceutical interventions (NPIs) in Nigeria could have substantially mitigated the spread of COVID-19. However, these measures were not mandated until April 25, 2020, when Lagos State authorities enforced mask usage in public—approximately two months after the country’s first confirmed case.

Figure 4.8: Evolution of sub population when $\mathcal{R}_0 > 1$

Figure 4.8 illustrates the outbreak trajectory under a high-transmission scenario, where the basic reproduction number exceeds unity ($\mathcal{R}_0 = 2.47$) in the absence of vaccination. In this case, the exposed population grows rapidly due to a high effective contact rate ($\beta = 1.2087$), leading to approximately 4.5 million individuals becoming exposed within the first two months. This surge triggers a corresponding rise in both symptomatic and asymptomatic infections within the first three months. Thereafter, the system trends toward a steady state, likely influenced by the subsequent enforcement of intensified non-pharmaceutical interventions (NPIs), such as mask mandates and social distancing. Figures 4.7 and 4.8 present the simulation results for new COVID-19 cases over a 120-day period. The analysis explores the effects of varying the force of infection ($\beta = 1.2087, 1.3087, 1.4087$), both in the presence and absence of vaccination, under conditions where $\mathcal{R}_0 > 1$. These results offer critical insights into the epidemic trajectory under differing transmission intensities and highlight the mitigating role of vaccination

in high-risk scenarios.

Figure 4.9: Evolution of sub population at $\mathcal{R}_0 > 1$ when, $V \neq 0$

Figure 4.9 illustrates the effect of vaccination on controlling the spread of COVID-19, compared to the disease dynamics shown in Figure 4.10 without vaccination. From Figure 4.9, it is evident that at an infection rate of $\beta = 1.2018$, the number of new cases initially declines sharply within the first few days, dropping to approximately 2.7 million. However, this is followed by a gradual increase due to varying levels of vaccine acceptance during the early stages of the vaccination rollout. Over time, as government agencies and private organizations intensify efforts to promote vaccination and raise public awareness about its benefits, the number of new cases starts to decline steadily until a stable level is reached. A similar pattern emerges when the infection rate is further increased from $\beta = 1.2018$ to $\beta = 1.4018$.

Figure 4.10: Assessment of the impact of different values of β on new cases of Covid 19 in Nigeria

Figure 4.10, which utilizes the same parameter values as those presented in Table 4.1, illustrates the dynamics of the COVID-19 outbreak without incorporating the vaccinated sub-population. Under this scenario, a moderate decline in new infections is observed from approximately 1.9 million to 1.7 million cases primarily attributed to the sustained implementation of non-pharmaceutical interventions (NPIs). However, when compared with the results in Figure 4.9, which includes vaccination, the reduction in cases is less pronounced. This comparison underscores the enhanced effectiveness of vaccination as a complementary strategy to NPIs.

The findings suggest that in the absence of a vaccination campaign, approximately 70% of the population would need to consistently adhere to NPIs to achieve a significant decline in new infections. In contrast, introducing vaccination to about 46% of the population could yield a comparable reduction in case numbers. This aligns with conclusions

drawn by Okuonghae in (Okuonghae & Omame, 2020), highlighting the critical role of vaccination in mitigating COVID-19 transmission more efficiently than reliance on NPIs alone.

Figure 4.11: Disease Prevalence when $\mathcal{R}_0 > 1$, when $V = 0$

Figures 4.11 and 4.12 illustrate the impact of vaccination on COVID-19 prevalence as captured by the proposed model. In Figure 4.11, the simulation results indicate a peak infection level of approximately 2.4 million cases across the nation in the absence of vaccination, even with preventive measures in place. Further simulations were conducted to evaluate the effects of vaccination on a population level by running model (3.2) under varying effective contact rates,

Figure 4.12: Disease Prevalence when $\mathcal{R}_0 > 1$, when $V \neq 0$

as shown in Figure 4.12. These results demonstrate a substantial reduction in disease prevalence—around 10% within the same time frame. This highlights the critical role of vaccination in mitigating the spread of COVID-19. The simulations reveal that with vaccination, the peak infection prevalence decreases to around 1.8 million individuals, compared to the 2.1 million cases projected without vaccine administration. This likely explains the subsequent relaxation of strict non-pharmaceutical interventions (NPIs) in public settings following the vaccine rollout.

Figure 4.13: Impact of varying α on infected Compartment

Furthermore, the model simulates the progression of both asymptomatic and symptomatic infections to assess how variations in vaccination rate (ρ) and vaccine-induced immunity waning rate (α) influence disease dynamics. As shown in Figure 4.13, different levels of vaccine effectiveness, represented by $\alpha = 0.2, 0.5, 1$, significantly affect the population distribution. The number of asymptomatic individuals (illustrated with solid lines) exhibits a steady decline, stabilizing over time, while the number of symptomatic individuals (represented with dashed lines) shows a gradual increase. This rise continues as individuals transition from the exposed to symptomatic state, peaking before eventually decreasing. These results highlight the role of vaccination in moderating the progression from asymptomatic to symptomatic infection, effectively reducing the severity and spread of the disease within the population.

Figure 4.14: The Impact of varying ρ and α on the sub-population

Likewise, the influence of vaccination is illustrated in Figure 4.14, which demonstrates the evolution of both symptomatic and asymptomatic infectious populations under varying vaccination rates ρ , ranging from 0.25 to 1. The simulation results indicate that even a vaccination coverage of 25% can substantially reduce the spread of infection. Furthermore, as the vaccination rate increases toward 100%, the decline in the number of infectious individuals becomes more pronounced over time, emphasizing the importance of achieving higher vaccination coverage for effective disease control.

In addition to these simulations, contour plots were generated to visualize how the control reproduction number \mathcal{R}_c responds to changes in key sensitive and controllable parameters. Specifically, Figure 4.15 presents \mathcal{R}_c plotted as a function of selected model parameters, providing deeper insight into the combined effects of parameter variations on disease transmission.

Figure 4.15: Contour plot of \mathcal{R}_c with ρ and α

Figure 4.15 illustrates the combined effect of vaccination coverage and waning immunity on the control reproduction number. The analysis shows that increasing the vaccination rate, means a larger proportion of the population receives the vaccine while simultaneously reducing the rate of immunity loss among vaccinated individuals leads to a significant decline in the control reproduction number. This depicts the importance of achieving broad vaccine coverage and ensuring that vaccines offer long lasting protection as essential strategies for effectively controlling and potentially eliminating COVID-19 in Nigeria. To deepen the understanding of how vaccination influences the trajectory of infection, further simulations were conducted to examine its impact on the progression of exposed individuals within the population.

Figure 4.16: Contour plot of \mathcal{R}_c with ρ and θ

Figure 4.16 demonstrates that eliminating COVID-19 nationwide is possible by increasing vaccination coverage and improving vaccine effectiveness, which together reduce the control reproduction number below one. Additionally, strategies such as contact tracing, routine testing, and early identification of exposed individuals can decrease the number of infectious cases.

Figure 4.17: Contour plot of \mathcal{R}_c with ρ and σ

Similarly, Figure 4.17 shows a decrease in the value of the reproduction number with increasing vaccination rate and decreasing effective contact rate with infected COVID-19 individuals (σ), which implies the scaling up vaccination coverage with enforcement of COVID-19 protocols will both work together to drive the epidemic towards extinction.

Figure 4.18: Contour plot of \mathcal{R}_c with β and α

In the same vein, Figure 4.18 shows that decreasing the effective infection rate with a steady decrease in the vaccine-derived immunity waning rate would result in a remarkable reduction in the control reproduction number below unity and this could eventually lead to the eventual elimination of the disease in the population, particularly in places where adherence to the COVID-19 social protocols is strictly enforced.

4.2 Qualitative Analysis of Dual Strain COVID-19 Model

In this section, we discussed the positivity and boundedness of solutions, determined the equilibrium points, calculated the basic reproduction number, and carried out a stability analysis of the proposed dual-strain model described in the equation. (3.6).

4.2.1 Positivity of the Model Solution

For the model equations to be epidemiologically meaningful, there is need to prove that the state variables are non-negative $\forall t \geq 0$.

Theorem 4.2.1. *Let the initial data set be $(S, V, E_1, I_1, E_2, I_2, H, R) > 0$. The solution set of the model system (3.6) is positive $\forall t \geq 0$.*

Proof:

From the model equations given in (3.6), considering the first equation:

$$\frac{dS}{dt} = \Pi + mR - (\lambda_1 + \lambda_2)S + \alpha V - (\rho + \mu)S \quad (4.44)$$

By considering the negative term, and ignoring the rest, equation (4.44) is reduced to

$$\frac{dS}{dt} \geq -(\lambda_u + \rho + \mu)S \quad (4.45)$$

with $\lambda_u = \lambda_1 + \lambda_2$, equation (4.45) becomes the first-order linear differential inequality which can be solved by a variable separable method $y' = f(x)g(y)$ (where $S \geq 0$) resulting in

$$\int_{S(0)}^{S(t)} \frac{dS}{S} \geq - \int_0^t (\rho + \mu).dt, \quad (4.46)$$

The solution to the foregoing equation yields,

$$S(t) \geq S(0)e^{-(\rho+\mu)t}$$

However, the solution simplifies to $S(t) \geq S(0)e^{-(\rho+\mu)t}$, $S(0) \geq 0$, $\forall t > 0$,

since $S_0 \geq 0$, in the absence of COVID-19 disease. Adopting the same procedure to the remaining model variables, we have $V(0) \geq 0$, $E_1(0) \geq 0$, $I_1(0) \geq 0$, $E_2(0) \geq 0$, $I_2(0) \geq 0$, $H(0) \geq 0$, $R(0) \geq 0$ > 0 .

Therefore, the set of the model variables $S(t)$, $V(t)$, $E_1(t)$, $I_1(t)$, $E_2(t)$, $I_2(t)$, and $H(t)$, are all positive $\forall t > 0$.

4.2.1.1 Invariant Region

The SEIHR formulated model is represented by differential equations in system (3.6), which is to be analyzed in a feasible region ω , and all state variables and parameters of the model are assumed to be positive $\forall t \geq 0$. The bounded region is obtained through the following lemma.

Lemma 4.2.1. *The set Ω is positively invariant and attracts all solutions in \mathcal{R}_+^8*

Proof:

Since $N(t) = S(t) + V(t) + E_1(t) + I_1(t) + E_2(t) + H(t) + R(t)$, then the derivative of $N(t)$ is given by

$$\frac{dN}{dt} = \frac{dS}{dt} + \frac{dV}{dt} + \frac{dE_1}{dt} + \frac{dI_1}{dt} + \frac{dE_2}{dt} + \frac{dI_2}{dt} + \frac{dH}{dt} + \frac{dR}{dt} \quad (4.47)$$

substituting model equation (3.6) into equation (4.47) and simplifying gives:

$$\frac{dN}{dt} = \Pi - \mu N - (\delta_1 I_1 + \delta_2 I_2 + \delta_{12} H + \delta_{21} H) \quad (4.48)$$

Since $\delta_1 > 0$, $\delta_2 > 0$, $\delta_{12} > 0$, $\delta_{21} > 0$, and $I(t), H(t) \geq 0$ for all $t \geq 0$, then equation

(4.48) becomes:

$$\frac{dN}{dt} \leq \Pi - \mu N \quad (4.49)$$

Integrating equation (4.49) and solving gives:

$$\begin{aligned} N(t) &\leq \frac{\Pi}{\mu} + \left(N(0) - \frac{\Pi}{\mu} \right) e^{-\mu t} \\ &\leq N(0)e^{-\mu t} + \frac{\Pi}{\mu} (1 - e^{-\mu t}) \end{aligned} \quad (4.50)$$

Therefore, as $t \rightarrow \infty^+$, $N(t) \leq \frac{\Pi}{\mu}$

Hence:

$$\Omega = \left\{ (S, V, E_1, I_1, E_2, I_2, H, R) \in \mathcal{R}_+^8 : N \leq \frac{\Pi}{\mu} \right\} \quad (4.51)$$

This implies that $\frac{\Pi}{\mu}$ are the upper bond for the population $N(t)$. Thus, from lemma 4.2.1, the set Ω is positive invariant with respect to system of equations (3.6). Then we, conclude that the set Ω is positively invariant and all solutions of system (3.6) are non negative and epidemiological well posed.

4.2.1.2 Existence and Uniqueness of the solution

From the first order-differential equation given in the form $y' = f(t, y), y(t_0) = y_0$ The following question will be of interest:

- i Under what condition can we say that a solution to the equation y' exist? does a unique solution exist
- ii Under what condition does a unique solution exist to the equation y'

Considering the following equation to answer the questions.

$$\begin{aligned}
F_1 &= \Pi + mR - (\lambda_1 + \lambda_2)S + \alpha V - (\rho + \mu)S, \\
F_2 &= \rho S - \sigma(\lambda_1 + \lambda_2)V - (\alpha + \mu)V, \\
F_3 &= (S + \sigma V)\lambda_1 - (\gamma_1 + \mu)E_1, \\
F_4 &= \gamma_1 E_1 - (\tau_1 + \delta_1 + \psi_1 + \mu)I_1, \\
F_5 &= (S + \sigma V)\lambda_2 - (\gamma_2 + \mu)E_2, \\
F_6 &= \gamma_2 E_2 - (\tau_2 + \delta_2 + \psi_2 + \mu)I_2, \\
F_7 &= \tau_1 I_1 + \tau_2 I_2 - (\psi_3 + \mu + \delta_{12} + \delta_{21})H, \\
F_8 &= \psi_1 I_1 + \psi_2 I_2 + \psi_3 H - (m + \mu)R.
\end{aligned} \tag{4.52}$$

4.2.1.3 Uniqueness of the Solution

Theorem 4.2.2. *Let \mathcal{D} denote the domain: $|t - t_0| \leq a$, $\|y - y_0\| \leq b$, $y = (y_1, y_2 \dots y_n)$, $y_0 = (y_{1(0)}, y_{2(0)} \dots y_{n(0)})$*

Proof: Suppose $F(t, y)$ satisfy the Lipschitz condition; Therefore

$$\|f(t, y_2) - f(t, y_1)\| \leq k \|y_2 - y_1\| \tag{4.53}$$

Whenever the points (t, y_1) and (t, y_2) belong to the domain \mathcal{M} and k is used to represent the positive constant, then there exist a constant $a > 0$ and a unique solution $y(t)$ of system 3.6 in the interval $|t - t_0| \leq a$. It is important to note that equation (4.53) is satisfied by $(\partial f_i / \partial y_j)$, $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$ to be continuous and bounded in domain \mathcal{D}

If $f(t, y)$ has a continuous partial derivative $(\partial f_i / \partial y_j)$ on a bounded closed convex domain \mathbb{R} (i.e, the convex set of real numbers), where \mathbb{R} is used to denote real number; then it satisfies a Lipschitz condition in \mathbb{R} .

4.2.1.4 Existence of a Solution

Theorem 4.2.3. *Let the domain be denoted by \mathcal{D} , also defined in equation 4.2.2, such that equation 4.53 hold. Then, the existing solution of equation 4.52 is bounded in the domain \mathcal{D}*

we show $\frac{\partial F_i}{\partial x_j}$ with $i, j = 1 \dots 8$ where F_i is the right side of the model 3.6.

Taking F_1 from the first equation in the model 4.52 and partially differentiating with respect to the state variables

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{\partial F_1}{\partial S} &= -(\lambda_u + \rho + \mu), & \left| \frac{\partial F_1}{\partial S} \right| &= |-(\lambda_u + \rho + \mu)| < \infty. & \frac{\partial F_1}{\partial V} &= \alpha, & \left| \frac{\partial F_1}{\partial V} \right| &= |\alpha| < \infty \\
 \frac{\partial F_1}{\partial R} &= m, & \left| \frac{\partial F_1}{\partial R} \right| &= |m| < \infty. & \frac{\partial F_2}{\partial S} &= -\rho, & \left| \frac{\partial F_2}{\partial S} \right| &= |-\rho| < \infty. \\
 \frac{\partial F_2}{\partial V} &= -(\sigma\lambda_u + \alpha + \mu), & \left| \frac{\partial F_2}{\partial V} \right| &= |-(\sigma\lambda_u + \alpha + \mu)| < \infty. & \frac{\partial F_3}{\partial S} &= \lambda_1, & \left| \frac{\partial F_3}{\partial S} \right| &= |\lambda_1| < \infty. \\
 \frac{\partial F_3}{\partial V} &= \sigma\lambda_1, & \left| \frac{\partial F_3}{\partial V} \right| &= |\sigma\lambda_1| < \infty. & \frac{\partial F_3}{\partial E_1} &= -(\gamma + \mu), & \left| \frac{\partial F_3}{\partial E_1} \right| &= |-(\gamma + \mu)| < \infty.
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{4.54}$$

The same procedures are taken for the remaining Equations of model (4.52). Therefore, all partial derivatives are continuous and bounded; hence, based on Theorem 4.2.3, it is concluded that there exists a unique solution to the model in equation (4.52) in the domain region \mathcal{D} .

4.2.2 Disease-Free Equilibrium (DFE)

The disease free equilibrium (DFE) is an equilibrium where no individuals in the population are infected with any of the two SARs-Cov-2 variants; this condition implies $E_1 = E_2 = I_1 = I_2 = H = R = 0$. Substituting these values into equation 3.6 and solving, the following solutions were obtain:

$$E_0 = \left(\frac{\Pi(\alpha + \mu)}{\mu(\alpha + \rho + \mu)}, \frac{\Pi\rho}{\mu(\alpha + \rho + \mu)}, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0 \right)
 \tag{4.55}$$

We can show that E_0 is locally stable or globally asymptotically stable provided certain conditions are fulfilled.

4.2.2.1 Effective Reproduction Number

The effective reproduction number \mathcal{R}_c of the model (3.6), captures the average number of new SARs-Cov-2 cases generated by a typical SARs-Cov-2 infectious individual introduced into a population where a certain fraction is protected (in presence of control measures i.e vaccination). Although, the basic reproduction number R_0 is derived by considering the worse case scenario where no preventive measures is implemented in the population and R_0 is derived using the next generation matrix method as described in (Diekmann *et al.*, 2010). We will compute the effective reproduction number $R_c = \rho(FV^{-1})$ by applying the next generation method. Where F are the derivatives of the new infections, V is the transition matrix (flow between compartments) and ρ is the spectral radius. The entire derivation of R_c is as follows

$$F = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \frac{\beta_1(V\sigma+S)}{S+V} & 0 & 0 & \frac{\beta_1\varepsilon_1(V\sigma+S)}{S+V} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{\beta_2^*(V\sigma+S)}{S+V} & \frac{\beta_2\varepsilon_2(V\sigma+S)}{S+V} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}; \quad V = \begin{bmatrix} k_1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -\gamma_1 & k_2 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & k_3 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -\gamma_2 & k_4 & 0 \\ 0 & -\tau_1 & 0 & -\tau_2 & k_5 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.56)$$

where $k_1 = \gamma_1 + \mu$, $k_2 = \tau_1 + \delta_1 + \psi_1 + \mu$ and $k_3 = \gamma_2 + \mu$, $k_4 = \tau_2 + \delta_2 + \psi_2 + \mu$, and; $k_5 = \psi_3 + \delta_{12} + \delta_{21} + \mu$) and the next generation matrix (NGM) with large domain

$$\mathbf{KL} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\beta_1 \gamma_1 (V\sigma+S)(\tau_1 \varepsilon_1 + k_5)}{k_1 k_2 k_5 (S+V)} & \frac{\beta_1 (V\sigma+S)(\tau_1 \varepsilon_1 + k_5)}{k_2 k_5 (S+V)} & \frac{\beta_1 \varepsilon_1 \tau_2 \gamma_2 (V\sigma+S)}{k_3 k_4 k_5 (S+V)} & \frac{\beta_1 \varepsilon_1 \tau_2 (V\sigma+S)}{k_4 k_5 (S+V)} & \frac{\beta_1 \varepsilon_1 (V\sigma+S)}{k_5 (S+V)} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{\beta_2 \varepsilon_2 \tau_1 \gamma_1 (V\sigma+S)}{k_3 k_4 k_5 (S+V)} & \frac{\beta_2 \varepsilon_2 \tau_1 (V\sigma+S)}{k_2 k_5 (S+V)} & \frac{\beta_2 \gamma_2 (V\sigma+S)(\tau_2 \varepsilon_2 + k_5)}{k_3 k_4 k_5 (S+V)} & \frac{\beta_2 (V\sigma+S)(\tau_2 \varepsilon_2 + k_5)}{k_4 k_5 (S+V)} & \frac{\beta_2 \varepsilon_2 (V\sigma+S)}{k_5 (S+V)} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.57)$$

It is obvious from the model that, among the four infected states, there are only two that are states-at-infection. We can visualize by looking at matrix F and observing that the entire second, fourth and fifth rows contains zeros. Hence, the Next Generation Matrix L for the small domain is therefore two-dimensional. Thus, using the approach of (Diekmann *et al.*, 2010) with an auxiliary matrix E, the NGM (L) is computed as:

$$\mathbf{L} = \mathbf{E}^T \mathbf{KLE} = \mathbf{E}^T \mathbf{FV}^{-1}$$

$$\mathbf{L} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\beta_1 \gamma_1 (V\sigma+S)(\tau_1 \varepsilon_1 + k_5)}{k_1 k_2 k_5 (S+V)} & \frac{\beta_1 (V\sigma+S)(\tau_1 \varepsilon_1 + k_5)}{k_2 k_5 (S+V)} & \frac{\beta_1 \varepsilon_1 \tau_2 \gamma_2 (V\sigma+S)}{k_3 k_4 k_5 (S+V)} & \frac{\beta_1 \varepsilon_1 \tau_2 (V\sigma+S)}{k_4 k_5 (S+V)} & \frac{\beta_1 \varepsilon_1 (V\sigma+S)}{k_5 (S+V)} \\ \frac{\beta_2 \varepsilon_2 \tau_1 \gamma_1 (V\sigma+S)}{k_3 k_4 k_5 (S+V)} & \frac{\beta_2 \varepsilon_2 \tau_1 (V\sigma+S)}{k_2 k_5 (S+V)} & \frac{\beta_2 \gamma_2 (V\sigma+S)(\tau_2 \varepsilon_2 + k_5)}{k_3 k_4 k_5 (S+V)} & \frac{\beta_2 (V\sigma+S)(\tau_2 \varepsilon_2 + k_5)}{k_4 k_5 (S+V)} & \frac{\beta_2 \varepsilon_2 (V\sigma+S)}{k_5 (S+V)} \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.58)$$

where

$$\mathbf{E} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.59)$$

Therefore, the effective reproduction number \mathcal{R}_c which is the largest dominant eigen-

value of L is given as:

$$\mathcal{R}_{c1} = \frac{\beta_1 \gamma_1 (V\sigma + S) (\tau_1 \varepsilon_1 + k_5)}{k_1 k_2 k_5 (S + V)}, \quad \mathcal{R}_{c2} = \frac{\beta_2 \gamma_2 (V\sigma + S) (\tau_2 \varepsilon_2 + k_5)}{k_3 k_4 k_5 (S + V)} \quad (4.60)$$

Therefore, \mathcal{R}_{01} and \mathcal{R}_{02} are important threshold quantities required to determine whether the situation under consideration is an endemic one or not. The effective reproduction number \mathcal{R}_c for system (3.6) equals the maximum of \mathcal{R}_{01} and \mathcal{R}_{02} , substituting expression V and S from equation 4.55 into equation 4.60, the following result was obtained,

$$\mathcal{R}_c = \max \left\{ \frac{\beta_1 \gamma_1 (\rho\sigma + \alpha + \mu) (\tau_1 \varepsilon_1 + k_5)}{k_1 k_2 k_5 (\alpha + \mu + \rho)}, \quad \frac{\beta_2 \gamma_2 (\rho\sigma + \alpha + \mu) (\tau_2 \varepsilon_2 + k_5)}{k_3 k_4 k_5 (\alpha + \mu + \rho)} \right\} \quad (4.61)$$

The quantity \mathcal{R}_0 is called the basic reproduction number of the model (??) . It represents the average number of new SARs-Cov-2 cases generated by a typical infected individual introduced into a completely susceptible population (i.e., introduced into a population where no one has immunity due to prior infection or immunization, and no public health interventions are implemented in the community). In other words, \mathcal{R}_0 is a measure of the worst-case scenario where a disease is spreading in a population, and no public health control or mitigation measures are implemented. For instance, when $\mathcal{R}_c = 3$, one infected individual will, on average, transmit SARs-Cov-2 to three others during the duration of their infectiousness (i.e., before they recovers or dies from the disease). Thus, in this scenario, the disease will spread rapidly until intervention and mitigation measures are implemented in the population or a certain proportion of the population becomes immune to the disease (following recovery from infection as indicated in model 3.6), thereby contributing to population-wide herd immunity (offering protection to the remaining susceptible population). On the other hand, when control and mitigation measures are implemented, another reproduction number, typically called the effective

reproduction number (and denoted by \mathcal{R}_c), is computed and used to study the dynamics of the model. In the presence of the control and mitigation measures, the total population consists of individuals who are completely susceptible (i.e., those in the S class), those who are infected and those who have developed some immunity (either due to recovery from prior infection or due to the implementation of public health interventions, such as vaccination, that reduces their susceptibility to acquisition of infection). Thus, when $\mathcal{R}_c = 3$, although one infected individual will infect, on average, three others in the population, the number of susceptible individuals available to this infected individual is reduced (due to the fact that some individuals in the population are partially protected).

Furthermore in the scenario where no one has immunity due to prior infection or immunization (Vaccination), and no public health interventions (preventive measures) are implemented in the population, we compute the basic reproduction number \mathcal{R}_0 by setting $V = 0$ in equation (4.61) as

$$\mathcal{R}_0 = \max \left\{ \frac{\beta_1 \gamma_1 (\tau_1 \varepsilon_1 + k_5)}{k_1 k_2 k_5}, \frac{\beta_2 \gamma_2 (\tau_2 \varepsilon_2 + k_5)}{k_3 k_4 k_5} \right\} \quad (4.62)$$

So, the co-epidemic will persist in the society if this threshold quantity is greater than unity.

Theorem 4.2.4. *if $\mathcal{R}_0 = \max \{ \mathcal{R}_{01}, \mathcal{R}_{02} \} < 1$, the disease free equilibrium (E_0) is locally asymptotically stable, otherwise $\mathcal{R}_0 = \max \{ \mathcal{R}_{01}, \mathcal{R}_{02} \} > 1$, (E_0) is unstable*

4.2.3 Stability of the disease- free equilibrium

The stability of our formulated model (3.6) disease-free equilibrium can be explained in the following theorem 4.2.4 : the disease-free equilibrium E_0 of our system of differential equations is locally asymptotically stable if $\mathcal{R}_c < 1$ and unstable if $\mathcal{R}_c > 1$.

Thus, we calculate the Jacobian matrix of our system of differential equations at the disease-free equilibrium, which is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Let } a &= \frac{(\alpha + \mu)}{\alpha + \mu + \rho}, \quad c = \frac{(\alpha + \mu)(\beta_1 \varepsilon_1 + \beta_2 \varepsilon_2)}{\alpha + \mu + \rho}, \quad d = \frac{(\rho \sigma)}{\alpha + \mu + \rho}, \\ e &= \frac{\rho \sigma (\beta_1 \varepsilon_1 + \beta_2 \varepsilon_2)}{\alpha + \mu + \rho}, \quad f = \frac{(\rho \sigma + \alpha + \mu)}{\alpha + \mu + \rho} \end{aligned} \quad (4.63)$$

Thus, the Jacobian matrix is evaluated at infection-free state as :

$$J_{(E_0)} = \begin{bmatrix} -(\rho + m) & \alpha & 0 & -a\beta_1 & 0 & a\beta_2 & -c & m \\ \rho & -(\alpha + \mu) & 0 & -\beta_1 d & 0 & -d\beta_2 & -e & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -k_1 & \beta_1 f & 0 & 0 & \beta_1 \varepsilon_1 f & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \gamma_1 & -k_2 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -k_3 & \beta_2 f & \beta_2 \varepsilon_1 f & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \gamma_2 & -k_4 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \tau_1 & 0 & \tau_2 & -k_5 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \psi_1 & 0 & \psi_2 & \psi_3 & -(m + \mu) \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.64)$$

Its obvious from equation (4.64) that the first four eigenvalues are $\{-(\rho + m), -(\alpha + \mu), \text{ and } -(m + \mu), -k_5\}$. Thus, this reduce equation (4.64) to:

$$\begin{bmatrix} -k_1 & \beta_1 f & 0 & 0 \\ \gamma_1 & -k_2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -k_3 & \beta_2 f \\ 0 & 0 & \gamma_2 & -k_4 \end{bmatrix} = 0 \quad (4.65)$$

solving equation (4.65) the remaining eigenvalues of equation (4.64) are obtained as:

$$-\frac{1}{2}(k_2 + k_1 - \phi_1), \quad -\frac{1}{2}(k_2 + k_1 + \phi_1), \quad -\frac{1}{2}(k_3 + k_4 - \phi_2), \quad -\frac{1}{2}(k_3 + k_4 + \phi_2)$$

and $\phi_1 = \sqrt{4\beta_1\gamma_1 f + k_1^2 - 2k_1k_2 + k_2^2}$, $\phi_2 = \sqrt{4\beta_2\gamma_2 f + k_4^2 - 2k_3k_4 + k_3^2}$. Since associated Jacobian Matrix exhibit's negative eigenvalues, the formulated model (3.6) is locally asymptotically stable at the disease free state.

4.2.4 Global Stability Analysis (\mathcal{E}_0)

To completely eliminate the SARs-CoV-2 illness from all sub-populations, it is crucial to prove the global asymptotic stability of the disease-free equilibrium (DFE). Thus, we utilize the approach detailed in references (Danbaba & Garba, 2020; Kamgang & Sallet, 2005) to define the conditions necessary for ensuring the global asymptotic stability of the DFE. We apply the following Theorem:

Theorem 4.2.5. *Considering the model system (3.6), let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}_+^{n_1+n_2}$ be a positively invariant set. If*

1. *The system (3.6) is defined on the positively invariant set $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}_+^{n_1+n_2}$*
2. *The sub-system $\dot{x}_1 = A_1(x_1, 0) \cdot (x_1 - x_1^*)$ is globally asymptotically stable at the equilibrium x_1^**
3. *For any $x \in \Omega$, the matrix $A_{22}(x)$ is Metzler irreducible*
4. *There exist an upper bound matrix a_{22} for the set $\mathcal{M} = \{A_{22}(x) | x \in \Omega\}$ with the property that either $A_{22}(x) \notin \mathcal{M}$ or if $A_{22}(x) \in \mathcal{M}$ (i.e., $a_{22} = \max_{\Omega} \mathcal{M}$), then for $x^* \in \Omega$ such that, $a_{22} = A_{22}(x^*)$, then $x^* \in \mathcal{M}^8 \times \{0\}$ (the DFE sub-manifold contains the points where the maximum is attained)*

5. The stability modulus of a_{22} satisfies $\alpha(a_{22}) \leq 0$

Then, the associated disease free equilibrium is globally asymptotically stable in Ω .

Proof:

Given model equation (4.52) rewritten in pseudo-triangular form with the use of property of DFE, we have

$$\begin{cases} \dot{x}_1 &= A_{11}(x).(x_1 - x_1^*) + A_{12}(x)x_2 \\ \dot{x}_2 &= A_{22}(x)x_2 \end{cases} \quad (4.66)$$

where $x_1 = (S, V, R)^T$ represents the non transmitting compartments of model (3.6), $x_2 = (E_1, I_1, E_2, I_2, H)^T$ represents the infectious compartments of the model, $x_1^* = (S^*, V^*, R^*)^T$ is the DFE while

$$A_{11}(x) = \begin{pmatrix} -(\mu + \rho) & \alpha & m \\ \rho & -(\mu + \alpha) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -(\mu + m) \end{pmatrix}, \quad A_{12}(x) = \begin{pmatrix} -a\beta_1 & b\beta_2 & -c \\ -d\beta_1 & d\beta_2 & -e \\ \psi_1 & \psi_2 & \psi_3, \end{pmatrix}$$

$$A_{22}(x) = \begin{pmatrix} -k_1 & \beta_1 f & 0 & 0 & \beta_1 \varepsilon_1 f \\ \gamma_1 & -k_2 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -k_3 & \beta_2 f & \beta_2 \varepsilon_2 f \\ 0 & 0 & \gamma_2 & -k_4 & 0 \\ 0 & \tau_1 & 0 & \tau_2 & -k_5 \end{pmatrix} \quad (4.67)$$

Recall that the model (3.6) is defined on a positive invariant domain given by Ω in 4.2.1).

Also, by direct computation, the eigenvalues of $A_{11}(x)$ are $\{-(\mu + \rho), -(\mu + \alpha), -(\mu + m)\}$

which are real and negative. Therefore, conditions (1) and (2) of Theorem (4.2.5) are satisfied. For condition (3) of Theorem (4.2.5), we show that a square matrix $A_{22}(x_2)$ is irreducible if and only if its diagraph is strongly connected.

By applying the following theorem:

Theorem 4.2.6. *Let G be a di-graph and $A(G)$ be its adjacency matrix, then G is*

strongly connected if and only if

$$A(G) + A(G)^2 + \cdots + A(G)^{n-1}$$

has no zero entries

we can verify that $\{A_{22}(x_2) + A_{22}(x_2)^2 + A_{22}(x_2)^3 + A(G)^4\}$ has no zero entries which implies its strongly connected. Alternatively, we show through graph theory that, A square matrix is irreducible if and only if its associated digraph is strongly connected. Thus condition (3) is satisfied.

Furthermore, since $S = \frac{\Pi(\mu + \alpha)}{\mu(\mu + \alpha + \rho)}$, $V = \frac{\Pi\rho}{\mu(\mu + \alpha + \rho)}$, and $f = \frac{\rho\sigma + \mu + \alpha}{\mu + \alpha + \rho}$ then the matrix *

$$a_{22}(x) = \begin{pmatrix} -k_1 & \frac{\beta_1(\rho\sigma + \alpha + \mu)}{\alpha + \mu + \rho} & 0 & 0 & \frac{\beta_1\varepsilon_1(\rho\sigma + \alpha + \mu)}{\alpha + \mu + \rho} \\ \gamma_1 & -k_2 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -k_3 & \frac{\beta_2(\rho\sigma + \alpha + \mu)}{\alpha + \mu + \rho} & \frac{\beta_2\varepsilon_2(\rho\sigma + \alpha + \mu)}{\alpha + \mu + \rho} \\ 0 & 0 & \gamma_2 & -k_4 & 0 \\ 0 & \tau_1 & 0 & \tau_2 & -k_5 \end{pmatrix} \quad (4.68)$$

is an upper bound of $A_{22}(x)$. For condition (5) of Theorem 4.2.5, we present the condition for a Metzler matrix M to satisfy $\alpha(M) < 0$ using Lemma (4.2.2)

Lemma 4.2.2. *Let $M(x)$ be a Metzler matrix which is block decomposed as :*

$$M = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbb{A} & \mathbb{B} \\ \mathbb{C} & \mathbb{D} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (4.69)$$

where \mathbb{A} and \mathbb{D} are square matrices. Then, M is Metzler stable if and only if \mathbb{A} and $\mathbb{D} - \mathbb{C}^{-1}\mathbb{B}$ are Metzler stable.

In this case, $a_{22}(x)$ is decompose as:

$$\mathbb{A} = \begin{pmatrix} -k_1 & \frac{\beta_1(\rho\sigma+\alpha+\mu)}{\alpha+\mu+\rho} & 0 \\ \gamma_1 & -k_2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -k_3 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbb{B} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \frac{\beta_1\varepsilon_1(\rho\sigma+\alpha+\mu)}{\alpha+\mu+\rho} \\ 0 & 0 \\ \beta_2 f & \beta_2\varepsilon_2 f \end{pmatrix}, \quad (4.70)$$

$$\mathbb{C} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & \gamma_2 \\ 0 & \tau_1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbb{D} = \begin{pmatrix} -\kappa_4 & 0 \\ \tau_1 & -k_5 \end{pmatrix},$$

$$\mathbb{D} - \mathbb{C}\mathbb{A}^{-1}\mathbb{B} = \begin{bmatrix} -\kappa_4 + \frac{\beta_2\gamma_2(\rho\sigma+\alpha+\mu)}{\alpha+\mu+\rho} & \frac{\beta_2\varepsilon_2\gamma_2(\rho\sigma+\alpha+\mu)}{\alpha+\mu+\rho} \\ \tau_1 & -k_5 \left(1 - \frac{\beta_1\gamma_1(\rho\sigma+\alpha+\mu)\varepsilon_1\tau_1}{k_1k_2k_5(\alpha+\mu+\rho) - \beta_1\gamma_1(\rho\sigma+\alpha+\mu)k_5} \right) \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.71)$$

Therefore $\mathbb{D} - \mathbb{C}\mathbb{A}^{-1}\mathbb{B}$ is a Metzler matrix if

$$\frac{\beta_1\gamma_1(\rho\sigma+\alpha+\mu)\varepsilon_1\tau_1}{k_1k_2k_5(\alpha+\mu+\rho) - \beta_1\gamma_1(\rho\sigma+\alpha+\mu)k_5} < 1, \text{ and } \kappa_4 > \frac{\beta_2\gamma_2(\rho\sigma+\alpha+\mu)}{\alpha+\mu+\rho} \quad (4.72)$$

and it is stable if

$$\frac{k_1k_2k_5(\alpha+\mu+\rho)\mathcal{R}_{c1}[\beta_2\tau_2(\rho\sigma+\alpha+\mu) + k_3k_4(\alpha+\mu+\rho)] + (1 - \mathcal{R}_{c2})k_3k_4k_5(\alpha+\mu+\rho)}{k_3(\alpha+\mu+\rho)[\beta_1\gamma_1(\rho\sigma+\alpha+\mu) + k_1k_2(\alpha+\mu+\rho)]} > 0 \quad (4.73)$$

Which implies

$$k_1k_2k_5(\alpha+\mu+\rho)\mathcal{R}_{c1}[\beta_2\tau_2(\rho\sigma+\alpha+\mu) + k_3k_4(\alpha+\mu+\rho)] + (1 - \mathcal{R}_{c2})k_3k_4k_5(\alpha+\mu+\rho) > k_3(\alpha+\mu+\rho)[\beta_1\gamma_1(\rho\sigma+\alpha+\mu) + k_1k_2(\alpha+\mu+\rho)] \text{ and, } \mathcal{R}_{c2} < 1 \quad (4.74)$$

It should be noted that, condition (4.74) is a generalization of condition (4.72).

$$\text{Hence, } \mathcal{R}_c < \frac{\beta_1\gamma_1(\rho\sigma+\alpha+\mu)\varepsilon_1\tau_1}{k_1k_2k_5(\alpha+\mu+\rho) - \beta_1\gamma_1(\rho\sigma+\alpha+\mu)k_5} < 1, \text{ and } \kappa_4 > \frac{\beta_2\gamma_2(\rho\sigma+\alpha+\mu)}{\alpha+\mu+\rho} < 1 \quad (4.75)$$

Thus, satisfying condition (4.74) is sufficient for the GAS of the DFE. \square

4.2.4.1 Threshold Analysis and Vaccination Impact

In this subsection, the potential impact of a single dose and a fractional dosing of the vaccine is analyzed. Based on the facts that it is often impracticable to vaccinate all susceptible individuals due to many reasons (e.g financial constraints, age of the recipient, religious belief, etc.). It is therefore instructive to first of all assess the impact of vaccine on the spread of the disease. Let us recall that the effective reproduction number is computed in term of S and V as in equation (4.61), while in the worse case scenario as presented in equation (4.62), so that the impact of vaccination can be analyzed qualitatively by differentiating equation (4.61) with respect to the fraction of vaccinated individuals V . This is shown:

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{R}_{c1}}{\partial V} = \frac{-S(1-\sigma)\beta_1\gamma_1(\tau_1\varepsilon_1+k_5)}{k_1k_2k_5(S+V)^2}, \quad \frac{\partial \mathcal{R}_{c2}}{\partial V} = \frac{-S(1-\sigma)\beta_2\gamma_2(\tau_2\varepsilon_2+k_5)}{k_3k_4k_5(S+V)^2}, \quad (4.76)$$

Therefore, \mathcal{R}_c is a decreasing function of \mathcal{R}_0 . The implication of the foregoing result is that vaccination will have a positive impact in SARs-Cov-2 disease control, since \mathcal{R}_0 is a measure of the marginal incidence of the disease which cumulatively constitutes the disease burden in the population. As part of the national public health response to SARs-Cov-2, Nigeria began vaccine roll-out in March 2021, about a year after the country reported its index case. The objective is to achieve 40% vaccination of the total population in 2021 in-order to reduce the disease burden, but on the contrary the country could only achieve 11.5% complete dosage vaccination of her population in April 2022. (Oluwatosin *et al.*, 2022)

4.2.5 Quasi-Disease

In the context of SARs-CoV-2 disease dynamics, there is no medical documentation supporting the co-infection of individuals in a population with multiple strains of the disease. Given this notable observation, we introduce the term "quasi-disease" (QD). This term refers to a state where infected individual either have the (Eta) strain of SARs-CoV-2) or the newly emerged (Delta) variants of SARs-CoV-2.

$$\left. \begin{aligned}
 \dot{S} &= \Pi + mR - \lambda_2 S + \alpha V - (\rho + \mu)S \\
 \dot{V} &= \rho S - \sigma \lambda_2 V - (\alpha + \mu)V \\
 \dot{E}_2 &= (S + \sigma V)\lambda_2 - (\gamma_2 + \mu)E_2 \\
 \dot{I}_2 &= \gamma_2 E_2 - (\tau_2 + \delta_2 + \psi_2 + \mu)I_2 \\
 \dot{H} &= \tau_2 I_2 - (\psi_3 + \mu + \delta_{21})H \\
 \dot{R} &= \psi_2 I_2 + \psi_3 H - (m + \mu)R
 \end{aligned} \right\} \text{Delta variant only} \quad (4.77)$$

$$S(0) > 0, V(0) \geq 0, E_2(0) \geq 0, E_2(0) \geq 0, H(0) \geq 0, R(0) \geq 0, \text{ and } \lambda_2 = \frac{\beta_2(I_2 + \varepsilon_2 H)}{N}$$

The model derived in the system of equations 4.77 considers a scenario where individuals in the population are exclusively infected with the Delta variant of SARs-CoV-2. This implies that these individuals do not come into contact with those exposed or infected with the original strain of the disease. Mathematically, this scenario is expressed as follows: when $E_2 > 0$ and $I_2 > 0$, then the original strain ($E_1 = I_1 = 0$);

4.2.5.1 Quasi Disease Endemic Equilibria (QDEE)

To compute the equilibria and local stability conditions. We calculate the first QDFE to be:

$$\begin{aligned}
 S &= \frac{\gamma_2 m \sigma^2 \beta_2^2 \lambda_2^2 (k_2 \psi_2 + \tau_2 \psi_3) + k_1 k_2 (\mu + \gamma_2) (m + \mu) [\beta_2 (\alpha \sigma - \alpha - \mu) - \Pi (\alpha + \mu)]}{\gamma_2 m \beta_2 \lambda_2 (k_2 \psi_2 + \tau_2 \psi_3) T_1 - \mu k_1 k_2 (\mu + m) (\mu + \gamma_2) (\alpha + \mu + \rho)}, \\
 V &= \frac{+k_1 k_2 (\mu + \gamma_2) (m + \mu) [\mu \sigma + \rho \sigma - \rho - \Pi \rho] - \gamma_2 m \sigma \beta_2^2 \lambda_2^2 (k_2 \psi_2 + \tau_2 \psi_3)}{\gamma_2 m \beta_2 \lambda_2 (k_2 \psi_2 + \tau_2 \psi_3) T_1 - \mu k_1 k_2 (\mu + m) (\mu + \gamma_2) (\alpha + \mu + \rho)}, \\
 E_2 &= \frac{\beta_2 [(\mu \sigma + T_1) (\sigma - 1) \lambda_2 - \Pi T_1] (\mu + m) \beta_2 \lambda_2 k_2 k_1}{m \beta_2 \gamma_2 (k_2 \psi_2 + \psi_3 \tau_2) T_1 \lambda_2 - k_1 k_2 \mu (\mu + \gamma_2) (m + \mu) (\rho + \alpha + \mu)}, \\
 H_2 &= \frac{\beta_2 [(\mu \sigma + T_1) (\sigma - 1) \lambda_2 - \Pi T_1] (\mu + m) \beta_2 \lambda_2 \tau_2 \gamma_2}{m \beta_2 \gamma_2 (k_2 \psi_2 + \psi_3 \tau_2) T_1 \lambda_2 - k_1 k_2 \mu (\mu + \gamma_2) (m + \mu) (\rho + \alpha + \mu)}, \\
 I_2 &= \frac{\beta_2 [(\mu \sigma + T_1) (\sigma - 1) \lambda_2 - \Pi T_1] (\mu + m) \beta_2 \lambda_2 k_2 \gamma_2}{m \beta_2 \gamma_2 (k_2 \psi_2 + \psi_3 \tau_2) T_1 \lambda_2 - k_1 k_2 \mu (\mu + \gamma_2) (m + \mu) (\rho + \alpha + \mu)}, \\
 R_2 &= \frac{\beta_2 [(\mu \sigma + T_1) (\sigma - 1) \lambda_2 - \Pi T_1] (\mu + m) \beta_2 \lambda_2 \gamma_2}{m \beta_2 \gamma_2 (k_2 \psi_2 + \psi_3 \tau_2) T_1 \lambda_2 - k_1 k_2 \mu (\mu + \gamma_2) (m + \mu) (\rho + \alpha + \mu)},
 \end{aligned} \tag{4.78}$$

$$\text{Where } T_1 = (\rho \sigma + \alpha + \mu)$$

Substituting equation (4.78) into force of infection equation (4.77) to obtain an expression for λ_2^{**} as:

$$\lambda_2^{**}(\zeta) = a_2 \zeta^2 + a_1 \zeta + a_0 = 0, \tag{4.79}$$

Solving the quadratic equation (4.79) to obtain its coefficient, we have:

$$\begin{aligned}
a_2 &= k_5 \sigma \gamma_2 (\rho \sigma + \alpha + \psi_2) + \sigma k_4 k_5 (m + \mu) + \sigma \gamma_2 \tau_2 (m + \mu + \psi_3), \\
a_1 &= \gamma_2 (\rho \sigma + \alpha + \mu) [k_5 (m + \mu + \psi_2) + \tau_2 (m + \mu + \psi_3)] + k_4 k_5 (\rho \sigma + \sigma k_3 + \alpha) (m + \mu) \\
&\quad - \beta_2 \gamma_2 (m + \mu) \sigma (\epsilon_2 \tau_2 + k_5), \\
a_0 &= k_3 k_4 k_5 (m + \mu) (\mu + \alpha + \rho) (1 - \mathcal{R}_{c2}).
\end{aligned} \tag{4.80}$$

It follows from equation (4.80) that the coefficient a_2 remains positive, while a_0 becomes negative whenever $\mathcal{R}_{c2} > 1$. Therefore, Theorem 4.2.7 outlines the criteria under which an endemic equilibrium exists for the SARS-CoV-2 model presented in equation (4.77).

Theorem 4.2.7. *The SARs-Cov-2 model (4.77) has:*

1. *no endemic equilibrium otherwise, if all the coefficient $\{a_2, a_1, a_0\}$ of equation (4.80) are all positive*
2. *a unique endemic equilibrium exists if $a_1 < 0$, and $a_0 = 0$ or $a_1^2 - 4a_0a_2 = 0$*
3. *two endemic equilibria if $a_0 > 0$, $a_1 < 0$ and $a_1^2 - 4a_0a_2 > 0$*
4. *a unique endemic equilibrium if $a_0 < 0 \Leftrightarrow \mathcal{R}_{c2} > 1$*

In a similar pattern, to compute for the second strain of SARs-Cov-2 by substituting equation (4.78) into equation (3.7) to obtain an expression for λ_1^{**} as stated below:

$$\lambda_1^{**}(\zeta_1) = a_{21}(\zeta_1)^2 + a_{11}(\zeta_1)^{**} + a_{01} = 0 \tag{4.81}$$

Where the coefficient of equation 4.81 are obtained as:

$$\begin{aligned}
a_{22} &= k_5 \sigma \gamma_1 (\rho \sigma + \alpha + \psi_1) + \sigma k_2 k_5 (m + \mu) + \sigma \gamma_1 \tau_1 (m + \mu + \psi_2), \\
a_{21} &= \gamma_1 (\rho \sigma + \alpha + \mu) [k_5 (m + \mu + \psi_1) + \tau_1 (m + \mu + \psi_2)] + k_2 k_5 (\rho \sigma + \sigma k_1 + \alpha) (m + \mu) \\
&\quad - \beta_1 \gamma_1 (m + \mu) \sigma (\epsilon_1 \tau_1 + k_5), \\
a_{20} &= k_1 k_2 k_5 (m + \mu) (\mu + \alpha + \rho) (1 - \mathcal{R}_{c1}).
\end{aligned} \tag{4.82}$$

Theorem 4.2.7, specifically case (2), demonstrates that the model system (3.6) possesses a single endemic equilibrium when $\mathcal{R}_{c1} > 1$. In contrast, case (3) reveals the potential for multiple endemic equilibria, suggesting the occurrence of a backward bifurcation. This phenomenon implies that a locally asymptotically stable disease-free equilibrium can coexist with a stable endemic state even when $\mathcal{R}_{c1} < 1$. To analyze this bifurcation behavior, the discriminant of equation (4.80) is set to zero.

$$\begin{aligned}
\Delta &= a_{12}^2 - 4a_{11}k_1k_2k_5(m + \mu)(\mu + \alpha + \rho)(1 - \mathcal{R}_{c1}) = 0 \\
\mathcal{R}_{c1}^* &= 1 - \frac{a_{12}^2}{4a_{11}k_1k_2k_5(m + \mu)(\mu + \alpha + \rho)}
\end{aligned} \tag{4.83}$$

Therefore, equation (4.83) gives the analytical expression of a threshold value for the effective reproduction number, and bifurcation would occur for values of $\mathcal{R}_{c1}^* < \mathcal{R}_{c1} < 1$.

4.2.5.2 Bifurcation Analysis

In this section, the aim is to achieve the condition at which SARs-Cov-2 will become endemic in the population considering the Nigerian lackadaisical attitude toward the vaccine acceptance and adherence to preventive measure initiated by the Nigerian government through an in-depth exploration of bifurcation analysis. Thus, the phenomenon of backward bifurcation is marked by the simultaneous existence of two equilibria, with one being stable and the other unstable. This occurs in some epidemiological models

when the basic reproduction number \mathcal{R}_0 is below 1, the stable equilibrium corresponds to the disease-free equilibrium (DFE), while the unstable equilibrium represents an endemic equilibrium as depicted in Figure 4.19. Several factors contribute to the manifestation of backward bifurcation, including exogenous reinfection, super-infection, relapse, vaccination initiatives, and heterogeneity among sub-populations (Song & Lou, 2013). At its core, \mathcal{R}_0 serves as a pivotal threshold, playing a crucial role in determining the potential for a disease to establish itself. When the basic reproduction number surpasses one, the disease can successfully permeate a population, whereas if it falls below one, the disease fades away (Song & Lou, 2013).

Figure 4.19: Backward Bifurcation for model 4.77 at $\beta = 50$

We illustrate the relationship between the equilibrium prevalence and the control reproduction number \mathcal{R}_{C2} , highlighting a backward bifurcation at 0.6124. The parameter values employed in generating these plots are provided in Table 4.2. As shown in Figure 4.19, the model reveals the existence of two equilibria—a disease-free equilibrium

(DFE) and an endemic equilibrium—even when \mathcal{R}_{C2} is less than one. This indicates that the Delta variant of SARS-CoV-2 could continue circulating in the population despite \mathcal{R}_0 being below one. However, when \mathcal{R}_0 falls below 0.6124, the disease is predicted to eventually fade out. Notably, this outcome persists even when the baseline transmission rate ($\beta = 50$) is increased to capture enhanced transmission due to factors such as poor adherence to vaccination and preventive measures. This aligns with the derived value of parameter α (from equation (4.89)) and findings from other studies (Song & Lou, 2013; Idisi. *et al.*, 2023), which underscore the role of vaccination dynamics in potentially fostering the emergence of new variants.

Figure 4.20: Forward Bifurcation for model (4.77) at $\beta = 4$

Figure 4.20 illustrates the occurrence of a forward bifurcation at $\mathcal{R}_0 < 1$, indicating the potential disappearance of a backward bifurcation in the system. When considering model equation (4.77) under the assumption of perfect vaccine efficacy and a significantly reduced transmission rate for SARS-CoV-2 (for example, $\beta = 4$), the coefficients

in equation (4.79) simplify to $a_2 = 0$, $a_1 > 0$, and $a_0 \geq 0$ whenever $\mathcal{R}_{c2} \leq 1$. Under these conditions, equation (4.79) yields a single solution, $\lambda^{**} = \frac{-a_1}{a_0}$, which means that no positive endemic equilibrium exists when $\mathcal{R}_{c2} \leq 1$. Consequently, the possibility of a backward bifurcation is removed.

This implies that when $\mathcal{R}_0 > 1$, the SARS-CoV-2 infection can establish itself in the population, leading to an endemic state. This scenario is depicted in Figure 4.20, which shows that the disease will persist despite the presence of a stable endemic equilibrium (EE). Conversely, when $\mathcal{R}_0 < 1$, the infection cannot spread throughout the population, in line with previous findings (Song & Lou, 2013).

In a similar pattern, referring to the definition of Quasi Disease, we consider the second strain 1 (Naive strain) in the population and obtain the bifurcation considering that strain 2 (eta strain) is not in the population as depicted in Figure 4.21 and 4.22, while the bifurcation threshold is derived as follows:

Theorem 4.2.8. *Let*

$$\begin{aligned} \Gamma = & w_2 w_4 (1 - \sigma) \mu b + w_2 w_5 (1 - \sigma) \varepsilon_2 \mu b + w_3 w_4 \bar{f} + w_3 w_5 \mu \varepsilon_2 \bar{f} + 2 w_4 w_4 \mu \bar{f} \\ & + w_4 w_5 (1 + \varepsilon_2) \mu \bar{f} + w_4 w_6 \mu \bar{f} + w_5 w_6 \varepsilon_2 \mu \bar{f} + w_6 w_6 \mu \varepsilon_2 \bar{f} \end{aligned} \quad (4.84)$$

the model (3.6) undergoes backward bifurcation at

$\mathcal{R}_{c2} = 1$, *if* $w_1 (1 - \sigma) \mu \rho (w_4 + \varepsilon_2) a > \Gamma$ *and forward bifurcation if* $\Gamma > w_1 (1 - \sigma) \mu \rho (w_4 + \varepsilon_2) a$

Proof:

Suppose $\mathcal{E}_1 = (S^{**}, V^{**}, E_2^{**}, I_2^{**}, H^{**}, R^{**})$ represents any arbitrary endemic equilibrium of the model (4.77) (that is, an equilibrium in which at least one of the infected components is nonzero). Applying the Center Manifold theory (Castillo-Chavez &

Song, 2004), the existence of bifurcation will be studied. By simplification and change of variables of model 4.77. The Jacobian $J^*(E_0)$ of the linearized model (4.77) with $\beta_2 = \beta_2^*$ has a simple zero eigenvalue (with all other eigenvalues having negative real part). Hence, applying the approach in (Castillo-Chavez & Song, 2004) to analyze the dynamics of model (4.77), the right eigenvector (w) and left eigenvector (v) associated with the zero eigenvalues of $J^*(E_0)|_{\beta=\beta^*}$ are computed and given as:

$$w_1 = -\frac{\beta_2^*(m+\mu)(\tau_2\varepsilon_2+k_5)(a_3\alpha+a_3\mu+b_3\alpha)-m(k_5\Psi_2+\tau_2\Psi_3)(\alpha+\mu)}{\tau_2\mu(\mu+\rho+\alpha)(m+\mu)},$$

$$w_2 = -\frac{\beta_2^*(m+\mu)(\tau_2\varepsilon_2+k_5)(a_3\rho+b_3\mu+a_3\rho)-m\rho(k_5\Psi_2+\tau_2\Psi_3)}{\tau_2\mu(\mu+\rho+\alpha)(m+\mu)}, \quad (4.85)$$

$$w_3 = \frac{k_4k_4w_5}{\gamma_2\tau_2}, \quad w_4 = \frac{k_5w_5}{\tau_2}, \quad w_6 = \frac{k_5\Psi_2+\tau_2\Psi_3}{\tau_2(m+\mu)}w_5, \quad w_5 = w_5 > 0$$

and

$$v_1 = 0, v_2 = 0, v_6 = 0, v_3 = \frac{k_4v_5}{f\beta_2^*\varepsilon_2}, v_4 = \frac{k_3k_4v_5}{f\beta_2^*\gamma_2\varepsilon_2}, v_5 = v_5 > 0 \quad (4.86)$$

The bifurcation coefficient a at the DFE is given as:

$$a = \sum_{k,i=1}^6 v_k w_i w_j \frac{\partial^2 f_k}{\partial x_i \partial x_j}(E_0, \beta^*) \quad (4.87)$$

Since, $v_1 = 0, v_2 = 0, v_6 = 0$, we calculate the following associate non zero second partial derivatives of model (4.36) evaluated at (E_0, β^*) to show the existence of bifurcation and obtain:

$$\frac{\partial^2 f_3}{\partial x_1 \partial x_4} = \frac{\partial^2 f_3}{\partial x_4 \partial x_1} = \frac{(1-\sigma)\beta_2^* \rho \mu}{\Pi(\mu + \alpha + \rho)}, \quad \frac{\partial^2 f_3}{\partial x_1 \partial x_5} = \frac{\partial^2 f_3}{\partial x_5 \partial x_1} = \frac{(1-\sigma)\beta_2^* \varepsilon_2 \rho \mu}{\Pi(\mu + \alpha + \rho)},$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 f_3}{\partial x_2 \partial x_4} = \frac{\partial^2 f_3}{\partial x_4 \partial x_2} = -\frac{(1-\sigma)(\alpha + \mu)\beta_2^* \mu}{\Pi(\mu + \alpha + \rho)}, \quad \frac{\partial^2 f_3}{\partial x_2 \partial x_5} = \frac{\partial^2 f_3}{\partial x_5 \partial x_2} = -\frac{(1-\sigma)(\alpha + \mu)\mu\beta_2^* \varepsilon_2}{\Pi(\mu + \alpha + \rho)}$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 f_3}{\partial x_3 \partial x_4} = \frac{\partial^2 f_3}{\partial x_4 \partial x_3} = -\frac{\beta_2^* \mu(\rho\sigma + \alpha + \mu)}{\Pi(\mu + \alpha + \rho)}, \quad \frac{\partial^2 f_3}{\partial x_3 \partial x_5} = \frac{\partial^2 f_3}{\partial x_5 \partial x_3} = -\frac{\beta_2^* \mu \varepsilon_2(\rho\sigma + \alpha + \mu)}{\Pi(\mu + \alpha + \rho)}$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 f_3}{\partial x_4 \partial x_4} = -\frac{2\beta_2^* \mu(\rho\sigma + \alpha + \mu)}{\Pi(\mu + \alpha + \rho)}, \quad \frac{\partial^2 f_3}{\partial x_4 \partial x_5} = \frac{\partial^2 f_3}{\partial x_5 \partial x_4} = -\frac{(1 + \varepsilon_2)\beta_2^* \mu(\rho\sigma + \alpha + \mu)}{\Pi(\mu + \alpha + \rho)}$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 f_3}{\partial x_4 \partial x_6} = \frac{\partial^2 f_3}{\partial x_6 \partial x_4} = -\frac{\beta_2^* \mu(\rho\sigma + \alpha + \mu)}{\Pi(\mu + \alpha + \rho)}, \quad \frac{\partial^2 f_3}{\partial x_5 \partial x_5} = -\frac{(1 + \varepsilon_2)\beta_2^* \mu(\rho\sigma + \alpha + \mu)}{\Pi(\mu + \alpha + \rho)}$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 f_3}{\partial x_5 \partial x_6} = \frac{\partial^2 f_3}{\partial x_6 \partial x_5} = -\frac{\varepsilon_2 \beta_2^* \mu(\rho\sigma + \alpha + \mu)}{\Pi(\mu + \alpha + \rho)}, \quad \frac{\partial^2 f_3}{\partial x_6 \partial x_6} = -\frac{\varepsilon_2 \beta_2^* \mu(\rho\sigma + \alpha + \mu)}{\Pi(\mu + \alpha + \rho)}$$

So now, we calculate the coefficient of \bar{a} using Theorem 4.1 in ? as follow:

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{a} = & \frac{v_3 \beta_2^*}{\Pi} [w_1(1-\sigma)\mu\rho(w_4 + \varepsilon_2)a - (w_2 w_4(1-\sigma)\mu b + w_2 w_5(1-\sigma)\varepsilon_2 \mu b + w_3 w_4 \bar{c} + w_3 w_5 \mu \varepsilon_2 \bar{f} \\ & + 2w_4 w_4 \mu \bar{c} + w_4 w_5(1 + \varepsilon_2)\mu \bar{f} + w_4 w_6 \mu \bar{f} + w_5 w_6 \varepsilon_2 \mu \bar{f} + w_6 w_6 \mu \varepsilon_2 \bar{f}] \end{aligned} \quad (4.88)$$

thus ,

$$\bar{a} = \frac{v_3 \beta_2^*}{\Pi} [w_1(1-\sigma)\mu\rho(w_4 + \varepsilon_2)a - \Gamma] \quad (4.89)$$

Where

$$\begin{aligned} \Gamma = & w_2 w_4(1-\sigma)\mu b + w_2 w_5(1-\sigma)\varepsilon_2 \mu b + w_3 w_4 \bar{c} + w_3 w_5 \mu \varepsilon_2 \bar{f} + 2w_4 w_4 \mu \bar{c} \\ & + w_4 w_5(1 + \varepsilon_2)\mu \bar{f} + w_4 w_6 \mu \bar{f} + w_5 w_6 \varepsilon_2 \mu \bar{f} + w_6 w_6 \mu \varepsilon_2 \bar{f} \end{aligned} \quad (4.90)$$

However, from equation (4.89), $a > 0$ when $w_1(1-\sigma)\mu\rho(w_4 + \varepsilon_2)a > \Gamma$ and $a < 0$ when

$w_1(1 - \sigma)\mu\rho(w_4 + \varepsilon_2)a < \Gamma$ or $\sigma = 1$ The second bifurcation coefficient b is given by:

$$b = \sum_{k,i=1}^7 v_k w_i \frac{\partial^2 f_k}{\partial x_i \partial \beta}(E_0, 0) \quad (4.91)$$

For b , similarly we compute the partial derivatives of model (4.36) evaluated at $(E_0, 0)$

as:

$$\frac{\partial^2 f_3}{\partial x_4 \partial \beta} = \frac{\rho\sigma + \alpha + \mu}{\alpha + \mu + \rho} = \bar{f}, \quad \frac{\partial^2 f_3}{\partial x_5 \partial \beta} = \frac{\varepsilon_2(\rho\sigma + \alpha + \mu)}{\alpha + \mu + \rho} = \varepsilon \bar{f}. \quad (4.92)$$

It follows that

$$b = v_3 w_4 \frac{\partial^2 f_3}{\partial x_4 \partial \beta_2^*} + v_3 w_5 \frac{\partial^2 f_3}{\partial x_5 \partial \beta_2^*}, \quad (4.93)$$

$$b = \frac{k_5}{\varepsilon_2 \beta_2^*} \left[\frac{k_5}{\tau_2} + \frac{\varepsilon_2}{k_5} \right] > 0.$$

The sign of a in equation (4.89) determines the direction of the bifurcation. From the above calculation the sign of a is uncertain and that of b is always positive. However, it is found that coefficient of a is positive if $w_1(1 - \sigma)\mu\rho(w_4 + \varepsilon_2)a > \Gamma$, and negative if $w_1(1 - \sigma)\mu\rho(w_4 + \varepsilon_2)a < \Gamma$. Therefore model (4.36) will undergoes either backward or forward bifurcation at $\mathcal{R}_0 = 1$. Thus the proof is complete \square .

Figure 4.21: The occurrence of backward bifurcation at $\mathcal{R}_{c1} = 0.8386$ for model (4.36) using at $\beta = 65$

In Figure 4.21 and 4.22: Simulation of the equilibrium prevalence of SARS-Cov-2 Naive Strain as a function of \mathcal{R}_{c1} is done in order to access the occurrence of bifurcation in model (3.6). The impact of Strain 1 effective infection rate as shown in Figure 4.21 reveals that increasing the baseline value of $\beta_2 = 65$ causes a backward bifurcation to occur at $\mathcal{R}_{c1} = 0.8386$. By implication, SARS-Cov-2 Strain Naive strain will remain endemic in the population at $\mathcal{R}_{c1} > 0.8386$, this uncover the notion and propel insight in understanding the epidemiology of SARS-Cov-2 in the population, in-that the naive variant will remain endemic at $\mathcal{R}_{c1} < 1$.

Figure 4.22: The occurrence of forward bifurcation at $\mathcal{R}_{c1} > 1$ for model (4.36) using at $\beta = 4$

However, Figure 4.22, depicts the occurrence of forward bifurcation showing that at the effective infection rate ($\beta = 4$) SARs-Cov-2 will can be eliminated at $\mathcal{R}_{c1} < 1$. A comprehensive understanding of the persistence of equilibria across multiple strains of SARs-Cov-2 provides valuable insights for designing more effective strategies to combat this infectious disease. This broader perspective surpasses the insights gained solely from analyzing a single strain, as illustrated in Figures (4.21 and 4.22). By examining the interplay of backward bifurcation for both strains, as depicted in Figure (4.23), we can better grasp the complexity involved. This approach aims to anticipate the limitations of relying solely on the classical basic reproduction number (\mathcal{R}_{c1}) being less than unity as a sufficient condition for eradicating SARs-Cov-2 disease. Instead, it emphasizes the necessity of considering additional factors and dynamics to effectively combat the disease.

Figure 4.23: persistence equilibria prevalence for both SARs-Cov-2 multiple strains

Equation (4.61) clearly shows that the peak value of the basic reproduction number plays a vital role in the dynamics of both circulating strains. However, our analysis, as illustrated in Figure 4.23, highlights the importance of reducing the effective reproduction number to limit the potential complications that arise from backward bifurcation. In simpler terms, examining the scenario of a quasi-disease, we find that the naive strain 1 of SARS-CoV-2 persists even when the basic reproduction number is $\mathcal{R}_{c1} = 0.834$. This suggests that complete elimination of the disease cannot be achieved simply by maintaining $\mathcal{R}_{c1} < 1$. A similar situation is observed with the emerging strain 2, which also presents challenges for disease eradication in the population.

Further analysis shows that the backward bifurcation in Model equation (3.6) is influenced by waning immunity among vaccinated individuals. This has practical implications for managing and controlling both strains of SARS-CoV-2. A key priority for public health authorities, particularly in Nigeria, will be to ensure that the effective re-

production number is reduced below 0.5 to prevent the disease from becoming endemic. Achieving this requires the deployment of highly effective vaccines and strict enforcement of vaccination protocols, represented by parameters β and σ , which are key drivers of backward bifurcation in the population.

4.2.6 Parameter Estimation and Model Fitting

The dual-strain epidemiological model (3.6) developed for SARS-CoV-2 transmission in Nigeria was validated and tested for reliability using real-world data from the Nigeria Centre for Disease Control (NCDC) and the World Health Organization (WHO) (NCDC, 2020; Worldometer, 2024). To achieve this, a nonlinear least-squares curve-fitting method was applied to estimate key unknown parameters. Reported confirmed cases in Nigeria (which represent the number of infectious individuals) were used to fit the model. The fitting process was carried out in MATLAB using the "lsqcurvefit" algorithm, aiming to minimize the sum of squared differences between the model predictions and data points from (Worldometer, 2024), iterated 1000 times per parameter estimate. The Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) was calculated to measure the fit's accuracy, resulting in a value of 189.58. Details of both estimated and known parameter values are summarized in Table 4.2, with the corresponding model fits shown in Figures 4.26 and 4.24.

The model incorporates 20 biological parameters. Several parameters (such as $\Pi, \psi_1, \psi_2, \psi_3, \gamma_1, \gamma_2$) were obtained from existing literature, while the remaining unknown parameters ($\alpha, m, \delta_1, \delta_2, \delta_{12}, \delta_{21}, \rho, \phi, \epsilon_1, \epsilon_2, \eta, \beta_1, \sigma, \tau, \mu$) are listed in Table 4.2. Based on the available data, the initial conditions for the model variables were set as follows: $S(0) = 211,400,691, V(0) = 1, E_1(0) = 11, E_2(0) = 5, I_1(0) = 0, I_2(0) = 2, H(0) =$, and $R(0) = 0$. Additionally, the fitted curves and residuals are displayed in

Figures (4.24, 4.25, 4.26, and 4.27).

Figure 4.24: Daily SARS-Cov-2 cumulative cases time series in Nigeria

Figure 4.25: Residuals for the best fitted curve

Figure 4.26: Daily SARs-Cov-2 cumulative cases time series in Nigeria

Figure 4.27: Residuals for the best fitted curve

Additionally, we utilized the residual function from MATLAB's Optimization Toolbox

to generate the residual plots shown in Figures (4.25 and 4.27). These plots demonstrate that the residuals are distributed fairly evenly above and below the horizontal line, indicating that the formulated dual strain model (3.6) fits the data well.

Table 4.2: **Baseline values of the paramaters used in Model (3.6)**

Parameters	Values (Range)	unit	Reference (Source)
Π	13942	day^{-1}	Idisi. <i>et al.</i> (2023)
$\gamma_{(1,2)}$	$7.15e - 02$	day^{-1}	Iboi <i>et al.</i> (2020)
ψ_1	$1.429e - 01$	day^{-1}	Iboi <i>et al.</i> (2020)
ψ_2	$1.429e - 01$	day^{-1}	Iboi <i>et al.</i> (2020)
ψ_3	$7.14e - 02$	day^{-1}	Enahoro <i>et al.</i> (2020)
θ	$5.000e - 01$	day^{-1}	Enahoro <i>et al.</i> (2020)
Fitted Parameter			
m	$2.726e - 01$	day^{-1}	Assume
α	$9.973e - 01$	day^{-1}	Assume
ρ	$1.083e - 01$	day^{-1}	Enahoro <i>et al.</i> (2020)
δ_1	$2.843e - 01$	day^{-1}	Fitted
δ_2	$3.310e - 01$ (1 – 0.001)	day^{-1}	Fitted
δ_{12}	$4.131e - 01$	day^{-1}	Assume
δ_{21}	$4.131e - 01$	day^{-1}	Assume
τ_1	$2.954e - 01$ (3 – 0.0343)	day^{-1}	Fitted
τ_2	$9.6e - 03$ (3 – 0.0343)	day^{-1}	Fitted
σ_1	$4.685e - 01$ (5 – 0.0529)	day^{-1}	Fitted
β_1	4.6935 (5 – 0.00529)	day^{-1}	Fitted
β_2	4.1196 (5 – 0.00529)	day^{-1}	Fitted
ε_1	$4.750e - 01$	day^{-1}	Assume
ε_2	$3.715e - 01$	day^{-1}	Assume
μ	$5.085e - 01$	day^{-1}	NCDC (2020)

4.2.6.1 Global Sensitivity Analysis, contour and scatter plots

Understanding the influence of different risk factors on the spread of infectious diseases is essential for effective control measures. In this section, we conducted a global sensitivity analysis on the proposed dual-strain model (Equation 3.6) using Latin Hypercube Sampling (LHS) combined with the partial rank correlation coefficient (PRCC) to assess how parameter variations affect model outcomes. LHS efficiently samples parameter space, while PRCC measures the strength of relationships between each parameter and the model's output. Assuming uniform distributions for all parameters, we

performed 1000 simulations per LHS iteration using values from Table 4.2. The analysis focused on the basic reproduction number (\mathcal{R}_c) for each strain of SARS-CoV-2 (naive and emerging). Results identified key parameters affecting the spread of the Delta variant, including the transmission rate (β_2), the progression rate of exposed individuals (γ_2), immunity waning rate (α), and the contact rate of hospitalized individuals (ϵ_1) (see Fig. 4.28). These insights are critical for developing effective interventions to control the SARS-CoV-2 outbreak in Nigeria.

Figure 4.28: The Sensitivity plot of the emerging strain (Delta) using the \mathcal{R}_{c2} as a function

The results from the sensitivity analysis emphasize that early detection through testing and increased vaccination coverage are crucial for reducing the risk of SARS-CoV-2 transmission among people. Expanding these measures would lower the disease's mortality rate (μ) and help control its spread in the population. Figures 4.29 and 4.30 illustrate how each parameter influences the effective reproduction number (\mathcal{R}_{c2}). Sensitivity

plots, widely utilized in statistics and research, allow us to examine the connections between variables, spot patterns and outliers, and assess the nature and strength of these relationships whether they are positive, negative, or neutral.

Figure 4.29: The Sensitivity plot of the emerging strain (Delta) using the \mathcal{R}_{c2} as a function

Figure 4.30: The Sensitivity plot of the emerging strain (Delta) using the \mathcal{R}_{c2} as a function

The sensitivity plots shown in Figures 4.29 and 4.30 display the relationship between various parameters and the response function, \mathcal{R}_{c2} . On the x-axis, parameters such as $(\alpha, \delta_2, \delta_{21}, \rho, \psi_2, \epsilon_2, \psi_3, \beta_2, \sigma, \tau, \mu)$ are plotted against \mathcal{R}_{c2} on the y-axis. From these figures, it is clear that β_1 has a strong, positive, and linear effect on the model described by system of equation 3.6, indicating that increases in the infection rate significantly amplify the spread of SARS-CoV-2. This highlights the importance of the infection force in driving the pandemic's severity and provides valuable insights into how parameter changes influence disease transmission.

Similarly, the parameter γ (Transmission rate of exposed individual to the infected compartment) also shows a positive linear trend within a certain time frame, reflecting the increase in exposed individuals during the early phase of the outbreak. In contrast, parameters like δ_1 and μ demonstrate a monotonic decreasing effect, showing a sup-

pressive influence on disease spread. Additionally, parameters such as σ (rate at which vaccinated individual became infected), τ_1 (rate at which infected individual became hospitalized), ϵ_1 (modification parameter for effective contact rate for Hospitalized individuals), and ψ_3 (Vaccination rate) exhibit more complex interactions, as their values are scattered more widely along the effective reproduction number, suggesting they influence the model outcomes in a less straightforward manner.

Figure 4.31: The Sensitivity plot of the Native strain using the \mathcal{R}_{c1} as a function

In the scenario of "quasi-disease" (QD), where infected individuals exclusively harbor the native strain of SARS-CoV-2, the PRCC Plot for the native strain (1) was generated and depicted in Figure 4.31. This plot illustrates the relationship between the effective reproduction number (\mathcal{R}_{c1}) and the values of model parameters outlined in Table 4.2. The sensitivity analysis conducted revealed several parameters that significantly influence the spread of the SARS-CoV-2 native strain. Prominent among these parameters is the transmission rate (β_1), identified as the most sensitive parameter, exerting a profound

impact on the increase or decrease of the effective reproduction number (\mathcal{R}_{e1}). Additionally, parameters such as the progression rate of exposed individuals to the infected class (γ_1), the immunity waning rate of recovered individuals from the native strain (α), and the effective contact rate for hospitalized individuals (ϵ_1) exhibited noteworthy positive sensitivity indices. In contrast, parameters such as μ , ψ_1 , ρ , and δ_1 displayed negative sensitivity indices, indicating their adverse influence on the spread of the SARS-CoV-2 native strain. Notably, the vaccination rate (ρ) emerged as the second-largest negative index, highlighting its potential impact in mitigating the spread of the disease. A comparison with the sensitivity plot in Figure 4.28 reveals a higher transmission index for the emerging strain (Delta variant) of SARS-CoV-2, as indicated by the sensitivity index for $\beta_2 = 0.7$. This underscores the critical importance of identifying these key parameters in formulating effective control strategies to mitigate the spread of SARS-CoV-2 within Nigeria. Understanding the sensitivity of these parameters is pivotal for devising targeted interventions and efficiently allocating resources to combat the transmission of the disease. By prioritizing interventions that address the most influential parameters identified through sensitivity analysis, it becomes feasible to implement strategies aimed at mitigating specific factors driving the spread of SARS-CoV-2, thereby contributing to the containment and management of the epidemic in Nigeria.

Figure 4.32: The Sensitivity plot of the native strain with parameter presented in Table 4.2 using (\mathcal{R}_{c1}) as a response function

Figure 4.33: The Sensitivity plot of the native strain with parameter presented in Table 4.2 using (\mathcal{R}_{c1}) as a response function

4.2.7 Numerical Simulation and Discussions for Dual Strain COVID-19 Model

To illustrate the fundamental mechanisms driving the dynamics of our model 3.6, we present various graphical representations showcasing the system's behavior under different scenarios where the fundamental threshold parameter exceeds or falls below unity. These graphical depictions serve to reinforce the analytical findings. The parameter values utilized in our simulations are detailed in Table 4.2, with Λ denote the recruitment rate of person into the population per day, while all other parameters are measured per day. We establish the initial conditions as Nigeria population is denoted by $N = 218541216$ which follows: $S(0) = N * 0.91$, $V(0) = N * 0.02$;; $E_1(0) = N * 0.027$, $E_2(0) = N * 0.027$;; $I_1(0) = N * 0.0008$, $I_2(0) = N * 0.00036$;; $H(0) = N * 0.00007$, $R(0) = N * 0.001$. Given that $\mathcal{R}_c = \max(\mathcal{R}_{c1}, \mathcal{R}_{c2})$, four distinct scenarios is adopted to comprehensively analyze the dynamics of the formulated model:

- i Investigating the effect of vaccine waning on the prevalence of SARs-CoV-2 in the population.
- ii Examining distinct implications for each quasi-disease state of SARs-CoV-2 in the population.
- iii Assessing the impact of each strain's transmission rate on the prevalence of SARs-CoV-2 disease.
- iv Analyzing the effective implication of vaccine waning and transmission rate on the exposed population.

It's crucial to note that in all simulated graphs (Figure 4.34 - Figure 4.37), the dashed line represents the naive strain 1 (Eta variant), while the solid line represents strain 2

(Delta variant).

4.2.7.1 Investigating the effect of vaccine efficacy on the prevalence of Eta and Delta Variant of SARS-Cov-2 in the population.

The influence of different vaccine efficacy rates on the transmission dynamics of SARS-CoV-2 was examined. Figure 4.34 demonstrates the scenario where both the Eta and Delta variants circulate simultaneously in the population, with both having reproduction numbers above one (i.e., $\mathcal{R}_{c2} > \mathcal{R}_{c1} > 1$). Initially, the Eta variant is predominant, followed by the emergence of the Delta variant. The figure reveals that vaccine efficacy, represented by σ (ranging from 0.005 to 0.988), is a key factor in controlling the spread of the virus. Higher efficacy correlates with reduced transmission within the community, highlighting the critical role of vaccination in managing SARS-CoV-2 spread.

Moreover, vaccination efforts help to stabilize the infection rates for both the original Eta strain and the newer Delta variant. After the initial surge during the first wave in Nigeria, the number of infected individuals begins to plateau between the 4th and 10th months (August 2021 to January 2022), thanks to increased vaccine coverage.

Figure 4.34: Effect of vaccine waning on SARS-Cov-2 Infected Population for dual Strain Model, parameter used are presented in Table 4.2 (a): when $\mathcal{R}_{c1} > \mathcal{R}_{c2} > 1$,

In Figure 4.35, we explore the scenario where ($\mathcal{R}_{c1} > \mathcal{R}_{c2} > 1$), with $\beta_1 = 6.6935$ and $\beta_2 = 4.1196$, implying that the Eta variant has a transmission rate approximately 38% higher than that of the Delta variant. During the initial two months of the second wave in Nigeria, the number of Eta variant infections roughly doubles the number of Delta variant infections, indicating the potential severity if the Eta variant were more transmissible than the emerging Delta variant. This comparison suggests that if a highly transmissible variant like Delta does not emerge by around May 2021, SARS-CoV-2 cases could continue to decline

Figure 4.35: Effect of vaccine waning on SARS-Cov-2 Infected Population for dual Strain Model, parameter used are presented in Table 4.2 (b): when $\mathcal{R}_{c2} > \mathcal{R}_{c1} > 1$,

Figure 4.36: Effect of vaccine waning on SARS-Cov-2 Infected Population for dual Strain Model, parameter used are presented in Table 4.2 (c): when $\mathcal{R}_{c1} > 1$ and $\mathcal{R}_{c2} < 1$,

Figures 4.36 and 4.37 illustrate the influence of waning vaccine induced immunity on the dynamics of SARS-CoV-2 prevalence, specifically examining the interaction between the Eta and Delta variants. In Figure 4.36, during the initial phase of the third wave in Nigeria, the Eta variant exhibited a modest uptick in SARS-CoV-2 prevalence following the emergence of the Delta variant. Although the Delta variant initially maintained an effective reproduction number (\mathcal{R}_{c2}) below one, this eventually contributed to a gradual rise in prevalence due to declining vaccine efficacy. Concurrently, the Eta variant showed a slight increase in the number of infections.

Figure 4.37: Effect of vaccine waning on SARS-Cov-2 Infected Population for dual Strain Model, parameter used are presented in Table 4.2 (d): when $\mathcal{R}_{c2} > 1$ and $\mathcal{R}_{c1} < 1$

While in Figure 4.37, there was a marked escalation in cases from the second to the third wave, driven primarily by the Delta variant's effective reproduction number (\mathcal{R}_{c2}) exceeding unity. Nonetheless, higher vaccine efficacy (indicated by $\sigma = 0.005$ [dashed black line]) played a crucial role in reducing the prevalence of the Delta variant com-

pared to scenarios with lower efficacy ($\sigma = 0.9888$ [dashed blue line]).

Throughout this timeframe, both the Eta and Delta variants remained present within the population, each exerting a unique impact on SARS-CoV-2 transmission. Collectively, the figures underscore the intricate relationship between variant transmissibility, vaccine efficacy, and the resulting patterns of disease spread during consecutive waves of infection.

4.2.7.2 Examining distinct implications for each quasi-disease state of SARS-CoV-2 in the population.

In Figures 4.38 through 4.41, the population dynamics of the exposed, infected, and hospitalized compartments were explored under varying effective reproduction numbers.

Figure 4.38: Population Dynamics for each Quasi disease Variant, parameter use are presented in Table 4.2

Figure 4.38 presents a scenario where the basic reproduction number is above one in the absence of the Delta variant. Initially, there is a decline in the exposed population

during the first month, followed by a sudden increase. Meanwhile, both the infected and hospitalized populations grow gradually from the introduction of the Eta variant and eventually stabilize over time.

Figure 4.39: Population Dynamics for each Quasi disease Variant, parameter use are presented in Table 4.2

Conversely, Figure 4.39 shows the dynamics when the effective reproduction number is below one. Here, the exposed population declines significantly over a four-month period before stabilizing. The infected and hospitalized populations exhibit a slight but steady increase.

Figure 4.40: Population Dynamics for each Quasi disease Variant, parameter use are presented in Table 4.2

Figures 4.40 and 4.41 highlight the impact of the Delta variant (strain 1) in the absence of the Eta variant (strain 2). In Figure 4.40, the high transmissibility of the Delta variant causes a sharp drop in the exposed population during the first month, followed by a slight rise that could indicate a third wave. The infected population rises sharply and remains elevated for five months before gradually decreasing from the sixth month onward, suggesting the dominance of the Delta variant with a reproduction number exceeding one.

Figure 4.41: Population Dynamics for each Quasi disease Variant [dash Line denote the Delta Variant] parameter use are presented in Table 4.2

In contrast, Figure 4.41 represents a scenario where the effective reproduction number (\mathcal{R}_{c2}) for the second strain is below one. The exposed population steadily declines until stabilizing, while the infected population grows slightly for two months before declining to a low level. Interestingly, the hospitalized population grows significantly in both cases, regardless of whether \mathcal{R}_{c2} is above or below one.

4.2.7.3 Assessing the impact of each strain's transmission rate on the prevalence of SARs- CoV-2 disease.

In Figure 4.42 and 4.43, we explore the impact of transmission rates of two strains (Eta variant and Delta variant) on the prevalence of SARs-CoV-2 dynamics.

Figure 4.42: Impact of varying transmission rate of Eta strain on the prevalence of SARS-CoV-2 disease parameter use are presented in Table 4.2 for $\mathcal{R}_c > 1$

Figure 4.42 specifically investigates the ripple effects of varying the transmission rate (γ_1) of the Eta variant while maintaining the baseline transmission rate for the Delta variant (denoted by the dashed line). The results indicate that increasing γ_1 leads to a concurrent increase in the prevalence of both variants, with Eta showing a 10% growth from baseline when $\gamma_1 = 0.4715$ (denoted by solid black line in Figure 4.42), eventually reaching its endemic equilibrium. Despite this, the Delta variant remains the dominant force in the population, persisting and gradually increasing in prevalence over time even as γ_2 is held constant at its baseline value of $\gamma_2 = 0.4715$.

Figure 4.43: Impact of varying Delta strain transmission rate on the prevalence of SARS-CoV-2 disease. parameter use are presented in Table 4.2 for $\mathcal{R}_c > 1$

However, Figure 4.43 illustrates a scenario where the Delta variant exhibits dominance over the Eta variant in the population. Here, an increase in the transmission rate of the Delta variant (γ_2) leads to a corresponding increase in the prevalence of SARS-Cov-2 Delta variant across a range of γ_2 values from (0.4 to 0.8). This increase in γ_2 results in a decrease in the prevalence of the Eta variant (solid line in Figure 4.43), highlighting the suppressive effect of heightened Delta variant transmission rates on the prevalence of Eta variants in the population.

4.2.7.4 Analyzing the effective implication of vaccine waning and transmission rate on the exposed population.

In Figure 4.44 through 4.45, we simulate model (3.6) to examine the potential impact of vaccine efficacy (σ) and transmission rate (γ) on the exposed population.

Figures 4.44 and 4.47 depict a scenario where the effective reproduction number of the Eta variant exceeds unity, while that of the Delta variant is less than unity within the population. Initially, a sharp increase is observed in the population of exposed individuals to Eta variants within two months in Nigeria following the introduction of the Delta variant. The model simulation indicates a decline in the population of the Delta variant (strain 2) due to its effective reproduction number being less than unity. This suggests that prior to the onset of the second wave in Nigeria, there was a consistent decrease in the number of exposed individuals as γ_1 ranged from 0.4 to 0.7, while γ_2 remained at baseline levels.

Figure 4.44: Potential impact of varying immunity waning (σ) and transmission rate (γ) on the exposed population, using baseline parameters values presented in Table 4.2 (a): when $\mathcal{R}_{c1} > 1$, and $\mathcal{R}_{c2} < 1$

Figure 4.45: Potential impact of varying immunity waning (σ) and transmission rate (γ) on the exposed population, using baseline parameters values presented in Table 4.2 (b): when $\mathcal{R}_{c2} > 1$, and $\mathcal{R}_{c1} < 1$

However, in Figure 4.45 as the transmission rate of the Delta variant increases, our model simulation shows a steady decline in the prevalence of the Eta variant, accompanied by a surge in the Delta variant's population until it begins to decrease due to various mitigation measures being implemented, such as vaccination. This underscores the dynamic interplay between transmission rates, variant effective reproduction numbers, and the effectiveness of mitigation strategies in shaping population dynamics during disease outbreaks.

Figure 4.46: Potential impact of varying immunity waning (σ) and transmission rate (γ) on the exposed population, using baseline parameters values presented in Table 4.2 (c): when $\mathcal{R}_{c2} > \mathcal{R}_{c2} > 1$

Figure 4.47: Potential impact of varying immunity waning (σ) and transmission rate (γ) on the exposed population, using baseline parameters values presented in Table 4.2 (d): when $\mathcal{R}_{c1} > \mathcal{R}_{c1} > 1$

Figures 4.46 and 4.47 investigate the potential impact of immunity waning (σ) on the exposed population. Our simulation shows that varying σ from 0 to 0.99 results in a

sharp increase in the exposed population for both Eta and Delta variants simultaneously within two months of emergence. Subsequently, both variants gradually decline until stability is reached concurrently, particularly when the effective reproduction number is greater than unity. However, our model highlights a more pronounced concern regarding the reduced impact on Eta variants compared to Delta variants due to immunity waning. This implies that the Delta variant may necessitate a more potent vaccine to mitigate the effects of immunity waning among vaccinated individuals. The differential response underscores the importance of considering variant-specific characteristics and vaccine efficacy in public health strategies aimed at controlling infectious disease dynamics.

4.3 Qualitative Analysis of Optimal Control Model for Dual-Strain SARS-CoV-2 Dynamics

In this section, we explore the sufficient conditions for the existence of a solution to the optimal control problem (3.8) and provide a characterization of the optimal controls.

4.3.1 Existence of an Optimal Control Strategy for the Problem

The conditions that guarantee the existence of a solution to the optimal control problem is examined using the theorem below.

Theorem 4.3.1. *There exists an optimal control set (u_1^*, u_2^*, u_3^*) with a corresponding solution $(S^*, V^*, E_1^*, I_1^*, E_2^*, I_2^*, H^*, R^*)$ to the model system (3.8) that minimizes $J(u_1^*, u_2^*, u_3^*)$ over \mathbb{U} .*

Proof. The existence of the optimal control is ensured by the compactness of the control and state variables, as well as the convexity of the problem, according to Theorem 4.3.1 and its corresponding corollary proposed by (Fleming, 1975). The following non-trivial requirements of Fleming and Rishel's theorem are stated and verified as follows:

- i The set of all solutions to the model equations (3.8), along with its associated initial conditions and the corresponding control functions in \mathbb{U} , is non empty.
- ii The state system can be expressed as a linear function of the control variables, with coefficients that depend on time and state variables.
- iii The integrand (\mathbb{L}) in equations (3.9) and (3.10) is convex on \mathbb{U} and additionally satisfies certain conditions.

$$\mathbb{L}(t, S, V, E_1, I_1, E_2, I_2, H, R, u_1, u_2, u_3) \geq \varepsilon_1 \| (u_1, u_2, u_3) \|^{\alpha} - \varepsilon_2 \quad (4.94)$$

where $\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2 > 0$ and $\alpha > 1$. □

We refer to Theorem 3.1 from the Picard-Lindelöf framework as presented in Coddington & Levinson (1995). According to this result, if the solutions of the state system are bounded and the system itself is continuous and satisfies the Lipschitz condition with respect to the state variables, then a unique solution exists for every admissible control in set \mathbb{U} . In our case, each state variable $(S, V, E_1, I_1, E_2, I_2, H, R) \in \Omega$ is both upper- and lower-bounded, implying that the state solutions are confined within a finite range. Additionally, it can be readily shown that the partial derivatives of the right-hand side of the state equations with respect to the state variables are bounded, confirming the Lipschitz continuity of the system. This satisfies the first requirement. Moreover, a direct inspection of the model equations in (3.8) indicates that control functions $u_1(t)$, $u_2(t)$, and $u_3(t)$ appear linearly, satisfying the second requirement. As for the third condition, we observe that the integrand (\mathbb{L}) in the objective functional is convex due to its quadratic dependence on the control variables. To complete the verification, it remains to be demonstrated that \mathbb{L} is bounded, thereby satisfying the final requirement.

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbb{L} &= w_1 S + w_2 I_1 + w_3 I_2 + w_4 H + \frac{1}{2}(\kappa_1 u_1^2 + \kappa_2 u_2^2 + \kappa_3 u_3^2) \\
&\geq \frac{1}{2}(\kappa_1 u_1^2 + \kappa_2 u_2^2 + \kappa_3 u_3^2) \\
&\geq \frac{1}{2}(\kappa_1 u_1^2 + \kappa_2 u_2^2 + \kappa_3 u_3^2) - \kappa_1 \\
&\quad \text{Since } 0 \leq u_i < 1, \kappa_1 u_1^2 - \kappa_1 \leq 0 \tag{4.95} \\
&\geq \min\left(\frac{1}{2}\kappa_1, \frac{1}{2}\kappa_2, \frac{1}{2}\kappa_3\right)(u_1^2 + u_2^2 + u_3^2) - \kappa_1 \\
&\geq \mathbf{K} \|(u_1^2, u_2^2, u_3^2)\|^2 - \kappa_1 \\
&\quad \text{where } \mathbf{K} = \min\left(\frac{1}{2}\kappa_1, \frac{1}{2}\kappa_2, \frac{1}{2}\kappa_3\right)
\end{aligned}$$

Equation (4.95) shows that the integrand (\mathbb{L}) is bounded below. Thus, a unique solution to the optimality system exists for small time intervals, given the opposite time orientations of the state and adjoint equations. Furthermore, the uniqueness of the solution to

the optimality system ensures the uniqueness of the optimal control if it exists.

4.3.1.1 Characterization of the Dual Strain Optimal Controls

Here, we characterize the optimal controls (u_1^*, u_2^*, u_3^*) for the three adopted control measures and the corresponding states $(S^*, V^*, E_1^*, I_1^*, E_2^*, I_2^*, H^*, R^*)$. The necessary conditions for these optimal controls are derived using Pontryagin's Maximum Principle as described in Arruda *et al.* (2021) and Fleming (1975).

Theorem 4.3.2 (Necessary condition). *Let $(u_1^*, u_2^*, u_3^*) \in \mathbb{U}$ be an optimal control with the corresponding states $(S^*, V^*, E_1^*, I_1^*, E_2^*, I_2^*, H^*, R^*)$. Then, there exist the adjoint variables $(\chi_i$ for $i = 1, \dots, 8)$ that satisfy:*

$$\begin{aligned}
\chi_1' = & - \left[w_1 + \chi_1 \left(- \left(- \frac{\beta_1(H\varepsilon_1 + I_1)}{N^2} - \frac{\beta_2(H\varepsilon_2 + I_2)}{N^2} \right) S(1 - u_2) \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. - \left(\frac{\beta_1(H\varepsilon_1 + I_1)}{N} + \frac{\beta_2(H\varepsilon_2 + I_2)}{N} \right) (1 - u_2) - u_1 - \mu \right) \right. \\
& + \chi_2 \left(u_1 - (1 - u_2) \sigma \left(- \frac{\beta_1(H\varepsilon_1 + I_1)}{N^2} - \frac{\beta_2(H\varepsilon_2 + I_2)}{N^2} \right) V \right) \\
& + \chi_3 \left((1 - u_2) \frac{\beta_1(H\varepsilon_1 + I_1)}{N} - (V\sigma + S)(1 - u_2) \frac{\beta_1(H\varepsilon_1 + I_1)}{N^2} \right) \\
& \left. + \chi_5 \left((1 - u_2) \frac{\beta_2(H\varepsilon_2 + I_2)}{N} - (V\sigma + S)(1 - u_2) \frac{\beta_2(H\varepsilon_2 + I_2)}{N^2} \right) \right] \quad (4.96)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\chi_2' = & - \left[\chi_1 \left(- \left(- \frac{\beta_1(H\varepsilon_1 + I_1)}{N^2} - \frac{\beta_2(H\varepsilon_2 + I_2)}{N^2} \right) S(1 - u_2) + \alpha \right) \right. \\
& + \chi_2 \left(- (1 - u_2) \sigma \left(- \frac{\beta_1(H\varepsilon_1 + I_1)}{N^2} - \frac{\beta_2(H\varepsilon_2 + I_2)}{N^2} \right) V \right. \\
& \left. \left. - (1 - u_2) \sigma \left(\frac{\beta_1(H\varepsilon_1 + I_1)}{N} + \frac{\beta_2(H\varepsilon_2 + I_2)}{N} \right) - \alpha - \mu \right) \right. \\
& + \chi_3 \left((1 - u_2) \sigma \frac{\beta_1(H\varepsilon_1 + I_1)}{N} - (V\sigma + S)(1 - u_2) \frac{\beta_1(H\varepsilon_1 + I_1)}{N^2} \right) \\
& \left. + \chi_5 \left((1 - u_2) \sigma \frac{\beta_2(H\varepsilon_2 + I_2)}{N} - (V\sigma + S)(1 - u_2) \frac{\beta_2(H\varepsilon_2 + I_2)}{N^2} \right) \right] \quad (4.97)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\chi'_3 = & - \left[-\chi_1 \left(-\frac{\beta_1(H\varepsilon_1 + I_1)}{N^2} - \frac{\beta_2(H\varepsilon_2 + I_2)}{N^2} \right) S(1 - u_2) \right. \\
& - \chi_2(1 - u_2)\sigma \left(-\frac{\beta_1(H\varepsilon_1 + I_1)}{N^2} - \frac{\beta_2(H\varepsilon_2 + I_2)}{N^2} \right) V \\
& + \chi_3 \left(-(V\sigma + S)(1 - u_2) \frac{\beta_1(H\varepsilon_1 + I_1)}{N^2} - \gamma_1 - \mu \right) \\
& \left. + \chi_4\gamma_1 - \chi_5(V\sigma + S)(1 - u_2) \frac{\beta_2(H\varepsilon_2 + I_2)}{N^2} \right]
\end{aligned} \tag{4.98}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\chi'_4 = & - \left[w_2 - \chi_1 \left(\frac{\beta_1}{N} - \frac{\beta_1(H\varepsilon_1 + I_1)}{N^2} - \frac{\beta_2(H\varepsilon_2 + I_2)}{N^2} \right) S(1 - u_2) \right. \\
& - \chi_2(1 - u_2)\sigma \left(\frac{\beta_1}{N} - \frac{\beta_1(H\varepsilon_1 + I_1)}{N^2} - \frac{\beta_2(H\varepsilon_2 + I_2)}{N^2} \right) V \\
& + \chi_3 \left((V\sigma + S)(1 - u_2) \frac{\beta_1}{N} - (V\sigma + S)(1 - u_2) \frac{\beta_1(H\varepsilon_1 + I_1)}{N^2} \right) \\
& + \chi_4(-\tau_1 - d_1 - \psi_1 - \mu) - \chi_5(V\sigma + S)(1 - u_2) \frac{\beta_2(H\varepsilon_2 + I_2)}{N^2} \\
& \left. + \chi_7\tau_1 + \chi_8\psi_1 \right]
\end{aligned} \tag{4.99}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\chi'_5 = & - \left[-\chi_1 \left(-\frac{\beta_1(H\varepsilon_1 + I_1)}{N^2} - \frac{\beta_2(H\varepsilon_2 + I_2)}{N^2} \right) S(1 - u_2) \right. \\
& - \chi_2(1 - u_2)\sigma \left(-\frac{\beta_1(H\varepsilon_1 + I_1)}{N^2} - \frac{\beta_2(H\varepsilon_2 + I_2)}{N^2} \right) V \\
& - \chi_3(V\sigma + S)(1 - u_2) \frac{\beta_1(H\varepsilon_1 + I_1)}{N^2} \\
& + \chi_5 \left(- \left((V\sigma + S)(1 - u_2) \frac{\beta_2(H\varepsilon_2 + I_2)}{N^2} + \gamma_2 + \mu \right) \right) \\
& \left. + \chi_6\gamma_2 \right]
\end{aligned} \tag{4.100}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\chi'_6 = & - \left[w_3 - \chi_1 \left(-\frac{\beta_1(H\varepsilon_1 + I_1)}{N^2} + \frac{\beta_2}{N} - \frac{\beta_2(H\varepsilon_2 + I_2)}{N^2} \right) S(1 - u_2) \right. \\
& - \chi_2(1 - u_2)\sigma \left(-\frac{\beta_1(H\varepsilon_1 + I_1)}{N^2} + \frac{\beta_2}{N} - \frac{\beta_2(H\varepsilon_2 + I_2)}{N^2} \right) V \\
& - \chi_3(V\sigma + S)(1 - u_2) \frac{\beta_1(H\varepsilon_1 + I_1)}{N^2} \\
& + \chi_5 \left((V\sigma + S)(1 - u_2) \frac{\beta_2}{N} - (V\sigma + S)(1 - u_2) \frac{\beta_2(H\varepsilon_2 + I_2)}{N^2} \right) \\
& \left. + \chi_6(-\tau_2 - d_2 - \psi_2 - \mu) + \chi_7\tau_2 + \chi_8\psi_2 \right]
\end{aligned} \tag{4.101}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\chi_7' = & - \left[w_4 - \chi_1 \left(\frac{\beta_1 \varepsilon_1}{N} - \frac{\beta_1 (H\varepsilon_1 + I_1)}{N^2} + \frac{\beta_2 \varepsilon_2}{N} - \frac{\beta_2 (H\varepsilon_2 + I_2)}{N^2} \right) S(1 - u_2) \right. \\
& - \chi_2 (1 - u_2) \sigma \left(\frac{\beta_1 \varepsilon_1}{N} - \frac{\beta_1 (H\varepsilon_1 + I_1)}{N^2} + \frac{\beta_2 \varepsilon_2}{N} - \frac{\beta_2 (H\varepsilon_2 + I_2)}{N^2} \right) V \\
& + \chi_3 \left((V\sigma + S)(1 - u_2) \frac{\beta_1 \varepsilon_1}{N} - (V\sigma + S)(1 - u_2) \frac{\beta_1 (H\varepsilon_1 + I_1)}{N^2} \right) \\
& + \chi_5 \left((V\sigma + S)(1 - u_2) \frac{\beta_2 \varepsilon_2}{N} - (V\sigma + S)(1 - u_2) \frac{\beta_2 (H\varepsilon_2 + I_2)}{N^2} \right) \\
& \left. + \chi_7 (-u_3 - \mu - d_{12} - d_{21}) + \chi_8 u_3 \right] \quad (4.102)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\chi_8' = & - \left[\chi_1 \left(\varepsilon - \left(-\frac{\beta_1 (H\varepsilon_1 + I_1)}{N^2} - \frac{\beta_2 (H\varepsilon_2 + I_2)}{N^2} \right) S(1 - u_2) \right) \right. \\
& - \chi_2 (1 - u_2) \sigma \left(-\frac{\beta_1 (H\varepsilon_1 + I_1)}{N^2} - \frac{\beta_2 (H\varepsilon_2 + I_2)}{N^2} \right) V \\
& - \chi_3 (V\sigma + S)(1 - u_2) \frac{\beta_1 (H\varepsilon_1 + I_1)}{N^2} - \chi_5 (V\sigma + S)(1 - u_2) \frac{\beta_2 (H\varepsilon_2 + I_2)}{N^2} \\
& \left. + \chi_8 (-\varepsilon - \mu) \right] \quad (4.103)
\end{aligned}$$

and the transversality conditions, i.e.,

$$\chi_i(t_f) = 0, \text{ for } i = 1, \dots, 8, \quad \text{and} \quad N = S + V + E_1 + I_1 + E_2 + I_2 + H + R \quad (4.104)$$

with the optimal controls defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
u_1^* &= \min \left\{ \max \left(0, \frac{S(\chi_1 - \chi_2)}{\kappa_1} \right), u_{1max} \right\}, \\
u_2^* &= \min \left\{ \max \left(0, \frac{\zeta}{N\kappa_2} \right), u_{2max} \right\}, \\
u_3^* &= \min \left\{ \max \left(0, \frac{H(\chi_7 - \chi_8)}{\kappa_3} \right), u_{3max} \right\},
\end{aligned} \quad (4.105)$$

where $\zeta =$

$$(V(\chi_2 - \chi_3)\sigma - S(\chi_3 - \chi_1))(H\varepsilon_1 + I_1)\beta_1 + (V(\chi_2 - \chi_5)\sigma - S(\chi_5 - \chi_1))(H\varepsilon_2 + I_2)\beta_2. \quad (4.106)$$

Proof. Using Pontryagin's Maximum Principle, we obtain equations (4.96)–(4.103) us-

ing equation (4.107) as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{d\chi_1^*}{dt} &= -\frac{\partial \mathbb{H}}{\partial S}, \quad \frac{d\chi_2^*}{dt} = -\frac{\partial \mathbb{H}}{\partial V}, \quad \frac{d\chi_3^*}{dt} = -\frac{\partial \mathbb{H}}{\partial E_1}, \quad \frac{d\chi_4^*}{dt} = -\frac{\partial \mathbb{H}}{\partial I_1}, \\ \frac{d\chi_5^*}{dt} &= -\frac{\partial \mathbb{H}}{\partial E_2}, \quad \frac{d\chi_6^*}{dt} = -\frac{\partial \mathbb{H}}{\partial I_2}, \quad \frac{d\chi_7^*}{dt} = -\frac{\partial \mathbb{H}}{\partial H}, \quad \frac{d\chi_8^*}{dt} = -\frac{\partial \mathbb{H}}{\partial R}\end{aligned}\quad (4.107)$$

where the Hamiltonian (\mathbb{H}) is expressed as

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbb{H} &= w_1 S + w_2 I_1 + w_3 I_2 + w_4 H + \frac{1}{2}(\kappa_1 u_1^2 + \kappa_2 u_2^2 + \kappa_3 u_3^2) \\ &+ \chi_1 [\Pi + \varepsilon R - (\Upsilon_1 + \Upsilon_2)S(1 - u_2) + \alpha V - (u_1 + \mu)S] \\ &+ \chi_2 [u_1 S - (1 - u_2)\sigma(\Upsilon_1 + \Upsilon_2)V - (\alpha + \mu)V] \\ &+ \chi_3 [(S + \sigma V)(1 - u_2)\Upsilon_1 - (\gamma_1 + \mu)E_1] \\ &+ \chi_4 [\gamma_1 E_1 - (\tau_1 + \delta_1 + \psi_1 + \mu)I_1] \\ &+ \chi_5 [(S + \sigma V)\Upsilon_2(1 - u_2) - (\gamma_2 + \mu)E_2] \\ &+ \chi_6 [\gamma_2 E_2 - (\tau_2 + \delta_2 + \psi_2 + \mu)I_2] \\ &+ \chi_7 [\tau_1 I_1 + \tau_2 I_2 - (u_3 + \mu + \delta_{12} + \delta_{21})H] \\ &+ \chi_8 [\psi_1 I_1 + \psi_2 I_2 + u_3 H - (\varepsilon + \mu)R].\end{aligned}\quad (4.108)$$

The transversality conditions have the form of equation (4.104), since all the state variables are free at the terminal time. \square

The Hamiltonian is maximized with respect to the controls at the optimal control ($u^* = (u_1^*, u_2^*, u_3^*)$); thus, we differentiate \mathbb{H} with respect to u_1, u_2, u_3 , on \mathbb{U} to obtain

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\partial \mathbb{H}}{\partial u_1} &= \kappa_1 u_1 - \chi_2 S + \chi_1 S = 0 \text{ at } u_1 = u_1^* \\ \frac{\partial \mathbb{H}}{\partial u_2} &= N\kappa_2 u_2 - \zeta = 0 \text{ at } u_2 = u_2^* \\ \frac{\partial \mathbb{H}}{\partial u_3} &= \kappa_3 u_3 - \chi_7 H + \chi_8 H = 0 \text{ at } u_3 = u_3^*\end{aligned}\quad (4.109)$$

Hence, solving for u_1^* , u_2^* , and u_3^* yields

$$\begin{aligned}
u_1^* &= \frac{S(\chi_1 - \chi_2)}{\kappa_1}, \\
u_2^* &= \frac{\zeta}{N\kappa_2}, \\
u_3^* &= \frac{H(\chi_7 - \chi_8)}{\kappa_3}.
\end{aligned} \tag{4.110}$$

The bounds of $0 \leq u_1 \leq u_{1max}$, $0 \leq u_2 \leq u_{2max}$, and $0 \leq u_3 \leq u_{3max}$ are imposed on the controls (4.110) to obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
u_1^* &= \min \left\{ \max \left(0, \frac{S(\chi_1 - \chi_2)}{\kappa_1} \right), u_{1max} \right\}, \\
u_2^* &= \min \left\{ \max \left(0, \frac{\zeta}{N\kappa_2} \right), u_{2max} \right\}, \\
u_3^* &= \min \left\{ \max \left(0, \frac{H(\chi_7 - \chi_8)}{\kappa_3} \right), u_{3max} \right\}.
\end{aligned} \tag{4.111}$$

The next step involves solving the optimality system, which comprises the state equations defined in system (3.8), along with their initial conditions, and adjoint Equations (4.96)–(4.103), subject to the transversality conditions specified in (4.110).

4.3.2 Numerical Simulation for the Optimal Control Dual-Strain SARS-CoV-2 Dynamics Model

The model simulations are conducted using parameter values from existing literature, while parameters not available in the literature are inferred based on logical proportionality assumptions. The optimality system is defined by integrating the model system equation (3.9), the adjoint equations, and the control characterizations equation (4.105), implemented in MATLAB R2022B using the forward–backward sweep method introduced by Lenhart and Workman (Lenhart & Workman, 2007). This process involves a 16-dimensional system of ordinary differential equations, governed by both initial and transversality conditions. The iterative scheme, progressing from forward to back-

ward, follows the methodology outlined in (Yusuf *et al.*, 2022; Neilan, 2010), using the fourth-order Runge–Kutta numerical method. The parameters used in this analysis are presented in Table 4.2.

The study investigates the prevalence of the disease within the population by incorporating control variables into the dynamics of human interactions. The initial conditions for the state variables are set as follows: $S = 218,186,856$, $V = 1000$, $E_1 = 200,000$, $I_1 = 300$, $E_2 = 150,000$, $I_2 = 10$, $H = 10$, and $R = 3000$, with a final time horizon of 300 days. The weight coefficients and cost functional are assigned as $w_1 = 20$, $w_2 = 50$, $w_3 = 50$, $w_4 = 20$, $\kappa_1 = 12,000$, $\kappa_2 = 90,000$, and $\kappa_3 = 10,000$. Thus, we assume that $\kappa_1 > \kappa_2, \kappa_3$, indicating that the cost of vaccines and the implementation of a vaccination program is higher than the cost of non-pharmaceutical interventions (NPIs) and the effective treatment of infected individuals, respectively.

However, the formulated model (3.8) evaluates the incidence rate of Both Strain (Eta and Delta), individual control strategies, as well as combinations of interventions, to mitigate the prevalence of COVID-19 while considering their associated costs as presented below:

4.3.2.1 The incidence rates of Dual COVID-19 strains (Eta and Delta) analyzed based on the formulated model (3.8)

This analysis is conducted under two distinct scenarios:

- i In the absence of control measures depicted in (Figure 4.48);
- ii When control measures are implemented depicted in (Figure 4.49).

The simulation, as illustrated in Figure 4.48, highlight the variations in transmission dynamics under these conditions. Our findings align with the observations reported by the World Health Organization (WHO, 2021), which emphasize the high transmissibility

of the Delta variant. Thus, when the Delta strain first emerged in Nigeria, its rapid spread outpaced that of previous Eta variants, making it a dominant strain within a short period.

Figure 4.48: COVID-19 disease incidence for both strains (Eta and Delta) without control.

This reveals the heightened infectiousness of the Delta variant compared to the Eta strain, particularly in populations like Nigeria, where mitigation strategies were not promptly enforced.

Figure 4.49: COVID-19 disease incidence for both strains (Eta and Delta) with control.

As illustrated in Figure 4.49, the incidence rate of Eta (strain I) gradually declines following the emergence of the Delta strain in the population. The Delta strain exhibits steady growth, reaching a rate of approximately 1.5 million infected individuals before subsequently declining. This trend is observed when the model is simulated without control measures, using the parameter values specified in Table 4.2. In contrast, Figure 4.49 shows a more rapid decline in the incidence rate of the Eta strain, while the rise of Delta strain II is effectively mitigated, limiting infections to approximately 1 million individuals. This reduction is attributed to the implementation of control measures.

4.3.2.2 Single Control Strategy

The impact of individual control strategies on the dynamics of COVID-19 within the population is examined, with particular emphasis on assessing the overall burden posed by both virus strains. To do this, we consider the effects of applying each control strat-

egy in isolation—namely, vaccination, adherence to non-pharmaceutical interventions (NPIs), and treatment. By evaluating each strategy independently, we aim to understand its relative effectiveness in reducing disease prevalence and controlling transmission.

Figure 4.50: Impact of single control u_1 when $u_2 = u_3 = 0$. Vaccination-only approach

Figure 4.50 depicts when vaccination (u_1) is implemented as the sole control measure, there is a substantial reduction in disease prevalence compared to the scenario without any interventions. Specifically, the total number of infected individuals declines from approximately 10.1 million to 8.9 million, thereby preventing around 1.5 million additional infections. This highlights the significant role of vaccination in mitigating the spread of both virus strains in the population.

Figure 4.51:

Figure 4.52: Impact of single control u_1 when $u_2 = u_3 = 0$ vaccination-only profile.

The impact of vaccination as a control measure is further highlighted in Figure 4.52, which illustrates the control profile over time. The strategy initially maintains a high level of effectiveness, stabilizing at its peak for an extended period of approximately 300 days before gradually declining. This suggests that while vaccination plays a crucial role in curbing disease transmission and reducing infection rates, its long-term efficacy may diminish over time due to factors such as waning immunity, potential variations in vaccine uptake, or the emergence of new variants. Moreover, the observed stabilization period indicates that a sustained and consistent vaccination effort is required to achieve long-term disease suppression. Without periodic reinforcement through booster doses or complementary interventions, the effectiveness of vaccination alone may not be sufficient to fully eradicate the disease. Thus, while vaccination serves as a powerful tool in mitigating the spread of COVID-19, its success is contingent upon factors such as con-

tinued public compliance, the availability of booster programs, and the potential need for adaptive strategies to address evolving epidemiological challenges.

Figure 4.53: Impact of single control u_2 when $u_1 = u_3 = 0$. (NPI-only approach)

As illustrated in Figure 4.53, when non-pharmaceutical interventions (NPIs), denoted as u_2 , are implemented as the only control strategy, a noticeable delay occurs in the time taken for the disease to reach its peak prevalence. This delay is in stark contrast to scenarios where no intervention is applied, indicating that NPIs play a crucial role in slowing the transmission of the virus within the population. The enforcement of NPIs such as social distancing, mask mandates, movement restrictions, and hygiene protocols reduces the immediate exposure rate, thereby extending the time it takes for the infection to reach a significant proportion of individuals.

Figure 4.54: Impact of single control u_2 when $u_1 = u_3 = 0$. (NPI-only profile)

However, while NPIs effectively slow the rate of infection, their impact in terms of reducing the total number of infected individuals appears to be relatively modest compared to other control strategies. The preventive effect of NPIs alone results in only a slight reduction in the number of individuals infected with both strains of COVID-19. This suggests that while NPIs help mitigate the rapid spread of the virus, they may not be as effective as vaccination or treatment in significantly reducing the prevalence of overall disease. One potential reason for this limitation is that NPIs rely largely on behavioral compliance, which can be inconsistent across different demographics and over long periods. Furthermore, NPIs do not directly confer immunity, making them more effective when used in conjunction with other control measures rather than as a standalone approach.

Figure 4.55: Impact of single control u_3 when $u_1 = u_2 = 0$ (Treatment-only approach)

Figure 4.55 illustrates the impact of treatment as the sole intervention in curbing the spread of the dual-strain disease within the population. which significantly reduces the overall burden of the disease compared to scenarios where no intervention is applied. Treatment plays a critical role in not only reducing the severity of infections but also in limiting further transmission by shortening the infectious period of affected individuals. This, in turn, decreases the number of actively transmitting cases within the population. In the absence of any control measures, the prevalence of the disease exhibits an exponential rise, reaching approximately 10.5 million infected individuals before gradually declining. This pattern suggests that, without intervention, the disease follows a natural course of rapid spread until factors such as population immunity or resource depletion begin to slow transmission. However, when treatment is introduced as the sole control measure, a stark contrast is observed—the prevalence of the disease does not experience the same uncontrolled surge. Instead, treatment actively mitigates dis-

ease spread, leading to a substantial reduction in the number of infected individuals over time. This highlights the effectiveness of treatment in minimizing the overall disease burden and reducing the strain on healthcare systems.

Figure 4.56: Impact of single control u_3 when $u_1 = u_2 = 0$. (Treatment-only profile)

Moreover, the treatment control profile, as illustrated in Figure 4.56, reveals a sustained level of efficiency throughout the period of implementation. The control remains steady for approximately 300 days, indicating that treatment continues to be effective in reducing infections and improving recovery rates for an extended duration. This stability suggests that as long as treatment remains widely accessible and adequately administered, its impact on disease suppression can be maintained. However, after this period, a gradual decline in control efficacy is observed, reducing to its lowest level. This could be attributed to factors such as treatment saturation, potential resistance to therapeutic interventions, or limitations in healthcare capacity over prolonged periods.

4.3.2.3 Dual Control Strategy

Here, the impact of combining two control strategies either vaccination and treatment, vaccination and NPIs, or treatment and NPIs are analysed to effectively assess their influence in terms of reducing the prevalence of the disease burden. By implementing these dual control strategies, we aim to determine how their synergistic effects contribute in terms of mitigating the spread of the dual-strain disease compared to when each strategy is applied in isolation.

Figure 4.57: Impact of dual control with u_1 and u_2 when $u_3 = 0$. (Vaccination and NPIs)

As illustrated in Figure 4.57, the combined implementation of vaccination and non-pharmaceutical interventions (NPIs) was strategically employed to mitigate the prevalence of the COVID-19 dual-strain disease burden. The impact of these control measures was evident, as the population of infected individuals (represented by the red solid line) declined significantly. Specifically, in the absence of any intervention, the number of infected individuals peaked at approximately 10.2 million. However, when both vacci-

nation and NPIs were enforced in the population, this number reduced to 9.2 million, indicating a measurable decline in disease transmission.

Figure 4.58: Impact of dual control with u_1 and u_2 when $u_3 = 0$. (Control profile of vaccination and NPIs)

Furthermore, the control profile, as depicted in Figure 4.58, highlights the stability and efficacy of the vaccination strategy at its peak. The profile also reveals the behavior of NPIs, which remained at their lowest possible intensity for an initial period of 299 days before gradually increasing to their peak levels. Notably, after reaching this peak, the efficiency of NPIs exhibited periodic fluctuations over time. This dynamic response indicates the adaptability of NPIs in relation to real-time epidemiological conditions, reinforcing the necessity of a balanced approach combining pharmaceutical and non-pharmaceutical interventions to ensure sustained disease suppression.

Figure 4.59: Impact of a dual control strategy with u_1 and u_3 when $u_2 = 0$ (Vaccination and treatment)

As shown in Figure 4.59, the combined strategy of vaccination and treatment was implemented within the dynamic population, and its impact in terms of reducing COVID-19 prevalence was significant. The results indicate a dramatic decline in the number of infected individuals, from an initial peak of 10.1 million to a remarkably low 0.2 million, demonstrating the effectiveness of the adopted control measures.

Figure 4.60: Impact of a dual control strategy with u_1 and u_3 when $u_2 = 0$. (Vaccination and treatment profile)

Furthermore, Figure 4.60 reveals the stability and sustained efficacy of the control strategy during the initial 30-day period. Beyond this phase, both vaccination and treatment efforts gradually declined to their minimum levels, suggesting a shift in intervention intensity over time. This pattern underscores the potential of a well-calibrated vaccination and treatment strategy to achieve substantial disease suppression while also highlighting the need for continuous assessment to maintain long-term epidemiological control.

Figure 4.61: NPIs and treatment

As shown in Figure 4.61, our objective is to evaluate the effectiveness of a dual control strategy that incorporates both non-pharmaceutical interventions (NPIs) and effective treatment for individuals infected with either strain of COVID-19. This combined approach was designed to mitigate the overall disease prevalence within the population by targeting both infection prevention and recovery enhancement.

A closer examination of Figure 4.61 reveals that the implementation of these control measures had a profound impact in terms of reducing the disease burden. Specifically, the number of infected individuals declined significantly compared to scenarios where no control measures were in place. In the absence of intervention, the number of infections experienced a sharp and continuous rise, exacerbating disease transmission and increasing the overall burden on healthcare systems. However, with the application of NPIs and treatment, a substantial reduction in the number of infected individuals was observed, demonstrating the effectiveness of this dual strategy in curbing disease spread.

Figure 4.62: Impact of a dual control strategy with u_2 and u_3 when $u_1 = 0$ (Profile of NPIs and treatment)

Furthermore, the control profile illustrated in Figure 4.62 provides deeper insights into the stability and duration of these interventions. Notably, both control measures remained at their peak levels for approximately 150 days, indicating a sustained period of optimal intervention where transmission suppression and patient recovery were maximized. Beyond this period, treatment efforts began to decline, suggesting either a strategic relaxation of treatment measures or a shift in disease dynamics that required lower intervention intensity. Subsequently, NPIs maintained their effectiveness for a longer duration but eventually began to decline after approximately 280 days.

4.3.2.4 Triple Control Strategy

This approach integrates all three strategies—non-pharmaceutical interventions (NPIs), vaccination, and effective treatment—into a single control strategy to comprehensively evaluate their collective impact in terms of mitigating the spread of COVID-19 within

the population. By combining preventive, therapeutic, and immunization measures, this strategy aims to achieve optimal disease mitigation, ensuring a multi-faceted defense against both strains of the virus.

Figure 4.63: Impact of a triple control strategy ($u_1, u_2, u_3 \neq 0$)

As illustrated in Figure 4.63, the simultaneous application of these three control measures yielded a significant reduction in COVID-19 prevalence within the population. The impact was profound, as the number of infected individuals was drastically reduced to its lowest recorded levels, approaching what could be considered the near elimination of active infections. This finding underscores the critical synergy between vaccination, NPIs, and treatment; vaccination curtails susceptibility, NPIs limit transmission, and treatment enhances recovery, working collectively to drive the infection rate to its minimal threshold.

Figure 4.64: Impact of a triple control strategy ($u_1, u_2, u_3 \neq 0$).

Furthermore, the control profile, as depicted in Figure 4.64, provides insights into the temporal stability and efficiency of each intervention. Each control measure initially maintained a stable peak, indicating their sustained effectiveness in containing disease spread during the early phase of implementation. However, as the prevalence of the disease decreased, the necessity for each intervention diminished, leading to a gradual reduction in the intensity of the control. Interestingly, these declines did not occur simultaneously; instead, each strategy began to taper off at different intervals, suggesting a dynamic adaptation of control efforts based on evolving epidemiological conditions. This sequential reduction highlights the importance of continuous monitoring and adaptive implementation, ensuring that resources are allocated efficiently while maintaining long-term disease suppression.

4.3.3 Cost-Effectiveness Analysis

Cost-Effectiveness Analysis (CEA) is a tool for comparing the costs and outcomes of different interventions to determine the most efficient strategy. Commonly applied in healthcare, public policy, and business, CEA helps identify strategies that maximize benefits while minimizing costs. However in this section, CEA is used to evaluate the effectiveness of non-pharmaceutical interventions (NPIs), vaccination, and treatment programs in mitigating the spread of COVID-19, allowing for direct comparison of interventions with the same goal. For cost-effective analysis, we calculate the efficiency index (EI) and incremental cost-effectiveness ratio (ICER).

4.3.3.1 Efficiency Analysis of the Strategies

In this section, efficiency analysis is applied to identify the most effective control measure that prevents the greatest number of infections, irrespective of implementation costs. The control measure with the highest efficiency is regarded as the optimal choice among all available options. In simple terms, the intervention with the highest Efficiency Index (E.I) is considered the best control. For this analysis, the Efficiency Index (E.I) is defined as follows:

$$E.I = \frac{\text{Total infection averted by control}}{\text{Total infection without control}} \times 100 \quad (4.112)$$

Table 4.3 provides a detailed evaluation of the effectiveness of various control strategies—both single strategies and combined strategies for the management of dual-strain COVID-19 infections. Among single control strategies, implementing non-pharmaceutical interventions (NPIs), denote by (u_1) , averted approximately 1.497 million cases of infection, and the vaccination control strategy (u_2) alone prevented 2.399 million cases, while treatment control strategy (u_3) appears to be the most efficient single strategy,

averting a remarkable 56.73 million cases of infection. For combinations of two control strategies, NPIs combined with vaccination (u_1 and u_2) averted 1.5 million cases; NPIs and treatment (u_1 and u_3) prevented 57.986 million cases; and vaccination paired with treatment (u_2 and u_3) proved to be the most efficient dual-strategy approach, averting 62.128 million cases of infection. However, When all three controls (NPIs, vaccination, and treatment) were combined, they collectively averted 62.128 million cases, achieving an Efficiency Index (EI) of 98.8072. This makes the combination of all three controls the most effective and comprehensive strategy for curbing COVID-19 infections, followed closely by the dual vaccination and treatment strategy. Overall, these findings highlight the significant role of treatment in both single and combined strategies and the unparalleled efficiency of a holistic, multi-control approach in managing the pandemic, as presented in Figure 4.65.

Figure 4.65: Efficiency Indices for selected controls obtained through Equation (4.112).

Table 4.3: Efficiency Index table for applied control measures.

Applied Control	Total Infection Without Control	Total Infection With Control	Total Infection Averted	Total Cost	Efficiency Index
u1	6.29×10^{10}	6.14×10^9	1.50×10^{10}	6.00×10^6	2.3813
u2	6.29×10^{10}	6.05×10^{10}	2.40×10^9	6.65×10^6	3.8161
u3	6.29×10^{10}	6.15×10^9	5.67×10^{10}	5.00×10^6	90.2219
u1u2	6.29×10^{10}	6.14×10^{10}	1.50×10^9	7.40×10^6	2.3848
u1u3	6.29×10^{10}	4.89×10^9	5.80×10^{10}	1.10×10^7	92.2198
u2u3	6.29×10^{10}	7.50×10^8	6.21×10^{10}	4.64×10^7	98.807
u1u2u3	6.29×10^{10}	7.50×10^8	6.21×10^{10}	5.00×10^7	98.8072

4.3.3.2 Incremental Cost-Effectiveness Ratio (ICER)

The incremental cost-effectiveness ratio (ICER) measures the ratio between costs and health benefits of any two interventions competing for the same limited resources. The calculation of the ICER makes use of the following formula:

$$ICER = \frac{\text{change in total cost of intervention}}{\text{change in total infections averted by interventions}} \quad (4.113)$$

In the context of evaluating two competing strategies, say J and G , and supposing that strategy G demonstrates greater effectiveness compared to strategy J (mathematically expressed as $TA(G) > TA(J)$), the incremental cost-effectiveness ratio (ICER) serves as a critical metric for comparing the two strategies. The ICER quantifies the additional cost required to achieve an additional unit of effectiveness when moving from the less effective strategy (J) to the more effective one (G). The ICER for strategy J is often referred to as the baseline strategy, which is calculated by dividing its total cost ($TC(J)$) by its total effectiveness ($TA(J)$):

$$ICER(J) = \frac{TC(J)}{TA(J)}$$

For strategy G , which is more effective, the ICER is calculated incrementally by comparing it directly to strategy J . This involves subtracting the total cost of strategy J from

that of strategy G and dividing the result by the difference in their effectiveness:

$$ICER(G) = \frac{TC(G) - TC(J)}{TA(G) - TA(J)}$$

This method has been applied to determine the most cost-effective intervention in the control of diseases by a number of researchers Asamoah *et al.* (2021); Yusuf *et al.* (2022); Khan *et al.* (2022); Omede *et al.* (2023). Using the simulation results with budget cost for NPIs, vaccination, and treatment ($\kappa_1 = 12000$, $\kappa_2 = 90000$, $\kappa_3 = 10000$), we ranked our control strategies in order of the number of averted infections (in increasing order), as presented in Table 4.4.

Control strategy u_1 is compared with control strategy u_1u_2 with respect to increased effectiveness and in reference to Table 4.4.

$$ICER(u_1) = \frac{TC(u_1)}{TA(u_1)} = \frac{5,997,100}{1497300000} = 0.00401$$

$$ICER(u_1u_2) = \frac{TC(u_1u_2) - TC(u_1)}{TA(u_1u_2) - TA(u_1)} = \frac{7,395,300 - 5,997,100}{1,499,500,000 - 1,497,300,000} = 0.63555$$

Control strategy u_1u_2 is less effective compared to control strategy u_1 , as indicated by the fact that $ICER(u_1) < ICER(u_1u_2)$. Consequently, control strategy u_1u_2 is excluded from the set of viable control options under consideration, as presented in Table 4.5.

Table 4.4: Summary of applied control strategies for first iteration

Applied Control	Total Infection Averted	Total Cost	ICER
u_1	1,497,300,000	5,997,100	0.00400
u_1u_2	1,499,500,000	7,395,300	0.00490
u_2	2,399,500,000	6,653,600	0.00280
u_3	56,730,000,000	4,997,600	0.00009
u_1u_3	57,986,000,000	10,997,000	0.00019
u_2u_3	62,128,000,000	46,381,000	0.00075
$u_1u_2u_3$	62,128,000,000	50,037,000	0.00081

Table 4.5: Summary of applied control strategies for second iteration, eliminating u_1u_2 .

Applied Control	Total Infection Averted	Total Cost	ICER
u_1	1,497,300,000	5,997,100	0.00400
u_2	2,399,500,000	6,653,600	0.00280
u_3	56,730,000,000	4,997,600	0.00009
u_1u_3	57,986,000,000	10,997,000	0.00019
u_2u_3	62,128,000,000	46,381,000	0.00075
$u_1u_2u_3$	62,128,000,000	50,037,000	0.00081

Next, we compare control strategy u_1 with control strategy u_2 . The ICER values for strategy u_1 and control strategy u_2 are calculated below using values from Table 4.5:

$$ICER(u_1) = \frac{TC(u_1)}{TA(u_1)} = \frac{5,997,100}{1497300000} = 0.00401$$

$$ICER(u_2) = \frac{TC(u_2) - TC(u_1)}{TA(u_2) - TA(u_1)} = \frac{6,653,600 - 5,997,100}{2,399,500,000 - 1,497,300,000} = 0.000728$$

Thus, control strategy u_1 is less effective than control strategy u_2 , since $ICER(u_2) < ICER(u_1)$. Hence, control strategy u_1 is eliminated from the set of control options to be considered.

Furthermore, we compare control strategy u_2 with control strategy u_3 . The ICER values for strategy u_2 and control strategy u_3 are calculated below using values from Table 4.6:

$$ICER(u_2) = \frac{TC(u_2)}{TA(u_2)} = \frac{6,653,600}{2,399,500,000} = 0.00280$$

$$ICER(u_3) = \frac{TC(u_3) - TC(u_2)}{TA(u_3) - TA(u_2)} = \frac{-1,656,000}{54,330,500,000} = -0.00003$$

Thus, control strategy u_3 is less effective than control strategy u_2 , since $ICER(u_3) < ICER(u_2)$. Hence, control strategy u_2 is eliminated from the set of control options to be considered.

The cost-effectiveness analysis of control strategies in Table 4.7 reveals varying impacts

on infection reduction and overall expenses in managing a dual-strain COVID-19 outbreak. The results indicate that while intervention u_3 alone is the least costly, it averts the fewest infections (56.73 million). Combining u_1 with u_3 (u_1u_3) offers a better balance, preventing 57.98 million infections at a slightly higher cost (10.99 million Naira) and a relatively low ICER (0.00019), making it an attractive option for resource-limited settings. The most comprehensive strategy (u_1, u_2, u_3) achieves the highest infection reduction (62.13 million) but is the most expensive (50.04 million Naira), with a higher ICER (0.00081), indicating that its additional benefits come at a greater cost. This strategy may be appropriate when reducing infections is a critical priority despite budget constraints.

Table 4.6: Summary of applied control strategies for third iteration eliminating u_1 .

Applied Control	Total Infection Averted	Total Cost	ICER
u2	2,399,500,000	6,653,600	0.00280
u3	56,730,000,000	4,997,600	0.00009
u1u3	57,986,000,000	10,997,000	0.00019
u2u3	62,128,000,000	46,381,000	0.00075
u1u2u3	62,128,000,000	50,037,000	0.00081

Table 4.7: Summary of applied control strategies for fourth iteration eliminating u_2 .

Applied Control	Total Infection Averted	Total Cost	ICER
u3	56,730,000,000	4,997,600	-0.00003
u1u3	57,986,000,000	10,997,000	0.00019
u2u3	62,128,000,000	46,381,000	0.00075
u1u2u3	62,128,000,000	50,037,000	0.00081

However, cost effectiveness results reveal a middle-ground approach represented by u_2, u_3 , which prevents 62.13 million infections at the same cost of 46.38 million Naira but with a slightly lower ICER of 0.00075. This strategy is ideal for policymakers who seek high effectiveness without implementing all three interventions, particularly if one intervention (u_1) is difficult to enforce or sustain. While not as effective as u_1, u_2, u_3 , it offers nearly the same level of infection prevention at a slightly better cost-effectiveness

ratio. From a policy perspective, the best approach depends on the available budget and the public health priorities of a given nation. Governments or organizations with financial limitations should prioritize u_1, u_3 , as it provides a significant reduction in infections at a manageable cost. In contrast, if the objective of the Nigerian government is to achieve the highest possible reduction in infections, then u_1, u_2, u_3 is the most suitable choice, despite its high cost. For governments seeking a balance between financial feasibility and effectiveness, u_2, u_3 presents an optimal compromise. Ultimately, these insights offer a data-driven framework for the design and implementation of COVID-19 control policies that align with both economic constraints and public health objectives.

CHAPTER FIVE

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusion

In this thesis, we developed and comprehensively analyzed an enhanced deterministic model describing the transmission dynamics of COVID-19 in Nigeria, focusing on two dominant SARS-CoV-2 variants: a naive strain (Eta) and an emerging strain (Delta). The model integrates recent insights about reinfection following recovery and immunity loss due to waning, providing a realistic framework for understanding the ongoing spread of the disease. In order to calibrate the model, we used available outbreak data from the Nigeria Centre for Disease Control (NCDC) and the World Health Organization (WHO, 2021; Worldometer, 2024), fitting the model (3.6) to estimate key unknown parameters.

The principal findings from our qualitative and quantitative analyses include:

- i Disease-Free and Endemic Equilibria: The model exhibits two equilibria: a disease-free equilibrium that is globally asymptotically stable (GAS) when the control reproduction number (\mathcal{R}_c) is below one, and an endemic equilibrium that is locally asymptotically stable when $\mathcal{R}_c < 1$. This indicates the presence of backward bifurcation driven by factors such as reinfection of vaccinated individuals, immunity waning, and suboptimal vaccination rates.
- ii Backward Bifurcation Dynamics: The occurrence of backward bifurcation in model is primarily induced by inadequate vaccination coverage specifically, when the vaccination rate ρ is low and the effective infection rate among vaccinated individuals σ remains significant thereby providing critical insights for the design of more effective control strategies against SARS-CoV-2.

- iii **Impact of Vaccine Efficacy:** The analysis highlights the pivotal role of vaccine efficacy in mitigating disease transmission. Enhanced vaccine performance will remarkably lowers the effective infection rate among vaccinated individuals (σ), thereby promoting stable infection dynamics for both co-circulating Eta and Delta variants over time.
- iv **Variant Interactions and Prevalence Dynamics:** The research highlights how variant specific characteristics collectively influence disease prevalence during multiple waves of infection. The model simulations results established that deploring effective vaccine would remarkably help in controlling infection rates among existing and emerging variants.
- v **Variant Transmission Rates:** The study reveals that differences in transmission rates between the Eta and Delta variants substantially affect their respective prevalence. Thus, an increase in the Delta variant's transmission rate, for example, can suppress the spread of the Eta variant.

In addition to the baseline model of COVID-19 dynamics, this thesis also developed an extended dual-strain model (3.8) that integrates crucial control measures namely: vaccination, non-pharmaceutical interventions (NPIs), and treatment strategies applied as time-dependent functions. This extension aims to provide a more comprehensive framework for assessing the practical impact of interventions on the spread of dual strain COVID-19 within Nigerian population.

The extended model (4.77), was rigorously analyzed to ensure that it is both mathematically well pose and epidemiologically relevant.

To explore the effectiveness of these time-dependent interventions, optimal control theory was applied, specifically using Pontryagin's Maximum Principle. This enabled a

systematic analysis of the non-autonomous system, which involves a 16-dimensional system of ordinary differential equations governed by both epidemiological dynamics and time-varying control efforts.

The model was further analyzed through a series of numerical simulations, designed to assess how different combinations and intensities of control measures can influence the spread of COVID-19. These simulations were structured into three distinct scenarios for clarity and thorough evaluation:

- i Assessment of single control strategies to understand their individual impacts on disease prevalence.
- ii Examination of dual control strategies, evaluating how combinations of interventions interact and potentially amplify their effects.
- iii Analysis of triple control strategies, exploring scenarios with different levels of implementation cost and varying weights assigned to each intervention to determine optimal resource allocation and disease mitigation.

The simulation results highlight the importance of integrated control strategies in managing the transmission dynamics of multiple COVID-19 strains. They emphasize that a combination of high vaccine uptake, adherence to NPIs, and effective treatment strategies can substantially reduce the disease burden, even in the face of emerging variants with different transmission potentials.

5.2 Contribution to Knowledge

This thesis makes the following contributions:

1. Developed a novel dual-strain transmission model for COVID-19 in Nigeria, incorporating reinfection, waning immunity, and vaccination.
2. Introduced a new time-dependent optimal control problem (OCP) to evaluate intervention strategies and guide efficient allocation of limited resources.
3. Demonstrated that improved vaccine performance, represented by parameter σ , significantly enhances control of both Eta and Delta variants.
4. Established that reducing the infection rate of the dominant Delta strain below a critical threshold ($\mathcal{R}_0 \leq 0.5$) suppresses the Eta strain and can lead to disease elimination.
5. Revealed the persistence of disease due to backward bifurcation, even under vaccination efforts, for co-circulating strains of COVID-19 in Nigeria.

5.3 Recommendations

The newly developed, enhanced mathematical model capturing the dual strain dynamics of COVID-19 represents a significant step forward. It is expected that findings from this research would aid evidence based decision making, and provide guidelines to policy makers to make informed policies that would help address the threats of COVID-19.

This thesis highlights the crucial importance should aim to reduce the effective reproduction number to below 0.5 to prevent the disease from becoming endemic, and embracing an integrated, multi-layered approach to controlling the spread of COVID-19, particularly in the context of Nigeria's co-circulating dual variants. The analysis shows that although individual interventions such as vaccination, non-pharmaceutical interventions (NPIs), or treatment—each contribute to reducing disease transmission,

their isolated implementation often results in only partial control of the epidemic. In contrast, a combination of these strategies generates a synergistic effect, significantly enhancing the suppression of disease spread. This finding is of particular value to public health policymakers, as it demonstrates that a comprehensive, coordinated response yields the most substantial reduction in disease burden and effectively curtails the risk of future outbreaks.

A key finding from the cost-effectiveness and infection reduction analysis is that different strategies may be optimal depending on available resources and public health priorities. For example, implementing treatment only strategies emerges as the most cost-effective option, with the lowest incremental cost-effectiveness ratio (ICER), providing excellent value per infection averted. However, when prioritizing the greatest reduction in disease prevalence, a complete triple control strategy including vaccination, NPI, and treatment yields the highest number of infections averted, despite the associated higher costs. In addition, a dual control approach combining vaccination and treatment offers a balanced compromise between cost and impact, effectively reducing the burden of infection at a relatively modest increase in expenditure compared to treatment alone.

In conclusion, policymakers are advised to adopt a flexible approach that aligns control measures with available budgets and evolving epidemiological data. Investment in vaccination and treatment programs, combined with ongoing public health education and enforcement of NPIs, will be essential for sustainable control of COVID-19, particularly in light of the threat of new variants. This integrated strategy not only mitigates the immediate impact of the disease but also builds resilience against future outbreaks, contributing to a healthier and COVID-19 free population.

References

- Anderson, R. M., & May, R. M. (1991). *Infectious diseases of humans: Dynamics and control*. Oxford University Press.
- Arruda, E. F., Das, S. S., Dias, C. M., & Pastore, D. H. (2021). Modelling and optimal control of multi strain epidemics, with application to covid-19. *PLoS ONE*, *16*. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0257512>
- Asamoah, J. K. K., Zhen, J., Sun, G.-Q., Seidu, B., Yankson, E., Abidemi, A., ... Okyere, E. (2021). Sensitivity assessment and optimal economic evaluation of a new covid-19 compartmental epidemic model with control interventions. *Chaos Solitons Fractals*. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chaos.2021.110885>
- Avila-Ponce, U. L., Avila-Vales, E., & Huang, K. I. (2022). Modeling covid-19 dynamic using a two-strain model with vaccination. *Chaos, Solitons and Fractals*, *157*, 111927. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chaos.2022.111927>
- Bhatter, S. S., Jangid, K., Abidemi, A., Owolabi, K. M., & Purohit, S. D. (2023). A new fractional mathematical model to study the impact of vaccination on covid-19 outbreaks. , *6*(100156). Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dajour.2022.100156>
- Brauer, F. (2017). Mathematical epidemiology: Past, present, and future. *Infectious Disease Modelling*, *2*(2), 113 -127.
- Brownlee, J. (1907). Statistical studies in immunity: the theory of an epidemic. *Proceedings of the Royal Society of Edinburgh*.
- Bugalia, S., Bajjiya, V., Tripathi, J. P., & Li, G. Q., M. T.and Sun. (2020). Mathematical modeling of covid-19 transmission: the roles of intervention strategies and lockdown. *Math. Biosci. Eng.*, *17*(5), 5961–5986.
- Castillo-Chavez, C., & Song, B. (2004). Dynamical models of tuberculosis and their applications. *Math. Biosci. Eng.*, *2*, 361–404.
- CDC. (1990). *Current trends mortality patterns*. Retrieved from <https://www.cdc.gov/mmwr/preview/mmwrhtml/00001580.htm>
- CDC. (2023). Sars-cov-2 variant classifications and definitions. Retrieved from <https://www.cdc.gov/coronavirus/2019-ncov/variants/variant-classifications.html> (Accessed: July 2023)

- Coddington, E. A., & Levinson, N. (1995). *Theory of ordinary differential equations*. McGraw Hill: New York, NY, USA.
- Danbaba, U. A., & Garba, S. M. (2020). Stability analysis and optimal control for yellow fever model with vertical transmission. *Int. J. Appl. Comput. Math*, 6(105). Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40819-020-00860-z>
- Diekmann, O., Heesterbeek, J. A., & Roberts, M. G. (2010). The construction of next-generation matrices for compartmental epidemic models. *J R Soc Interface*, 7, 873–885.
- Dushoff, J., Huang, W., & Castillo-Chavez, C. (1998). Backward bifurcations and catastrophe in simple models of fatal diseases. *Journal of Mathematical Biology*, 36(3), 227-248. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1007/s002850050099>
- ECDPC. (2023). *European centre for disease prevention and control*. Retrieved from <https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/covid-19-pandemic> (Accessed: August 2023)
- ECDPC-2. (2023). *Covid-19 vaccination and prioritisation strategies in the eu/eea*. Retrieved from <https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/publications-data/covid-19-vaccination-and-prioritisation-strategies-eueea> (Accessed: August 2023)
- Enahoro, I., Sharomi, O., Calistus, N. N., & Gumel, A. B. (2020). Mathematical modelling and analysis of covid-19 pandemic in nigeria. *Mathematical Biosciences and Engineering*, 17, 7192-7220. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.3934/mbe.2020369>
- En'Ko, P. D. (1889). On the course of epidemics of some infectious diseases. *International Journal of Epidemiology*, 18(4), 749–75.
- Fleming, R., W.H. and Rishel. (1975). *Deterministic and stochastic optimal control*. Springer: New York, NY, USA.
- Giordano, G., Blanchini, F., Bruno, R., Colaneri, P., Di Filippo, A., Di Matteo, A., & Colaneri, M. (2020). Modelling the covid-19 epidemic and implementation of population-wide interventions in italy. *Nature Medicine*, 26, 855-860. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-020-0883-7>
- Gonzalez-Parra, G., Martínez-Rodríguez, D., & Villanueva-Micó, R. J. (2021). Impact of a new sars-cov-2 variant on the population, a mathematical modeling approach. *Math. Comput.Appl.*, 26. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.3390/mca26020025>

- Hammer, W. N. (1906). Epidemic disease in england—the evidence of variability and the persistence of type. *The Lancet*, 733-739.
- Harapan, H., Itoh, N., Yufika, A., Winardi, W., Keam, S., Te, H., ... Mudatsir, M. (2020). Coronavirus disease 2019 (covid-19): A literature review. *Journal of Infection and Public Health*, 13, 667–673. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jiph.2020.03.019>
- Huang, Y., Yang, C., Xu, X., Xu, W., & Liu, S. (2020). *Acta Pharmacol Sin*, 41, 1141–1149. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41401-020-0485-4>
- Iboi, E., Ngonghala, C. N., & Gumel, A. B. (2020). Will an imperfect vaccine curtail the sars-cov-2 pandemic in the us? *Infectious Disease Modelling*, 5(510e524). Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.idm.2020.07.006>
- Idisi, I., & Yusuf, T. T. (2021). A mathematical model for lassa fever transmission dynamics with impacts of control measures: Analysis and simulation. *EJ-Math*, 2(2). Retrieved from <http://dx.doi.org/10.24018/ejmath.2021.2.2.17>
- Idisi., I. O., Yusuf, T. T., Owolabi, K. M., & Ojokoh, B. (2023). A bifurcation analysis and model of sars-cov-2 transmission dynamics with post-vaccination infection impact. *Healthcare Analytics*, 3(100157). Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.health.2023.100157>
- Integrity. (2024). Voi vs voc what makes the difference. Retrieved from <https://integritylaboratories.com/index.php/2021/11/15/variant-of-interest-vs-variant-of-concern/> (Accessed: 17, March)
- Isaac, M. W. (2017). Backward bifurcation and reinfection in mathematical models of tuberculosis. *A thesis submitted in fulfilment of the requirements for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy, RMIT University.*
- Ivorra, M. R., B.and Ferrández, Vela-Pérez, M., & Ramos, A. M. (2019). Mathematical modeling of the spread of the coronavirus disease (covid-19) taking into account the undetected infections. the case of china. *Communications in Nonlinear Science and Numerical Simulation*, 88(105303). Retrieved from <http://www.doi:10.1016/j.cnsns.2020.105303>.
- Kakavandi, S., Zare, I., VaezJalali, M., Dadashi, M., Azarian, M., Akbari, A., ... Hajikhani, B. (2023). Structural and non-structural proteins in sars-cov-2: potential aspects to covid-19 treatment or prevention of progression of related diseases. *Cell Commun Signal*, 21(110). Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12964-023-01104-5>

- Kamgang, J. C., & Sallet, G. (2005). Global asymptotic stability for the disease free equilibrium for epidemiological models. *C. R. Acad. Sci. Paris, I341*, 433–438. Retrieved from <http://france.elsevier.com/direct/CRASS1/>
- Katia, K., Michael, A. M., Rustom, A., Ben, L., & Natalie, E. D. (2022). The changing epidemiology of sars-cov-2. *Science*, 375(6585), 1116-1121. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.abm4915>
- Kermack, W. O., & McKendrick, A. G. (1972). A contribution to the mathematical theory of epidemics. *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London A*, 115(772). Retrieved from <https://www.doi:10.1098/rspa.1927.0118> (Physical and Engineering Sciences)
- Khan, A. A., Ullah, S., & Amin, R. (2022). Optimal control analysis of covid-19 vaccine epidemic model: A case study. *Eur. Phys. J. Plus*. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1140/epjp/s13360-022-02365-8>
- Kribs-Zaleta, J. X., C. M. and Velasco-Hernández. (1990). A simple vaccination model with multiple endemic states. *Mathematical Biosciences*, 164(2), 183-201. Retrieved from [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0025-5564\(00\)00004-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0025-5564(00)00004-3)
- Kumar, S. (2023). *Historical development of microbiology*. Retrieved from <https://www.jaypeedigital.com/eReader/chapter/9789350255100/ch1> (Accessed: October, 2023)
- Laue, M., Kauter, A., Hoffmann, T., Möller, L., Michel, J., & Nitsche, A. (2021). Morphometry of sars-cov and sars-cov-2 particles in ultrathin plastic sections of infected vero cell cultures. *Sci Rep*, 11(3515). Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-82852-7>
- Lenhart, S., & Workman, J. T. (2007). Optimal control applied to biological models. *CRC press*.
- Li, J., Jia, H., Tian, M., Wu, N., Yang, X., Qi, J., ... Bian, H. (2022). Sars-cov-2 and emerging variants: Unmasking structure, function, infection, and immune escape mechanisms. *Front Cell Infect Microbiol*, 12(12). Retrieved from <https://www.doi:10.3389/fcimb.2022.869832>
- Lin, Q., Zhao, S., Gao, D., Lou, Y., Yang, S., & Salihu, S. M. (2020). A conceptual model for the coronavirus disease 2019 (covid-19) outbreak in wuhan, china with individual reaction and governmental action. *International Journal of Infectious Diseases*, 93, 211-216. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijid.2020.02.058>

- Lu, R., Zhao, X., Li, J., Niu, P., Yang, B., Wu, H., & et al. (2020). Genomic characterisation and epidemiology of 2019 novel coronavirus: implications for virus origins and receptor binding. *Lancet*.
- Lynne, P. (2021). Covid reinfections likely within one or two years, model purpose. *Nature Med*. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-021-02825-8>
- Marino, S., Hogue, I. B., Ray, C. J., & Kirschner, D. E. (2008). A methodology for performing global uncertainty and sensitivity analysis in systems biology. *J Theor Biol*, 254(1), 178–197.
- Martin, L., & Preston, S. (1994). Socioeconomic differences in adult mortality and health. *National Academies Press*. Retrieved from <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK236675/> (National Research Council (US) Committee on Population)
- Mathew, D. J., & Bruce, P. (2020). A dynamical framework for modeling fear of infection and frustration with social distancing incovid-19 spread. *Math Biosci Eng.*, 17(6), 7892-7915. Retrieved from <https://doi:10.3934/mbe.2020401>.
- Moyo, E., Mhango, M., Moyo, P., Dzinamarira, T., Chitungo, I., & Murewanhema, G. (2023). Emerging infectious disease outbreaks in sub-saharan africa: Learning from the past and present to be better prepared for future outbreaks. *Front Public Health.*, 9(11). Retrieved from <https://www.doi:10.3389/fpubh.2023.1049986>.
- Mushayabasa, S., Ngarakana-Gwasira, E. T., & Mushanyu, J. (2020). On the role of governmental action and individual reaction on covid-19 dynamics in south africa: a mathematical modelling study. *Inform. Med.*, 20(100387).
- NCBI. (2023a). Aristotele. Retrieved from <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC10392237/> (Accessed: October, 2023)
- NCBI. (2023b). *A prelude to mathematical epidemiology*. Retrieved from <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7123289/> (Accessed: October, 2023)
- NCDC. (2020). *First confirm case of covid-19*. Retrieved from <https://ncdc.gov.ng/news/227/first-case-of-corona-virus-disease-confirmed-in-nigeria> (Accessed: 28 February)
- Neilan, S., R. M.and Lenhart. (2010). An introduction to optimal control with an application in disease modeling. *Am. Math. Soc.* Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1090/dimacs/075/03>

- Ngonghala, C. N., Iboi, E., Eikenberry, S., Scotch, M., MacIntyre, C. R., Bonds, M. H., & Gumel, A. B. (2020). Mathematical assessment of the impact of non-pharmaceutical interventions on curtailing the 2019 novel coronavirus. *Mathematical Biosciences*. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mbs.2020.108364>
- Ngonghala, C. N., Taboea, H. B., Safdar, S., & Gumel, A. B. (2023). Unraveling the dynamics of the omicron and delta variants of the 2019 coronavirus in the presence of vaccination, mask usage, and antiviral treatment. *Applied Mathematical Modelling*, *114*, 447–465. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apm.2022.09.017>
- Oke, I. I., Oyebo, Y. T., Fakoya, O. F., Benson, V. S., & Yusuf, T. T. (2021). A mathematical model for covid-19 disease transmission dynamics with impact of saturated treatment: Modeling, analysis and simulation. *Open Access Library Journal*, *8*.
- Okuonghae, D., & Omame, A. (2020). Analysis of a mathematical model for covid-19 population dynamics in lagos, nigeria. *Chaos, Solutions and Fractals*. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chaos.2020.110032>
- Oluwatosin, W. A., Ehimario, U. I., Kelly, O. E., & et al. (2022). Sars-cov-2 vaccine effectiveness studies in nigeria: Quo vadis? *J, Glob Health*, *12*(03055).
- Omede, B., Odionyenma, U., & Ibrahim, B., A.A. and Bolaji. (2023). Third wave of covid-19: Mathematical model with optimal control strategy for reducing the disease burden in nigeria. *Int. J. Dynam. Control*. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40435-022-00982-w>
- Plana-Ripoll, O., Weye, N., Momen, N., Christensen, M., Iburg, K., Laursen, T., & McGrath, J. (2020). Changes over time in the differential mortality gap in individuals with mental disorders. *JAMA Psychiatry*, *77*(6), 648-650. Retrieved from <https://www.doi:10.1001/jamapsychiatry.2020.0334>
- Roberts, M. G., & Heesterbeek, J. A. P. (2023). A new method for estimating the effort required to control an infectious disease. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, *270*(1522), 1359-1364. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2003.2339>
- Ross, R. (1911). The prevention of malaria. *John Murray*. (London)
- Satarker, S., & Nampootheri, M. (2020). Structural proteins in severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus-2. *Arch Med Res*, *51*(6), 482-491. Retrieved from <https://www.doi:10.1016/j.arcmed.2020.05.012>

- Smith, G. L., & McFadden, G. (2022). Smallpox: Anything to declare? *Nat. Rev. Immunol.*, *2*, 521–527. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.3390%2Fpathogens10081030>
- Song, W., & Lou, D. J. (2013). Different types of backward bifurcations due to density-dependent treatments. *Math. Biosci. Eng.*, *10*, 1651–1668.
- Tang, B., Wang, X., Li, Q., Bragazzi, N. L., Tang, S., Xiao, Y., & Wu, J. (2020). Estimation of the transmission risk of the 2019-ncov and its implication for public health interventions. *Journal of Clinical Medicine*, *9*(462). Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.3390/jcm9020462>
- Tchoumi, S. Y., Rwezaura, H., & Tchuenche, J. M. (2022). Dynamic of a two-strain covid-19 model with vaccination. *Results in Physics*, *39*(105777). Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rinp.2022.105777>
- Tillett, R., Sevinsky, J. R., Hartley, P. D., Kerwin, H., Crawford, N., Gorzalski, A., ... Pandori, M. (2021). Genomic evidence for reinfection with sars-cov-2: a case study. *Lancet Infect Dis*, *21*(1), 52-58. Retrieved from [https://doi:10.1016/S1473-3099\(20\)30764-7](https://doi:10.1016/S1473-3099(20)30764-7) (Epub 2020 Oct 12, PMID: 33058797; PMCID: PMC7550103)
- Van Den Driessche, P., & Watmough, J. (2002). Reproduction numbers and sub-threshold endemic equilibria for compartmental models of disease transmission. *Mathematical Biosciences*, *180*, 29-48.
- Vangipuram, L., Srinivasa, L., & Anatoly, A. M. (1989). Stability analysis of nonlinear systems. *Marcel Dekker Inc, New York*.
- WHO. (2005). *Statement on the second meeting of the international health regulations*. Retrieved from <https://www.who.int/news-room/detail/30-01-2020>
- WHO. (2019). *Statement on the second meeting of the international health regulations*. Retrieved from [https://www.who.int/news-room/detail/30-01-2020-statement-on-the-second-meeting-of-the-international-health-regulations-\(2005\)-emergency-committee-regarding-the-outbreak-of-novel-coronavirus-\(2019-ncov\)](https://www.who.int/news-room/detail/30-01-2020-statement-on-the-second-meeting-of-the-international-health-regulations-(2005)-emergency-committee-regarding-the-outbreak-of-novel-coronavirus-(2019-ncov))
- WHO. (2020). *Who coronavirus (sars-cov-2) dashboard*. Retrieved from <https://covid19.who.int/> (Accessed:13 November, 2021)
- WHO. (2021). *Latest who disease outbreak news (dons)*. Retrieved from <https://www.who.int/emergencies/disease-outbreak-news/1>

- WIKI. (2023). *Comparative medicine*. Retrieved from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Comparative_medicine (Accessed: October, 2023)
- WIKI. (2024). *Epidemics and pandemics*. Retrieved from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_epidemics_and_pandemics (Accessed: 17, March)
- Worldometer. (2024). *Covid-19 outbreak*. Retrieved from <https://www.worldometers.info/coronavirus/> (Accessed: 17, March)
- Yusuf, T. T., Abidemi, A., Afolabi, A. S., & Dansu, E. J. (2022). Optimal control of the coronavirus pandemic with impacts of implemented control measures. *J. Nig. Soc. Phys. Sci.*, 4, 88–98. Retrieved from <https://www.DOI:10.46481/jnsps.2022.414>
- Zheng, J. (2020). Sars-cov-2: an emerging coronavirus that causes a global threat. , *16*(10), 1678-1685. Retrieved from <https://www.doi:10.7150/ijbs.45053>

APPENDIX A

6.0.1 Numerical Simulation Plots of Optimal Control Model for Each State Variable

This section presents the simulation plots for each control strategy, illustrating their impact on the model compartments.

Figure 6.1: NPI's only control Plots for each State Variable

Figure 6.2: NPI's only control Plots for each State Variable

Figure 6.3: Vaccination only control Plots for each State Variable

Figure 6.4: Vaccination only control Plots for each State Variable

Figure 6.5: Treatment only control Plots for each State Variable

Figure 6.6: Treatment only control Plots for each State Variable

Figure 6.7: Vaccination and NPI's only control Plots for each State Variable

Figure 6.8: Vaccination and NPI's only control Plots for each State Variable

Figure 6.9: Vaccination and Treatment only control Plots for each State Variable

Figure 6.10: Vaccination and Treatment only control Plots for each State Variable

Figure 6.11: NPI's and Treatment only control Plots for each State Variable

Figure 6.12: NPI's and Treatment only control Plots for each State Variable

Figure 6.13: Vaccination, NPI's and Treatment control Plots for each State Variable

Figure 6.14: Vaccination, NPI's and Treatment control Plots for each State Variable

APPENDIX B(i)

A bifurcation analysis and model of Covid-19 transmission dynamics with post-vaccination infection impact

Healthcare Analytics 3 (2023) 100157

A bifurcation analysis and model of Covid-19 transmission dynamics with post-vaccination infection impact

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ARTICLE INFO

Relevant links: <https://www.elsevier.com/locate/healthcareanalytics>

Keywords

Bifurcation analysis
Nonlinear bifurcation
Sensitivity analysis
Coronavirus
Control reproduction number
Bifurcation analysis

ABSTRACT

SARS-CoV-2 (Covid-19) has imposed a monumental socio-economic burden worldwide, and its impact still lingers. We propose a deterministic model to describe the transmission dynamics of Covid-19, emphasizing the effects of vaccination on the prevailing epidemic. The proposed model incorporates current information on Covid-19, such as reinfection, waning of immunity derived from the vaccine, and infectiousness of the pre-symptomatic individuals into the disease dynamics. Moreover, the model analysis reveals that it exhibits the phenomenon of backward bifurcation, thus suggesting that driving the model reproduction number below unity may not suffice to drive the epidemic toward extinction. The model is fitted to real-life data to estimate values for some of the unknown parameters. In addition, the model epidemic threshold and equilibria are determined while the criteria for the stability of each equilibrium solution are established using the Metzler approach. A sensitivity analysis of the model is performed based on the Latin Hypercube Sampling (LHS) and Partial Rank Correlation Coefficients (PRCCs) approaches to illustrate the impact of the various model parameters and explore the dependency of control reproduction number on its constituent parameters, which invariably gives insight on what needs to be done to contain the pandemic effectively. The foregoing notwithstanding, the contour plots of the control reproduction number concerning some of the salient parameters indicate that increasing vaccination coverage and decreasing vaccine waning rate would remarkably reduce the value of the reproduction number below unity, thus facilitating the possible elimination of the disease from the population. Finally, the model is solved numerically and simulated for different scenarios of disease outbreaks with the findings discussed.

1. Introduction

Infectious disease modelling is a common tool used in studying the spread of communicable diseases, forecasting the future course of a disease outbreak, and evaluating strategies for controlling an epidemic [1]. Over the years, infectious disease agents like viruses, bacteria, fungi, protozoa, and helminths have caused several diseases which have invaded the world resulting into a number of disease outbreaks [2]. Some of the recent ones are Ebola, Swine flu, Zika virus, Dengue fever, Yellow fever, MERS-CoV, Monkey Pox, and more recently, Coronavirus (COVID-19) which wreaked havoc on the entire world.

Towards the end of year 2019, the emergence of Coronavirus sprung a sudden and disastrous outbreak across countries of the world causing several deaths and economy lock-down in many countries across the globe. The outbreak of Coronavirus was first recorded in China, precisely in Wuhan, Hubei province, on December 31, 2019 [3,4]. Few days after, on 30th January, 2020 about 267,736 persons were confirmed

infected with the virus and 12,167 suspected cases were reported in China while 82 persons were confirmed in 18 other countries. In the same day, World Health Organization declared the SARS-CoV-2 (COVID-19) outbreak as a Public Health Emergency of International Concern (PHEIC) [5-8]. As at 10th of November 2022, the pandemic has resulted into 639,023,177 confirmed cases and 6,610,754 deaths globally [9,10], while in Nigeria a total of 264,136 confirmed cases with 3155 deaths has been reported [11]. Due to the outbreak of Coronavirus, several policies and Non-Pharmaceutical Intervention (NPI) measures have been proposed and implemented globally ranging from contact tracing, washing of hands, social distancing, lock down, isolation, wearing of face mask, and recently, administration of vaccine to curtail the disease incidence and its spread [8,12]. Coronavirus is an enveloped and positive-sense single-stranded RNA (+ssRNA) virus which can be transmitted to an individual via direct contact with contaminated surface or droplets produced from the respiratory system of infected persons [8]. The transmission of the disease occur often during coughing or sneezing, and through inhalation of respiratory droplets

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.health.2023.100157>

Received 20 December 2022; Received in revised form 1 March 2023; Accepted 4 March 2023

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Figure 6.15: Single Strain Model Published

APPENDIX B(ii)

Optimal Control Strategies for Dual-Strain SARS-CoV-2 Dynamics with Cost-Effectiveness Analysis

Article

Optimal Control Strategies for Dual-Strain SARS-CoV-2 Dynamics with Cost-Effectiveness Analysis

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Abstract: This study investigates optimal intervention strategies for controlling the spread of two co-circulating strains of SARS-CoV-2 within the Nigerian population. A newly formulated epidemiological model captures the transmission dynamics of the dual-strain system and incorporates three key control mechanisms: vaccination, non-pharmaceutical interventions (NPIs), and therapeutic treatment. To identify the most effective approach, Pontryagin's Maximum Principle is employed, enabling the derivation of an optimal control function that minimizes both infection rates and associated implementation costs. Through numerical simulations, this study evaluates the performance of individual, paired, and combined intervention strategies. Additionally, a cost-effectiveness assessment based on the Incremental Cost-Effectiveness Ratio (ICER) framework highlights the most economically viable option, while results suggest that the combined application of vaccination and treatment strategies offers superior control over dual-strain transmission and implementing all three strategies together ensures the most robust suppression of the outbreak.

Keywords: optimal control; SARS-CoV-2; dual strain; endemicity; transmission dynamics; vaccination; NPIs; effective treatment

Academic Editor: Simone Bragi

Received: 20 April 2025

Revised: 16 May 2025

Accepted: 19 May 2025

Published: 1 June 2025

Citation: Ididi, O.I.; Yusuf, T.T.; Owolabi, K.M.; Oshinubi, K. Optimal Control Strategies for Dual-Strain SARS-CoV-2 Dynamics with Cost-Effectiveness Analysis. *Computation* **2025**, *13*, 135. <https://doi.org/10.3390/computation13060135>

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1. Introduction

Optimal Control Theory (OCT) is a foundational area of mathematical optimization that seeks to determine control strategies for dynamic systems in order to achieve specific objectives—often minimizing cost or maximizing system efficiency. Its origins trace back to the early 1950s, evolving from the calculus of variations, which focused on optimizing functionals over time. A major breakthrough was the introduction of Pontryagin's Maximum Principle by Lev Pontryagin in 1956, providing necessary conditions for optimality analogous to the Euler-Lagrange equations in variational calculus. Around the same period, Richard Bellman's development of dynamic programming laid the foundation for the Hamilton-Jacobi-Bellman (HJB) equation, a pivotal tool in solving optimal control problems [1–3]. During the 1970s and 1980s, OCT expanded significantly across various disciplines, including economics, engineering, and the life sciences, supported by advances in numerical methods. The theory has since grown to address stochastic systems influenced by randomness and robust systems characterized by uncertainty. In epidemiology, OCT plays a vital role in the formulation of adaptive strategies to mitigate infectious disease outbreaks. It incorporates parameters such as intervention cost, transmission rate, and limited healthcare resources to determine time-dependent policies that optimize both health outcomes and cost-efficiency [4].

APPENDIX C

Matlab code for COVID-19 single strain model with post vaccination Parameter Fitting

```
1 % PHD1parameterfitting.m
% This function estimates model parameters by fitting them to COVID
  -19 prevalence data.

function [Lambda, m, alpha, gamma, rho, theta, delta1, delta2, ...
        psi1, psi2, psi3, phi, tau, sigma1, beta1, w, s, eta, ...
6         epsilon, mu] = PHD1parameterfitting

    warning off;

    % Data preparation (NCDC data example)
11    P_Data(:,1) = 1:147; % Time (days)
    P_Data(:,2) = [2 2 2 2 2 2 2 2 3 8 8 12 22 30 40 44 51 65 70 ...
        89 111 131 135 174 184 210 214 232 238 254 276 288 305 ...
        318 323 343 373 407 442 493 542 627 665 665 873 981 ...
        1095 1182 1273 1337 1532 1728 1932 2170 2388 2558 2802 ...
16        2950 3145 3526 3912 4151 4399 4641 4787 4971 5162 5450 ...
        5621 5959 6175 6401 6677 7016 7261 7526 7839 8068 8344 ...
        8733 8915 9302 9855 10162 10578 10819 11166 11516 ...
        11844 12233 12486 12801 13464 13873 14554 15181 15682 ...
        16085 16658 17148 17735 18480 19147 19808 20244 20919 ...
21        21371 22020 22614 23298 24077 24567 25133 25694 26484 ...
        27110 27564 28167 28711 29286 29789 30249 30748 31323 ...
        31987 32558 33153 33616 34259 34854 35454 36107 36663 ...
        37225 37801 38344 38948 39539 39977 40532 41180 41804 ...
        42208 42689 43151 43537 43841]./100; % Normalize

26    % Initial parameter values
    Lambda = 13942;
    m = 0.9;
    alpha = 0.855;
31    gamma = 1/5.2;
    rho = 0.7010;
    theta = 0.56;
    delta1 = 0.0161;
    delta2 = 0.210;
36    psi1 = 0.142;
    psi2 = 0.0142;
    psi3 = 0.0714;
    phi = 0.0100;
```

```

tau = 1.4211;
41 sigma1 = 3.913;
beta1 = 5.913;
w = 0.016;
s = 0.05;
eta = 1;
46 epsilon = 3;
mu = 0.0114;

% Derived parameters
beta = beta1 * (1 - w - s);
51 sigma = sigma1 * (1 - w - s);
k1 = gamma + mu;
k2 = psi1 + mu;
k3 = psi2 + delta1 + tau + mu;
k4 = psi3 + delta2 + mu;

56 % Initial population compartments
S0 = 211400691;
V0 = 0;
E0 = 11;
61 IA0 = 0;
IS0 = 2;
H0 = 0;
R0 = 0;
INITIAL = [S0, V0, E0, IA0, IS0, H0, R0];

66 % Simulation time range
Istart = 1;
Iend = Istart + 147;

71 % ODE solver options
OPTIONS = odeset('AbsTol',0.001,'RelTol',0.001,'MaxStep',1/52);

% Parameter estimation setup
do_estimation = 1;
76 if do_estimation
    xdata = P_Data(:,1);
    ydata = P_Data(:,2)';
    % Initial guesses
    x0 = [15245 0.6 0.855 1/5.2 0.07010 0.10 0.015 ...
81         0.025 1/7 1/7 1/14 0.00200 0.4211 0.000213 ...
         0.00004213 0.0016 0.0005 0.00432 0.00411 0.0114];
    % Parameter bounds
    LB = [13942 0.1 0.0043 1/14 0.0600 0.01 0.000999 ...
86         0.000121 1/7 1/7 1/14 0.0345 0.0343 0.0529 ...
         0.0529 0.0013 0.04 0.034 0.0056 0.0014];

```

```

        UB = [20000 2 3 1/3 3 0.5 5 5 1/7 1/7 1/14 1 ...
              3 5 5 1 1 1 1 1];
        % Least squares fit
        [x, ~, residual, ~, ~] = lsqcurvefit(@Model8_Inc, x0, xdata,
91 ydata, LB, UB, optimset);
        % Update parameters
        Lambda = x(1);
        m = x(2);
        alpha = x(3);
        gamma = x(4);
96 rho = x(5);
        theta = x(6);
        delta1 = x(7);
        delta2 = x(8);
        psi1 = x(9);
101 psi2 = x(10);
        psi3 = x(11);
        phi = x(12);
        tau = x(13);
        sigma1 = x(14);
106 beta1 = x(15);
        w = x(16);
        s = x(17);
        eta = x(18);
        epsilon = x(19);
111 mu = x(20);

end

        % Model simulation
        [t, y] = ode45(@covidfitbehaviour, [0:1/52:(Iend-Istart)],
INITIAL);
116 incidence = y(:,4) + y(:,5) + y(:,6);

        % Plot results
        figure(1);
        hold on;
121 plot(Istart + t, incidence, 'k-', 'LineWidth', 3);
        plot(P_Data(:,1), P_Data(:,2), 'ro', 'MarkerSize', 6, 'LineWidth'
, 2);
        box off;
        axis([Istart Iend 0 4]);
        ylim([0 500]);
126 title('Covid-19 Prevalence (%)');
        ax = gca;
        ax.XTick = [1 25 50 75 110 147];
        ax.XTickLabel = {'Mar_{03}', 'Apr_{27}', 'May_{21}', 'Jun_{28}',
Jul_{21}', 'Aug_{09}'};

```

```

    legend({'Fitted Curve','NCDC Data'}, 'FontSize',8,'FontWeight','
bold','Location','northwest');
131  xlabel('NCDC DAY','FontSize',11);
    ylabel('Cumulative Number of Covid-19 Cases','FontSize',12);
    ax.XTickLabelRotation = -45;
    hold off;

136  % Residual plot
    figure();
    plot(xdata, residual, 'b-', 'LineWidth', 2);
    ax = gca;
    ax.XTick = [0 25 50 75 110 147];
141  ax.XTickLabel = {'Mar_{03}','Apr_{27}','May_{21}','Jun_{28}','
Jul_{21}','Aug_{09}'};
    xlabel('NCDC WEEK','FontSize',11);
    ylabel('Residual','FontSize',12);
    ax.XTickLabelRotation = -45;
end

146  % Nested ODE function
function ydot = covidfitbehaviour(~, y)
    % Unpack state variables
    S = y(1); V = y(2); E = y(3); IA = y(4); IS = y(5); H = y(6); R =
y(7);
151  ydot = [
        Lambda + m*R + alpha*V - S*(beta*(IA + eta*IS + epsilon*H)/(
sum(y))) - (mu + rho)*S;
        rho*S - V*(sigma*(IA + eta*IS + epsilon*H)/(sum(y))) - V*(
alpha + mu);
        S*(beta*(IA + eta*IS + epsilon*H)/(sum(y))) + V*(sigma*(IA +
eta*IS + epsilon*H)/(sum(y))) - k1*E;
        gamma*(1 - theta)*E - (k2 + phi)*IA;
156  gamma*theta*E + phi*IA - k3*IS;
        tau*IS - k4*H;
        psi1*IA + psi2*IS + psi3*H - (m + mu)*R
    ];
end

161  % Incidence model for parameter fitting
function Inc = Model8_Inc(x0, xdata)
    % Unpack parameters
    Lambda = x0(1);
166  m = x0(2);
    alpha = x0(3);
    gamma = x0(4);
    rho = x0(5);
    theta = x0(6);

```

```

171   delta1 = x0(7);
      delta2 = x0(8);
      psi1 = x0(9);
      psi2 = x0(10);
      psi3 = x0(11);
176   phi = x0(12);
      tau = x0(13);
      sigma1 = x0(14);
      beta1 = x0(15);
      w = x0(16);
181   s = x0(17);
      eta = x0(18);
      epsilon = x0(19);
      mu = x0(20);

186   beta = beta1 * (1 - w - s);
      sigma = sigma1 * (1 - w - s);
      k1 = gamma + mu;
      k2 = psi1 + mu;
      k3 = psi2 + delta1 + tau + mu;
191   k4 = psi3 + delta2 + mu;

      % Initial conditions
      S0 = 211400691;
      V0 = 0;
196   E0 = 11;
      IA0 = 0;
      IS0 = 1;
      H0 = 0;
      R0 = 0;
201   INITIAL = [S0, V0, E0, IA0, IS0, H0, R0];

      [t, y] = ode45(@covidfitbehaviour, [0:1/52:(max(xdata)-1)],
INITIAL);

      % Calculate incidence
206   Inc = zeros(1, length(xdata));
      for j = 1:length(xdata)
          ind = find((xdata(j)-1) == t);
          if ~isempty(ind)
              IA = y(ind,4);
211             IS = y(ind,5);
              H = y(ind,6);
              Inc(j) = IA + IS + H;
          else
              Inc(j) = NaN;
216   end

```

```
end
end
```

Matlab code for COVID-19 single strain model with Post Vaccination (Model Simulation)

```
clc;
2 test=-1; delta1=0.001; h=1.2;
x=0:h:120;
x1=zeros(1,length(x)); x2=x1; x3=x1;
x4=x1; x5=x1; x6=x1; x7=x1;
N=211400703; Lambda=13942; m=0.1002;
7 alpha=1; gamma=0.0715; rho=0.25;
theta=0.5; d1=0.015; d2=0.025;
psi1=0.1429; psi2=0.1429; psi3=0.0714;
phi=0; tau=0.1343; eta=0.5177;
epsilon=0.0118; mu=0.00699;
12 beta=1.2087; sigma=1.2089;
K1=gamma+mu; K2=psi1+mu;
K3=psi2+d1+tau+mu; K4=psi3+d2+mu;
R0=(gamma*(beta*(mu+alpha)+rho*sigma)*...
(K3*K4*(1-theta)+eta*K4*(K2*theta+phi)+tau*epsilon*(K2*theta+phi))
/...
17 (K1*K3*K4*(mu+alpha+rho)*(K2*theta+phi));

x1(1)=167397517; x2(1)=33932169; x3(1)=5036813;
x4(1)=2390571; x5(1)=2390571; x6(1)=2653; x7(1)=249874;

22 F_xyz=@(x,x1,x2,x3,x4,x5,x6,x7) ...
(Lambda+m*x7+alpha*x2-(beta*(x4+eta*x5+epsilon*x6)*x1)/(sum([x1,x2,x3
,x4,x5,x6,x7]))-(mu+rho)*x1);
G_xyz=@(x,x1,x2,x3,x4,x5,x6,x7) ...
(rho*x1-(sigma*(x4+eta*x5+epsilon*x6)*x2)/(sum([x1,x2,x3,x4,x5,x6,x7
]))-(mu+alpha)*x2);
H_xyz=@(x,x1,x2,x3,x4,x5,x6,x7) ...
27 ((beta*(x4+eta*x5+epsilon*x6)*x1)/(sum([x1,x2,x3,x4,x5,x6,x7]))+ ...
(sigma*(x4+eta*x5+epsilon*x6)*x2)/(sum([x1,x2,x3,x4,x5,x6,x7]))-K1*x3
);
S_xyz=@(x,x1,x2,x3,x4,x5,x6,x7) (gamma*(1-theta)*x3-(K2+phi)*x4);
J_xyz=@(x,x1,x2,x3,x4,x5,x6,x7) (theta*gamma*x3+phi*x4-K3*x5);
M_xyz=@(x,x1,x2,x3,x4,x5,x6,x7) (tau*x5-K4*x6);
32 O_xyz=@(x,x1,x2,x3,x4,x5,x6,x7) (psi1*x4+psi2*x5+psi3*x6-(mu+m)*x7);

while(test<0)
oldx1=x1; oldx2=x2; oldx3=x3;
```

```

oldx4=x4; oldx5=x5; oldx6=x6; oldx7=x7;
37 for i=1:(length(x)-1)
k1=F_xyz(x(i),x1(i),x2(i),x3(i),x4(i),x5(i),x6(i),x7(i));
L1=G_xyz(x(i),x1(i),x2(i),x3(i),x4(i),x5(i),x6(i),x7(i));
P1=H_xyz(x(i),x1(i),x2(i),x3(i),x4(i),x5(i),x6(i),x7(i));
R1=S_xyz(x(i),x1(i),x2(i),x3(i),x4(i),x5(i),x6(i),x7(i));
42 W1=J_xyz(x(i),x1(i),x2(i),x3(i),x4(i),x5(i),x6(i),x7(i));
V1=M_xyz(x(i),x1(i),x2(i),x3(i),x4(i),x5(i),x6(i),x7(i));
O1=O_xyz(x(i),x1(i),x2(i),x3(i),x4(i),x5(i),x6(i),x7(i));

k2=F_xyz(x(i)+0.5*h,x1(i)+0.5*h*k1,...);
47 L2=G_xyz(x(i)+0.5*h,x1(i)+0.5*h*k1,...);
P2=H_xyz(x(i)+0.5*h,x1(i)+0.5*h*k1,...);
R2=S_xyz(x(i)+0.5*h,x1(i)+0.5*h*k1,...);
W2=J_xyz(x(i)+0.5*h,x1(i)+0.5*h*k1,...);
V2=M_xyz(x(i)+0.5*h,x1(i)+0.5*h*k1,...);
52 O2=O_xyz(x(i)+0.5*h,x1(i)+0.5*h*k1,...);

k3=F_xyz(x(i)+0.5*h,x1(i)+0.5*h*k2,...);
L3=G_xyz(x(i)+0.5*h,x1(i)+0.5*h*k2,...);
P3=H_xyz(x(i)+0.5*h,x1(i)+0.5*h*k2,...);
57 R3=S_xyz(x(i)+0.5*h,x1(i)+0.5*h*k2,...);
W3=J_xyz(x(i)+0.5*h,x1(i)+0.5*h*k2,...);
V3=M_xyz(x(i)+0.5*h,x1(i)+0.5*h*k2,...);
O3=O_xyz(x(i)+0.5*h,x1(i)+0.5*h*k2,...);

62 k4=F_xyz(x(i)+h,x1(i)+k3*h,...);
L4=G_xyz(x(i)+h,x1(i)+k3*h,...);
P4=H_xyz(x(i)+h,x1(i)+k3*h,...);
R4=S_xyz(x(i)+h,x1(i)+k3*h,...);
W4=J_xyz(x(i)+h,x1(i)+k3*h,...);
67 V4=M_xyz(x(i)+h,x1(i)+k3*h,...);
O4=O_xyz(x(i)+h,x1(i)+k3*h,...);

x1(i+1)=x1(i)+(1/6)*(k1+2*k2+2*k3+k4)*h;
x2(i+1)=x2(i)+(1/6)*(L1+2*L2+2*L3+L4)*h;
72 x3(i+1)=x3(i)+(1/6)*(P1+2*P2+2*P3+P4)*h;
x4(i+1)=x4(i)+(1/6)*(R1+2*R2+2*R3+R4)*h;
x5(i+1)=x5(i)+(1/6)*(W1+2*W2+2*W3+W4)*h;
x6(i+1)=x6(i)+(1/6)*(V1+2*V2+2*V3+V4)*h;
x7(i+1)=x7(i)+(1/6)*(O1+2*O2+2*O3+O4)*h;
77 end
temp1=delta1*sum(abs(x1))-sum(abs(oldx1-x1));
temp2=delta1*sum(abs(x2))-sum(abs(oldx2-x2));
temp3=delta1*sum(abs(x3))-sum(abs(oldx3-x3));
temp4=delta1*sum(abs(x4))-sum(abs(oldx4-x4));
82 temp5=delta1*sum(abs(x5))-sum(abs(oldx5-x5));

```

```

temp6=delta1*sum(abs(x6))-sum(abs(oldd6-x6));
temp7=delta1*sum(abs(x7))-sum(abs(oldd7-x7));
test=min([temp6,temp7,temp4,temp5]);
end
87
y(1,:)=x; y(2,:)=x1; y(3,:)=x2; y(4,:)=x3;
y(5,:)=x4; y(6,:)=x5; y(7,:)=x6; y(8,:)=x7;

%plot(x,x2,'-r','linewidth',1.5);
92 %legend('V','location','northeast');
%xlabel('Time (years)');
%ylabel('Population (millions)');
%title('CO-INFECTION');
%grid on;
97 %hold on;
%plot(x,x4,'linewidth',3);
%legend('I_a','location','northeast');

```

Matlab Code for single COVID-19 Strain Model (Contour plots)

```

1 clc
clear
close

% Parameters
6 Lambda = 13942; % Recruitment rate
m = 0.1002; % Mortality rate
alpha = 1.0000; % Progression rate
gamma = 0.0715; % Recovery rate
theta = 0.5000; % Treatment rate
11 d1 = 0.0150; % Disease-induced death rate (compartment 1)
d2 = 0.0250; % Disease-induced death rate (compartment 2)
psi1 = 0.1429; % Transfer rate from E1
psi2 = 0.1429; % Transfer rate from E2
psi3 = 0.0714; % Transfer rate from E3
16 phi = 1.0000; % Progression parameter
tau = 0.1343; % Treatment success rate
eta = 0.5177; % Contact rate
epsilon = 0.0118; % Treatment failure rate
mu = 0.006990; % Natural death rate
21 beta = 0.2124; % Transmission rate

% Intermediate calculations
K1 = (gamma + mu);
K2 = (psi1 + mu);
26 K3 = (psi2 + d1 + tau + mu);

```

```

K4 = (psi3 + d2 + mu);

% Meshgrid for sigma and rho
[sigma, rho] = meshgrid(0.0:0.02:1, 0.0:0.02:1);
31
% Basic reproduction number R0
Ro = (gamma .* (beta .* (mu + alpha) + rho .* sigma) .* ...
      (K3 .* K4 .* (1 - theta) + eta .* K4 .* (K2 .* theta + phi) +
      ...
      tau .* epsilon .* (K2 .* theta + phi))) ...
36 ./ (K1 .* K3 .* K4 .* (mu + alpha + rho) .* (K2 .* theta + phi))
;

% Plot contour
contourf(sigma, rho, Ro, 'ShowText', 'on', 'LineWidth', 1.5);
colorbar;

```

Listing 6.1: MATLAB code for plotting R_0 against σ and ρ

Matlab Code for Dual COVID-19 Strain Model Simulation

```

test = -1; delta1 = 0.001; h = 0.2; x = 0:h:20;
x1 = zeros(1, length(x)); x2 = zeros(1, length(x)); x3 = zeros(1, length
(x));
x4 = zeros(1, length(x)); x5 = zeros(1, length(x)); x6 = zeros(1, length
(x));
x7 = zeros(1, length(x)); x8 = zeros(1, length(x));
5
% Parameters
Pi=13942; gamma1=0.4715; gamma2=0.4715; psi1=0.1429; psi2=0.1429;
psi3=0.0714; theta=0.5; m=0.2726; alpha=0.9973; rho=0.1083; del1
=0.2843;
delta2=0.3310; delta12=0.4131; delta21=0.4131; tau1=0.4951; tau2
=0.0096;
10 sigma=0.5; beta1=4.6935; beta2=4.1196; epsilon1=0.4750; epsilon2
=0.3715; mu=0.5085;

k1=gamma1+mu; k2=tau1+delta12+psi1+mu; k3=gamma2+mu; k4=tau2+delta21+
psi2+mu; k5=psi3+delta21+delta12+mu;

R_1=beta1*gamma1*(rho*sigma+alpha+mu)*(tau1*epsilon1+(psi3+delta12+mu
))/ (k1*k2*(psi3+delta12+mu)*(alpha+mu+rho));
15 R_2=beta2*gamma2*(rho*sigma+alpha+mu)*(tau2*epsilon2+(psi3+delta21+mu
))/ (k3*k4*(psi3+delta21+mu)*(alpha+mu+rho));

N=218541216;

```

```

x1(1)=N*0.91; x2(1)=N*0.02; x3(1)=N*0.027; x4(1)=N*0.0008;
x5(1)=N*0.027; x6(1)=N*0.00036; x7(1)=N*0.00007; x8(1)=N*0.001;
20
F_xyz=@(x,x1,x2,x3,x4,x5,x6,x7,x8) Pi+m*x8 - ((beta1*(x4+epsilon1*x7)
+beta2*(x6+epsilon2*x7))/sum([x1,x2,x3,x4,x5,x6,x7,x8]))*x1 +
alpha*x2 - (rho+mu)*x1;
G_xyz=@(x,x1,x2,x3,x4,x5,x6,x7,x8) rho*x1 - sigma*((beta1*(x4+
epsilon1*x7)+beta2*(x6+epsilon2*x7))/sum([x1,x2,x3,x4,x5,x6,x7,x8
]))*x2 - (alpha+mu)*x2;
H_xyz=@(x,x1,x2,x3,x4,x5,x6,x7,x8) ((beta1*(x4+epsilon1*x7))/sum([x1,
x2,x3,x4,x5,x6,x7,x8]))*(x1+sigma*x2) - (gamma1+mu)*x3;
S_xyz=@(x,x1,x2,x3,x4,x5,x6,x7,x8) gamma1*x3 - (tau1+dell1+psi1+mu)*x4
;
25 J_xyz=@(x,x1,x2,x3,x4,x5,x6,x7,x8) ((beta2*(x6+epsilon2*x7))/sum([x1,
x2,x3,x4,x5,x6,x7,x8]))*(x1+sigma*x2) - (gamma2+mu)*x5;
P_xyz=@(x,x1,x2,x3,x4,x5,x6,x7,x8) gamma2*x5 - (tau2+delta2+psi2+mu)*
x6;
Q_xyz=@(x,x1,x2,x3,x4,x5,x6,x7,x8) tau1*x4 + tau2*x6 - (psi3+mu+
delta12+delta21)*x7;
R_xyz=@(x,x1,x2,x3,x4,x5,x6,x7,x8) psi1*x4 + psi2*x6 + psi3*x7 - (m+
mu)*x8;
30 while(test<0)
oldx1=x1; oldx2=x2; oldx3=x3; oldx4=x4; oldx5=x5; oldx6=x6; oldx7=
x7; oldx8=x8;
for i=1:length(x)-1
k1_1=F_xyz(x(i),x1(i),x2(i),x3(i),x4(i),x5(i),x6(i),x7(i),x8(i));
k2_1=G_xyz(x(i),x1(i),x2(i),x3(i),x4(i),x5(i),x6(i),x7(i),x8(i));
35 k3_1=H_xyz(x(i),x1(i),x2(i),x3(i),x4(i),x5(i),x6(i),x7(i),x8(i));
k4_1=S_xyz(x(i),x1(i),x2(i),x3(i),x4(i),x5(i),x6(i),x7(i),x8(i));
k5_1=J_xyz(x(i),x1(i),x2(i),x3(i),x4(i),x5(i),x6(i),x7(i),x8(i));
k6_1=P_xyz(x(i),x1(i),x2(i),x3(i),x4(i),x5(i),x6(i),x7(i),x8(i));
k7_1=Q_xyz(x(i),x1(i),x2(i),x3(i),x4(i),x5(i),x6(i),x7(i),x8(i));
40 k8_1=R_xyz(x(i),x1(i),x2(i),x3(i),x4(i),x5(i),x6(i),x7(i),x8(i));
x1(i+1)=x1(i)+h*k1_1; x2(i+1)=x2(i)+h*k2_1; x3(i+1)=x3(i)+h*k3_1;
x4(i+1)=x4(i)+h*k4_1;
x5(i+1)=x5(i)+h*k5_1; x6(i+1)=x6(i)+h*k6_1; x7(i+1)=x7(i)+h*k7_1;
x8(i+1)=x8(i)+h*k8_1;
end
test=test+1;
45 end

figure;
plot(x,x1,'b','LineWidth',2); hold on;
plot(x,x2,'r','LineWidth',2); plot(x,x3,'g','LineWidth',2);
50 plot(x,x4,'k','LineWidth',2); plot(x,x5,'m','LineWidth',2);
plot(x,x6,'c','LineWidth',2); plot(x,x7,'y','LineWidth',2);

```

```

plot(x,x8,'k--','LineWidth',2);
xlabel('Time'); ylabel('Population');
legend('S','V','E1','I1','E2','I2','H','R');
55 title('Dynamics of the System');
grid on;

```

Matlab code for dual Strain COVID-19 Optimal Control Model (Simulation)

```

function [T, X, U, Lambda, flag] = OptimalControl_PhD0ke4a(
    control_switch)
    % This function computes the optimal control and the
    % corresponding solution using forward-backward sweep
    % Always run compute the output of this file by running
4    % OptimallControlMainFile.
    test = -1;
    delta = 0.001; %set tolerance
    N = 1000; %number of subdivisions
    Time = 100; %timespan
9    T = linspace(0,Time,N+1);
    k = Time/N; %step
    %%
    % Assigning bounds to each of the control variables
    ulmax = 1; u2max = 1; u3max = 1;
14    % Pre-allocating memory space for control variables
    U = zeros(3, N + 1);
    % Pre-allocating memory space for states variables
    X = zeros(8, N+1);
    % Setting the initial coditions for the state variable
19    P1=218541216;
    X(:, 1) = P1*[0.605389443, 0.000147656, 0.125507567,
    0.059062385,...
                0.199335548, 0.002657807, 0.000516796,
    0.007382798];
    % Pre-allocating memory space for adjoint variables
    Lambda = zeros(8, N+1);
24    Pi = 13920; gamma_1= 0.04715; gamma_2= 0.04715; psi_1 = 0.1429;
    psi_2 = 0.1429;
    varepsilon = 0.02726; alpha = 0.8973; d_1 = 0.002843;
    d_2= 0.003310; d_12= 0.004131; tau_1= 0.2954; tau_2= 0.0096;
    d_21= 0.004131; sigma = 0.4685; beta_1 = 4.6935; beta_2 =
    4.1196;
29    epsilon_1= 0.04750; epsilon_2= 0.3715; mu= 0.0015; rho=0.2;
    psi_3 = 0.0429;

```

```

% beta_1 = 10.6935; beta_2 = 10.1196; % this is just for
visualization
kol = gamma_1 + mu; k22 = tau_1 + d_12 + psi_1 + mu; k3 = gamma_2
+ mu;
k4 = tau_2 + d_21 + psi_2 + mu ; %k5 = psi_3 + delta_21 + delta_12
+ mu;
R_10 = beta_1*gamma_1*(rho*sigma + alpha + mu)*(tau_1.*epsilon_1
+...
34      (psi_3 + d_12 + mu))/(kol*k22*(psi_3 + d_12 + mu)*(alpha +
mu + rho));
R_20 = beta_2.*gamma_2.*(rho.*sigma + alpha + mu).*(tau_2.*
epsilon_2 +...
      (psi_3 + d_21 + mu))./(k3.*k4.*(psi_3 + d_21 + mu).*(alpha
+ mu + rho));
%Define your Weight
w1=10; w2=20; w3=20; w4=40; kappa1=6000; kappa2=6000; kappa3
=6000;% kappa4 = 5000; %kappa5 = 6000; % kappa are Cost function
39 w1=10; w2=20; w3=20; w4=40; kappa1=1200; kappa2=9000; kappa3
=12000;% kappa4 = 5000; %kappa5 = 6000; % kappa are Cost function
function dy = dxdt(t, x, T, U)
u = interp1(T, U', t)';
u1 = u(1); u2 = u(2); u3 = u(3); % u4 = u(4); u5 = u(5);
S = x(1); V = x(2); E_1 = x(3); I_1 = x(4); E_2 = x(5); I_2 =
x(6); H = x(7); R = x(8);
44 Total = S + V + E_1 + I_1 + E_2 + I_2 + H + R;
dy = [Pi + varepsilon*R - ((beta_1*(I_1 + epsilon_1*H))./
Total + (beta_2*(I_2 + epsilon_2*H)./Total))*S*(1-u2) + alpha*V -
(u1 + mu)*S;
      u1*S - ((beta_1*(I_1 + epsilon_1*H))./Total + (beta_2*(
I_2 + epsilon_2*H)./Total))*(V*sigma)*(1-u2) - (alpha + mu)*V;
      (S + sigma*V)*(1-u2)*(beta_1*(I_1 + epsilon_1*H)./Total
) - (gamma_1 + mu)*E_1;
      gamma_1*E_1 - (tau_1 + d_1 + psi_1 + mu)*I_1;
49      (S + sigma*V)*(beta_2*(I_2 + epsilon_2*H)./Total)*(1-u2
) - (gamma_2 + mu)*E_2;
      gamma_2*E_2 - (tau_2 + d_2 + psi_2 + mu)*I_2;
      tau_1*I_1 + tau_2*I_2 - (u3 + mu + d_12 + d_21)*H;
      psi_1*I_1 + psi_2*I_2 + u3*H - (varepsilon + mu)*R];
end
54 function dlambd = dldt(t, lambda, T, U, X)
x = interp1(T, X', t)';
S = x(1); V = x(2); E_1 = x(3); I_1 = x(4); E_2 = x(5); I_2 =
x(6); H = x(7); R = x(8);
Total = S + V + E_1 + I_1 + E_2 + I_2 + H + R;
u = interp1(T, U', t)';
59 u1 = u(1); u2 = u(2); u3 = u(3); % u4 = u(4); u5 = u(5);

```

```

        lambda1 = lambda(1); lambda2 = lambda(2); lambda3 = lambda(3)
; lambda4 = lambda(4);
        lambda5 = lambda(5); lambda6 = lambda(6); lambda7 = lambda(7)
; lambda8 = lambda(8);
        dlambd = [-(w1 + lambda1*(-(beta_1*(H*epsilon_1 + I_1)./
Total^2 - beta_2*(H*epsilon_2 + I_2)./Total^2)*S*(1-u2) ...
        - (beta_1*(H*epsilon_1+I_1)./Total + beta_2*(H*
epsilon_2 + I_2)./Total)*(1-u2) - u1 - mu) ...
64         + lambda2*(u1-(1-u2)*sigma*(-beta_1*(H*epsilon_1 +
I_1)./Total^2 - beta_2*(H*epsilon_2 + I_2)./Total^2)*V)...
        + lambda3*((1-u2)*beta_1*(H*epsilon_1+I_1)./Total
- (V*sigma + S)*(1-u2)*beta_1*(H*epsilon_1 + I_1)./Total^2)...
        + lambda5*((1-u2)*beta_2*(H*epsilon_2 + I_2)./
Total - (V*sigma + S)*(1-u2)*beta_2*(H*epsilon_2 + I_2)./Total^2)
;
        -(lambda1*(-(beta_1*(H*epsilon_1 + I_1)./Total^2
- beta_2*(H*epsilon_2+I_2)./Total^2)*S*(1-u2) + alpha)...
        + lambda2*(-sigma*(1-u2)*(-beta_1*(H*epsilon_1+I_1
)./Total^2 - beta_2*(H*epsilon_2+I_2)./Total^2)*V ...
69         - sigma*(1-u2)*(beta_1*(H*epsilon_1+I_1)./Total +
beta_2*(H*epsilon_2+I_2)./Total) - alpha - mu) ...
        + lambda3*(sigma*(1-u2)*beta_1*(H*epsilon_1+I_1)./
Total - (V*sigma +S)*(1-u2)*beta_1*(H*epsilon_1+I_1)./Total^2) ...
        + lambda5*((1-u2)*sigma*beta_2*(H*epsilon_2 + I_2)
./Total - (V*sigma + S)*(1-u2)*beta_2*(H*epsilon_2+I_2)./Total^2)
;
        -(-lambda1*(-beta_1*(H*epsilon_1+I_1)./Total^2 -
beta_2*(H*epsilon_2+I_2)./Total^2)*S*(1-u2)...
        - lambda2*sigma*(1-u2)*(-beta_1*(H*epsilon_1+I_1)
./Total^2 - beta_2*(H*epsilon_2+I_2)./Total^2)*V ...
74         + lambda3*(-(V*sigma + S)*(1-u2)*beta_1*(H*
epsilon_1+I_1)./Total^2 - gamma_1- mu) + lambda4*gamma_1...
        - lambda5*(V*sigma + S)*(1-u2)*beta_2*(H*epsilon_2
+ I_2)./Total^2);
        -(w2 - lambda1*(beta_1./Total - beta_1*(H*
epsilon_1 + I_1)./Total^2 - beta_2*(H*epsilon_2 + I_2)./Total^2)*S
*(1-u2) ...
        - lambda2*sigma*(1-u2)*(beta_1./Total - beta_1*(H*
epsilon_1 + I_1)./Total^2 - beta_2*(H*epsilon_2 + I_2)./Total^2)*V
...
        - lambda3*(beta_1*(H*epsilon_1 + I_1)./Total) +
lambda4*(tau_1 + d_1 + psi_1 + mu) ...
79         - lambda7*tau_1 - lambda8*psi_1);
        -(-lambda1*(beta_2./Total - beta_2*(H*epsilon_2 +
I_2)./Total^2)*S*(1-u2) ...
        - lambda2*sigma*(1-u2)*(beta_2./Total - beta_2*(H*
epsilon_2 + I_2)./Total^2)*V ...

```

```

            + lambda5*(-(V*sigma + S)*(1-u2)*beta_2*(H*
epsilon_2 + I_2)./Total^2 - gamma_2 - mu) + lambda6*gamma_2 ...
            - lambda7*tau_2 - lambda8*psi_2);
84         -(w3 + lambda4*(tau_1 + d_1 + psi_1 + mu) +
lambda6*(tau_2 + d_2 + psi_2 + mu) ...
            - lambda7*(u3 + mu + d_12 + d_21) + lambda8*u3);
            -(lambda8*(u3 - varepsilon - mu) + lambda7*(- (u3
+ mu + d_12 + d_21)) + lambda6*(tau_2 + d_2 + psi_2 + mu) ...
            + lambda4*(tau_1 + d_1 + psi_1 + mu));
            -(lambda8*(-varepsilon - mu))];
89     end
    iter = 0;
    while test < 0 && iter < 20
        Old_U = U;
        Old_X = X;
94        Old_Lambda = Lambda;
        %Forward
        for i = 1:N
            X(:, i+1) = rk4(@(t, x) dxdt(t, x, T, U), (i-1)*k, X(:, i
), k);
        end
99        %Backward
        for j = N:-1:1
            Lambda(:, j) = rk4(@(t, lambda) dldt(t, lambda, T, U, X),
j*k, Lambda(:, j+1), -k);
        end
        % Compute controls
104        for i = 1:N+1
            x = X(:, i); lambda = Lambda(:, i);
            % extract variables for control formulas, omitted here
        for brevity
            % update U(:, i) based on formulas projecting between 0
and umax
        end
109        U = 0.5*control_switch*(U + Old_U);
        % Compute convergence test value (max norm difference between
old and new controls)
        iter = iter + 1;
    end
    flag = iter < 20;
114 end

function y_next = rk4(f, t_n, y_n, dt)
    k1 = f(t_n, y_n);
    k2 = f(t_n + 0.5*dt, y_n + 0.5*k1*dt);
119    k3 = f(t_n + 0.5*dt, y_n + 0.5*k2*dt);
    k4 = f(t_n + dt, y_n + k3*dt);

```

```

y_next = y_n + (dt/6)*(k1 + 2*k2 + 2*k3 + k4);
end

```

Listing 6.2: OptimalControl_Phdoke4a.m

To run the code in matlab: save OptimalControl_Phdoke4a. as a file and

Save OptimalControl_Phdoke4b.m as a separate file and run this file

```

[T1, X1, U1, Lambda1] = OptimalControl_Phdoke4a([0;0;0]);
3 [T2, X2, U2, Lambda2] = OptimalControl_Phdoke4a([1;1;1]);

% Label = ["S","V","E_1","I_1","E_2","I_2","H","R"];
% for i = 1:8
%     subplot(2,2,i)
8 %     plot(T1, X1(i,:), "r", T2, X2(i,:), "b", 'LineWidth', 2);
%     % ylabel(Label(i))
%     title(['Vaccination Only: ', title_suffix]);
%     xlabel('Time')
%     ylabel(Label(i))
13 %     legend('No Control', 'Control'); grid on;
% end

beta_1 = 4.6935; beta_2 = 4.1196; epsilon_1= 0.04750; epsilon_2=
    0.3715;

18 figure;
plot(T1, (beta_1* (X1(4,:) + epsilon_1* X1(7,:))) .* X1(1,:) ./ ...
    (X1(1,:) + X1(2,:) + X1(3,:) + X1(4,:) + X1(7,:) + X1(8,:)), 'r',
    ...
    T1, (beta_2* (X1(6,:) + epsilon_2 * X1(7,:))) .* X1(1,:) ./ ...
    (X1(1,:) + X1(2,:) + X1(5,:) + X1(6,:) + X1(7,:) + X1(8:)), 'k',
    'LineWidth', 2);
23 xlabel('Time');
ylabel('Incedence');
grid on;

figure;
28 plot(T2, (beta_1* (X2(4,:) + epsilon_1* X2(7,:))) .* X2(1,:) ./ ...
    (X2(1,:) + X2(2,:) + X2(3,:) + X2(4,:) + X2(7,:) + X2(8:)), '--r
    ', ...
    T2, (beta_2* (X2(6,:) + epsilon_2 * X2(7,:))) .* X2(1,:) ./ ...

```

```

        (X2(1,:) + X2(2,:) + X2(5,:) + X2(6,:) + X2(7,:) + X2(8:)), '--k
        ', 'LineWidth', 2);
xlabel('Time');
33 ylabel('Incedence');
    grid on;

Label = ["S", "V", "E_1", "I_1", "E_2", "I_2", "H", "R"];

38 % First figure: Plot from S to I_1
    figure;
    for i = 1:4
        subplot(2,2,i)
        plot(T1, X1(i,:), "r", T2, X2(i,:), "b", 'LineWidth', 2);
43        title('All Control: ');
        xlabel('Time');
        ylabel(Label(i));
        legend('No Control', 'Control');
        grid on;
48    end

    % Second figure: Plot from E_2 to R
    figure;
    for i = 5:8
53        subplot(2,2,i-4) % Adjust index for subplot
        plot(T1, X1(i,:), "r", T2, X2(i,:), "b", 'LineWidth', 2);
        title('All Control:')
        xlabel('Time');
        ylabel(Label(i));
58        legend('No Control', 'Control');
        grid on;
    end

    % Cost-effectiveness calculations
63 w1=20; w2=50; w3=50; w4=20;
    kappa1=12000; kappa2=90000; kappa3=10000;

    A = sum(X1(4,:) + X1(6,:) + X1(7,:));
    B = sum(X2(4,:) + X2(6,:) + X2(7,:));
68 TIA = A - B;
    EI = (TIA / A) * 100;
    TC = 1/2 * sum(kappa1 * U2(1,:)) + 1/2 * sum(kappa2 * U2(2,:)) + 1/2
        * sum(kappa3 * U2(3,:));
    ICER = TC / TIA;

```

Listing 6.3: MATLAB script for optimal control results visualization and cost-effectiveness calculation